

MASTER'S THESIS

Master`s Program in Multicultural and International Education November 2019

Computer-Assisted Language Learning at Higher Secondary Schools in Bangladesh

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Master of Multicultural and International Education (MIE)

MD NAZRUL ISLAM

OsloMet – Oslo Metropolitan University

**Faculty of Education and International Studies
Department of International Studies and Interpreting**

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The researcher fully acknowledges Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet) for its academic support and all other forms. Exceptional support goes out to the management and teaching staff of this University. He highly appreciates prof. Anders Breidlid for taking the excellent class that was amazing and creative. Thanks, prof. Kristin Skinstad, for her influencing guidelines, prof. Ellen Carm was always helpful in each field, and finally, Merethe Skårås, who was his thesis supervisor, she ever tried to assist him so that he could do better in his thesis; he remembers her with great pleasure. Although the researcher was a little problem then, she helped him attend the thesis supervision class via Skype. Special thanks go to the International Office personnel who help him a lot. His deepest thanks go to the government of Norway for putting in place terms and conditions that provide for programs like without tuition fees.

The researcher acknowledges students, teachers, and principals who help him provide information. If they do not cooperate with him, finishing his thesis will not be possible. Thanks to his friends and family, who encourage him to write this thesis. He appreciates all his colleagues who approved his vacation leave to complete this thesis, especially the governing body's chairman.

His colleagues like Kenneth, Tammy, Jacinta, Hamzeh, Joe, and Zohreh were of great worth during some stages of the thesis, especially in the draft thesis. Therefore, he outspreads his heartfelt gratitude to them, but he will always remember Kenneth, whose inspiration helps him finish his thesis.

ABSTRACT

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is one of the most crucial tools and techniques that can help to improve the students' language competencies. This new technology in language education has amplified learner autonomy, creativity, productivity, and group work. The intended use of modern educational technology can increase both learning and teaching, and the introduction of the computer into foreign language instruction appears to conform to the statement. The world is heading towards a knowledge of the economy, and much money will be provided for Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL). However, the investment will be successful if the students, teachers, and administrators can comprehend the importance of it and the teachers can execute the system properly. Active CALL requires teachers to select the appropriate resources and tools based on learners' levels and needs. So, teachers' training is essential for the successful implementation of CALL. This study explores the schools' existing facilities, problems, and future possibilities in Bangladesh. The study accompanies to find answers to three central research questions. The theory of behaviorism and social constructivism uses to investigate the data. The analysis finds that schools in Bangladesh need more facilities for CALL because of available funds. The students are eager to use technology in language learning, but the teachers must be trained in CALL and its benefits. They need to learn of different uses of the internet and other e-tools for language teaching. So, they need different sorts of training that will be effective for them. The heads of schools react positively to the future development of teachers through training. This study suggests that trained teachers, the assistance of institutions, and available funds are essential to implement CALL at higher secondary schools in Bangladesh.

Keywords: *Technology, foreign language, instruction, system, resources, behaviorism, social constructivism, policymakers.*

Abbreviations

ADB	Asian Development Bank
BAL	Bangladesh Awami League
BIAM	Bangladesh Institute of Administration and Management
BIDE	Bangladesh Institute of Distance Education
BNP	Bangladesh Nationalist Party
BNU	Bangladesh National University
BOU	Bangladesh Open University
BRAC	Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee
CAI	Computer Assisted Instruction
CALL	Computer Assisted Language Learning
CALT	Computer Assisted Language Teaching
CLT	Communicative Language Teaching
CMC	Computer-Mediated Communication
EFL	English as a Foreign Language
ESL	English as a Second Language
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GEM	Global Education Monitoring
HSC	Higher Secondary School Certificate
HTML	Hyper Text Markup Language
IER	Institute of Education and Research
IT	Information Technology
MKO	More Knowledgeable Other
NAEM	National Academy of Educational Management
NBC	Network-Based Communication
NBLT	Network-Based Language Teaching
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NIEAR	National Institute of Education, Administration, Extension and Research
PACE	Post Primary and Continued Education
PDP	Parallel Distributed Processing
PLATO	Programmed Logic for Automated Teaching Operation
SAC	Self-Access Centre
SDT	Social Development Theory

SNC	Social Networking Communities
SSC	Secondary School Certificate
TEFL	Teaching English as a Foreign Language
TELL	Test of English Language Learning
TESOL	Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages
TQI	Teaching Quality Improvement
TTC	Teachers Training College
ZPD	Zone of Proximal Development

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	II
Abstract	III
Abbreviations	IV
Table of Contents	VI
1. Introduction	1
1.1 Contextual framework of the study	2
1.1.1 epistemology of the study and brief history of the context	2
1.1.2 The political culture	3
1.1.3 The main phases of education and teachers training.....	4
1.1.4 The major categories of education	5
1.1.5 English as a subject and foreign language	5
1.2 Rationale	6
1.3 Purpose of the study	7
1.4 Objectives of the study	7
1.5 Research questions	7
1.6 Structure of the thesis	8
2. Background and Literature review	9
2.1 CALL and CALT	9
2.1.1 History of behaviorist CALL	10
2.1.2 Communicative and cognitive CALL	11
2.1.3 Socio-cognitive CALL	11
2.1.4 Social constructivism	12
2.2 Necessity of CALL	13
2.3 Computer-mediated communication	14
2.4 Self-access center	16
2.5 Blog	17
2.6 Podcast	18
2.6.1 How to create and use podcast	19
2.7 Social-networking websites: Facebook	20
2.8 Other social-networking sites	21
2.8.1 E-mail	21
2.8.2 Skype	21

2.8.3	Listserv	21
2.8.4	Wiki	21
2.9	The virtual world: distance education	21
2.10	E-learning	23
2.10.1	Scenarios of e-learning for Bangladesh	23
2.10.2	Challenges in E-learning	24
2.11	Teacher training	24
3.	Theoretical Framework and Conceptual Framework	28
3.1	Theoretical framework	28
3.1.1	Behaviorist theory	28
3.1.2	Social constructivism (development) theory	31
3.2	Conceptual framework	33
4.	Research Methodology	38
4.1	Introduction	38
4.2	Research design	38
4.3	Research process	41
4.4	Location selection	41
4.5	Gaining access	42
4.6	Sample selection	42
4.6.1	Research participants	44
4.7	Semi-structured observation	46
4.8	Interview preparations	47
4.9	Interview guides	47
4.10	Setting	47
4.11	Interviews	48
4.11.1	Focus group discussion	48
4.11.2	Teachers and principals' interview	52
4.12	Data analysis	53
4.13	Ethical concerns	54
4.13.1	Informed consent	55
4.14	Trustworthiness in the study	56
4.14.1	Transferability	57
4.14.2	Credibility	58

4.14.3	Conformability	58
4.14.4	Dependability	59
4.14.5	Authenticity	59
4.15	Limitations	59
5.	Findings	61
5.1	Purpose of using technology	61
5.1.1	Students' perspective of using technology	61
5.1.2	Teachers' perspective of using technology	62
5.2	Technology for language teaching and learning	62
5.2.1	Students' perspectives	62
5.2.2	Teachers' perspectives	63
5.2.3	Homework	64
5.2.4	Internet and social network	64
5.3	Teachers role in using technology	64
5.3.1	Problems in using technology	65
5.3.2	Mobile technology for language learning	65
5.4	Language website for learning a language	66
5.4.1	Distraction from a particular website	66
5.4.2	Comparison of web materials and real materials	66
5.5	Suggestions and future possibilities	67
5.5.1	Suggestions	67
5.5.2	The possibilities for future language learning	68
6.	Discussion	70
6.1	Overview	70
6.2	Discussion based on research questions	71
6.3	Discussion based on theoretical framework	72
7.	Summary and conclusion	76
7.1	Introduction	76
7.2	Summary of the findings	76
7.3	Contribution to research	77
7.4	Practical implication	77
7.5	Recommendations	77
7.6	Further studies	77

7.7 Conclusion	78
Bibliography	79
Appendix	91
Appendix 1: Interview guides focus group interview	91
Appendix 2: Interview guides for individual interview (Teachers)	92
Appendix 3: Interview guides for individual interview (Heads)	93
Appendix 4: Participants list	94
Appendix 5: Research sites on the map	95

1. INTRODUCTION

This qualitative research aims to explore and analyze how and to what extent teachers and students use technology for language learning, its challenges, and the future possibilities in Bangladesh. The study explains the keen interest in combining different methodologies with instructional techniques that promise to motivate students and respond effectively to their needs (Mahrooqi & Troudi, 2014). Technology-mediated language learning is an alternative that many higher secondary institutions have begun to investigate as a way to remove the difficulties. Till now, there has been reluctance in higher education societies to integrate technologies due to an inability of the techniques to deliver the amount and quality of interpersonal communication. It is central to facilitating higher-order thinking abilities such as that advanced in small group discussions, Socratic dialogue, collaborative learning, brainstorming, debriefing, case analyses, and problem-based learning. This scenario, however, has altered. The type of communication considered central to many educators can be prolonged through new communication technologies such as computer-mediated language learning and teaching. In specific applications, these technologies are also proving to be cost-effective and user-friendly to language students experiencing time, place, or situational drawbacks (Bates, 1995) and, at the same time, supporting the development of higher-order thinking skills (Newman, Webb & Cochrane, 1995; Bullen, 1997). For these reasons, many higher secondary institutions are assimilating communication and instructional technologies into their language teaching agendas. Though how successful technology-mediated language learning activities will facilitate higher-order thinking skills, and it will be reliant upon the method taken to the design, delivery, selection, and utilization of appropriate and efficient technologies with a support structure to maintain and sustain the language learning transactions (Pisel, 1995; Schreiber, 1998). It often demands educators to obtain new perspectives in some diverse areas - one of which is a philosophical orientation to language teaching and learning. One's philosophical orientation will order how educators view teaching, learning, knowledge (Darkenwald & Merriam, 1982), and the use of technology.

Furthermore, while one's working philosophy will not undertake problems educators encounter when integrating technologies, it can assist in understanding and guiding decision-making. According to Darkenwald and Merriam, the result is intentional and informed repetition, where decisions regarding the application of technologies are made more studiously and rationally. Educators who simplify and articulate their philosophical position about using technologies in the language learning process inform what they are doing as they use technologies to facilitate language learning and why.

A research paper shows that a student in Bangladesh spends about 1600 hours learning English before getting into university, where 1000 hours the instructional time is enough to become proficient in a language (Rahman, 1998). However, they cannot interact in English even after spending many hours learning English. So, it is essential to examine the present situation, challenges, and future options for computer-assisted language learning and teaching, although there are few researchers in this field. However, more is needed to assume actual

conditions in Bangladesh. This study endeavored to find out the existing facilities of the schools and students, teachers, and heads' behavior towards technology. It also focused on students, teachers, and principals' opinions regarding CALL. Finally, the researcher discusses behaviorism and social constructivism theory with epistemology and other philosophies to establish the research findings.

1.1 Contextual framework of the study

In this section, the researcher discusses the brief history of the context of the study (1.1.1), the political culture of the main political parties (1.1.2), the education system and mainstream of education (1.1.3), significant categories of education (1.1.4) and English as a subject and foreign language at the higher secondary school (1.1.5).

1.1.1 Epistemology of the study and brief history of the context

In this section, the study discusses the epistemology of the study in the first paragraph and a few subsequent paragraphs on the brief history of the Bangladeshi context of education.

The hegemony of Western knowledge originates from a specific way European intellectuals, academics, scientists, teachers, and writers have described the 'Orient'. The concept of knowledge about the 'Orient' and the 'Oriental' have been generated and created out of an unequal power relationship (Said 2003, p.40). Tucker (1999) describes that this has created a description and understanding of countries and societies in the South based on "historical imagination," where cultures are reduced to frozen stereotypes, and where development discourses have been used to legitimize human exploitation, colonialism, slavery, and genocide (p.8). Western epistemology's hegemonic position is linked to what can be described as the 'global architecture of education.' Jones (2007) describes the global architecture of education as a "complex web of ideas, networks of influence, policy frameworks and practices, financial arrangements, and organizational structures—a system of global power relations that exerts a heavy, even determining, influence on how education is constructed around the world" (p.325). He describes that much of today's professional and academic life can be understood regarding the global reach of transnational academic and epistemic communities and networks. Academic and epistemic communities and systems interact with states, multinational organizations, civil society, and the private sector to influence policy development and implementation through research and methods of creating and confirming knowledge (p.330). Knowledge production about the South is carried out in an unequal power relationship where resourceful Western scholars too often conduct studies about the South.

In contrast, Southern scholars need more resources to review the South and the West/North. This knowledge production has resulted in scholars, students, and people in the South "can no longer recognize themselves in the discourses that claim to portray them" (Tucker, 1999, p.13). According to Breidlid (2013), it creates an epistemological gap in teaching methods and contents in classrooms in today's South. The contents and methods are only "minor adaptations of what is being taught in the West/North," making it difficult for South students to understand. Because "their own cultures and worldviews are seldom, if ever,"

considered "beyond their folkloristic aspects" (Breidlid, 2013, pp. 2-3). Vavrus (2009) confirms this by describing how teacher students struggled to transform theoretical knowledge demonstrated in class to practice because they did not have "a cultural framework in which to place the discourse and methods used in our class" (p.306).

After almost 200 years of colonial period from 1947 to 1971, East Pakistan (present Bangladesh) was West Pakistani (current Pakistan) colony. When the Pakistani regime was established to rule East Pakistan, West Pakistan made new primary schools, and primary schoolgoers increased significantly. In East Pakistan, both primary school and schoolgoers decreased. The graph shows the primary school availability in East and West Pakistan from 1950 to 1971. It assumes that East Pakistan was deprived of education at that time in primary education but also all levels of education.

Figure 1: School-going students aged 5-14 (Islam, 2023, p.2072)

Educational disparities in undivided Pakistan were systematic; they should have prevailed at all levels of education. Barring only two categories, Arts and Science colleges, and teacher training academies, West Pakistan had a complete advantage in the obtainability of higher education facilities. Given the primary backwardness of the Eastern wing, one would have expected some equalization in regional supplies in the later years, for instance, through the greater allocation of new units to East Pakistan. Nonetheless, data reveals a further divergence in higher education structure instead. Altogether, the status in primary and post-primary schooling confirms the conjecture of systematic educational inequalities and hegemonic behavior between East and West Pakistan at almost all levels of education.

1.1.2 The political culture

In this section, the investigator analyses the hegemonic political culture of Bangladesh. After nine months of the freedom fight, Bangladesh became independent in 1971. From 1975 to 1991 army ruled the country, and there were various movements when the education system was not prioritized. Then overcoming the military regime, it returned to civil law in 1991, and Bangladesh started a multi-party parliamentary democratic system. However, the political culture and stability of democratic institutions have been marked since the beginning because of hostility and continuous violence between the two main political parties, namely the current ruling party Bangladesh Awami League (BAL) and Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP). Both

parties have dispositional attributions and cannot leave out their intrinsic factors (Breidlid, 2013). According to the Global Education Monitoring (GEM) Report (country case, 2017), the concentration of power in the hands of a few people or offices (for instance, the Prime Minister's Office), factional politics in the institutions, and the absence of opposition from the Parliament leading to fragile checks and balances have had a severe impact on the policy domain. As a result, there was no accountability, quality monitoring, or equity and equality.

1.1.3 The main phases of education and teachers' training

Education in Bangladesh has three main phases - primary, secondary, and higher education. Another stream of education in Bangladesh is Kindergarten education or pre-primary education aged 3 to 5 years. According to the researcher's experience, it is not regulated by the government. Primary school is a 5-year cycle, whereas secondary education is a 7-year. There are three sub-cycles in secondary education: junior secondary for three years, secondary education for two years, and higher secondary education (college) for two years. The entry age for primary school is six years. The junior secondary 11-13 years, secondary 14-15, and higher secondary stage 16-17-year age are designed for students. Higher secondary is followed by higher education in general, technical, and medical streams requiring 5 to 6 years to obtain a master's degree. According to the National Education Policy (2010), primary education is an 8-year cycle, and secondary education is a 4-year cycle (p. 6 & 14). However, it is still in progress. Hossain (2010) categorizes secondary school into three sub-categories-junior secondary (grade 6 to 8), secondary (grade 9 to 10), and higher secondary (grade 11 to 12). Breidlid (2005c) states,

A national curriculum constructs a national identity where absolute cultural values are promoted while others are not. Such a selection is indeed very contentious because it most certainly means that the cultural heritage of many schoolchildren is not being valued (p. 251).

In Bangladesh, there are 116 Teacher Training Colleges (TTCs) (15 government and 101 private) that offer 1-year Bachelor of Education (B. Ed) degree to secondary school teachers (Pouzevara & Khan, 2007, p. 11). In addition to these TTCs, NIEAR (National Institute of Education, Administration, Extension and Research), IER (Institute of Education and Research), BIDE (Bangladesh Institute of Distance Education), NAEM (National Academy of Educational Management) and some other private institutions provide training for the teachers of secondary level. Still, there needs to be sometimes training with English specialists training English teachers (Rahman, 1998, p. 99). Teachers hardly receive any training for teaching a particular subject, so they show in the classrooms through age-old methods and techniques (Khan, 2005, p. 119). Moreover, the syllabuses of real training focus more on the theoretical aspects of the teaching method.

Consequently, the trainees cannot utilize their knowledge in the classroom (Rahman, 1998; Yasmeen, 2005). Unluckily, policymakers need to pay more attention to these subjects that make a gap between the understanding of training and the things practiced. At present, ADB (Asian Development Bank) is funding TQI-SEP 2005-2011 (Teaching Quality Improvement in Secondary Education Project), which provides training to all eligible teachers of grades 6-10 in government and private schools (Pouzevara & Khan, 2007, p. 13). Some

government projects like ELTIP and PERC for secondary and primary English teachers also exist. Still, a lack of coordination in these projects is often responsible for not achieving the expected result (Khan, 2005, p. 120). To compensate for this lack, BRAC, an NGO, has developed a project named PACE (Post Primary and Continued Education), where the local authorities train secondary English teachers and teacher trainers (Khan). It shows that there is no pre-service training for the teachers of higher secondary level except the three months of training provided by one higher secondary teacher training college to their teachers. From Quader's (2005) report, it has been discovered that the training takes place in several venues like the Bangladesh Institute of Administration and Management (BIAM) and some other sites. Conversely, none of the abovementioned training educates teachers about technology and its advantages.

1.1.4 The major categories of education

The education system of Bangladesh is mainly divided into three major categories—general education, madrasa education, and vocational education (Anwar, 2006). “Primary education, secondary education, and tertiary education are the three parts of general education” (Pouzevara & Khan, 2007, p.9). Primary schooling, managed by the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, is consisted of grades 1 to 5 (Pouzevara and Khan). The learners who get their higher secondary certificate (HSC) can enroll in tertiary education. They can attend a 3-year degree course in a degree-level college or a 4-year honors course based on their capacity and interest (Patra et al., 2010). There are a total of 88 universities in Bangladesh—31 public universities and 54 private universities¹. Bangladesh National University (BNU) and Bangladesh Open University (BOU) are two particular universities; where the first one offers university courses in affiliation with different colleges, and the latter provides non-campus distance education (Patra et al., 2010). Besides private universities, two international universities provide world-class standard education (Patra et al.). Madrasa education is very similar to general knowledge, but the second phase is Dakhil, and the higher secondary stage is Alim (Anwar, 2006). After completing the primary level, technical and vocational courses are offered in professional and trade institutes. (Patra et al. 2010)

1.1.5 English as a subject and foreign language

According to National Curriculum, English is a compulsory subject from grades I to XII; among them, grades I to V one hundred marks, grades VI to VIII (Junior School Certificate-JSC) 150 marks, and grades IX to X (Secondary School Certificate-SSC) and grades XI to XII (Higher Secondary Certificate-HSC) 200 marks. In the next paragraph, the researcher discusses English as a foreign language teaching and learning with a few citations.

Over the period, researchers have demonstrated that different ways of integrating computer use into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching have different effects on learning. Since the internet has a global reach and provides extensive international resources, teachers can access helpful language resources for preparing materials for language classes. Teaching English is not only chalking and talking but making students communicate

¹ <http://www.ugc.gov.bd/university/?action=public>

effectively. With the progress of information and communication technology, computers and the internet have become increasingly important in education. Despite this development, computer education for teachers faces significant challenges. “Computer has become an influential part of language teaching because of the rapid growth of technology” (Gardner & Miller, 1999, p.1). At present, “language teaching can hardly be done without the assistance of computer technology” (Jones, 2001, p. 360). Students expect computers among the available facilities for language courses, and teachers and administrators realize that computer-assisted language courses are more attractive than traditional language courses (Jones). Since the early 1960s, language teachers have witnessed dramatic changes in language use and teaching (Kern & Warschauer, 2000). In Bangladesh, computer-assisted language learning (CALL) is quite a familiar concept in some private schools in urban areas. However, all schools may need the necessary infrastructure for computer-assisted language learning (CALL). Even if they have, their teachers may need to gain the knowledge and skills to use technology for language teaching. Bangladesh is now a developing country, so there are a lot of challenges in the field of computer-assisted language teaching on the one hand, and there are some possibilities on the other side.

1.2 Rationale

Over the past several decades, studies analyzing the relationship between computer and EFL learning have refined to focus on several critical issues, including motivation and governing the necessary skills. While computers have been accessible among language teachers since the 1960s, their usefulness has been amplified by the development of Internet-based technologies. With the emergence of CALL, Network-Based Language Teaching (NBLT) or online teaching has also become popular, where teaching involves using computers connected to local or global networks (Kern & Warschauer, 2000). This form of teaching and learning is also known as “computer-mediated communication” (CMC) (Simpson, 2002). Educators recognize that utilizing computer technology and CALL programs can be convenient for creating both independent and collaborative learning environments (Lai & Kritsonis, 2006). According to Warschauer et al. (2014), technology is increasingly a core component of teacher training courses for language teachers across all educational levels in both the state and private sectors. Most language teaching positions now require knowledge of the theory and practice of learning technologies and digital literacy skills. However, the successful implementation of any technology requires considerable effort by teachers and administrators (Timucin, 2006). Jones (2001) believes that CALL cannot be regarded solely as a "self-access operation"; and commitment is very crucial for the successful execution of CALL. Warschauer (2000), however, has supported the use of technology despite some disadvantages for two reasons. Firstly, using computers for education is comparable to using books or print, and if there is no debate on the prior, discussing using the latter is useless. Secondly, students need to learn the language of technology (e-mails, conducting web research) to survive in times awaiting them; technology has to be used "as a legitimate medium of communication in its right".

Therefore, the way to obtain a glimpse of the perceptions of the benefit of the Test of English Language Learning (TELL) and CALL on students' language learning is to help

teachers to clarify their goals. Examine technology choices made by language teachers, and observe and interview teachers and students while using the computer to determine the strengths and weaknesses of its perceived effects.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The overall purpose is to study Computer-Assisted Language Learning at the Higher Secondary School in Bangladesh. The increasing need for the CALL program for more helpful language teaching and learning classes encourages teachers and students to experiment with new methods and digital tools. Digital equipment as an innovative technology can increase the students' awareness regarding their processes of knowledge construction and support their lifelong learning experiences.

1.4 Objectives of the study

Research suggests that integrating modern technology can yield positive results and improve learning. Learning English by computer encourages students to learn the language, develops their ability to use the word, and helps them overcome the language barrier. So, the objectives of this study are:

- Objective-1** *to focus on the various uses of technology that teachers adopt to enhance language skills,*
- Objective-2** *to define the challenges in using technology,*
- Objective-3** *to demonstrate the possibilities of technology enhancement in teaching English, and*
- Objective-4** *to provide a research-based guide to solving problems that students face in using technology.*

So far as the researcher knows, there is no such kind of research work in existence anywhere- either at home or abroad; precisely, he proposes research work entitled "Computer-Assisted Language Learning at the Higher Secondary School (College) in Bangladesh." This research will help to understand the views of teachers and students about using technology in EFL teaching and learning. As qualitative forms I do this research, it takes the shape of a unique and vibrant way of study that, he considers, will serve as a source for further investigations of all these types.

1.5 Research questions

1. How and to what extent do teachers and students use technology in teaching and learning processes related to language learning in Bangladesh?
2. What are the challenges of computer-assisted language teaching and learning in Bangladesh?

3. What are the prospects of computer-assisted language teaching and learning in Bangladesh?

1.6 Structure of the thesis

This study is arranged into seven chapters, beginning with the introductory chapter. The practical aim of the study resulted in a decision to organize the analysis around a theoretical framework. The framework structure describes the implementation of Computer-Assisted Language Learning and Teaching with institutional and individual experiences.

Chapter 2 Background and Literature review

Chapter 3 Theoretical Framework/Conceptual framework

Chapter 4 Research Methodology

Chapter 5 Findings

Chapter 6 Discussion

Chapter 7 Summary and conclusion

2. BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, the researcher discusses the background of the CALL program and related literature on CALL. So far, the researcher has studied computer-assisted language learning, which he discusses here and relates to his findings. Nowadays, technology has become a vital part, and people can only go with the assistance of modern inventions. Computers and other modern facilities already dominate education in developed countries, and developing countries like Bangladesh are also heading towards that. However, while leading to a technology-enhanced education system, Bangladesh may need more equipment and trained teachers (Akhter, 2012). This research attempts to determine the present condition of computer-assisted language learning and teaching. As a part of that endeavor, some recent and past research findings have been accumulated in this chapter to analyze different aspects of computer-assisted language teaching and learning and some related e-tools for better understanding. Finally, he discusses the CALL and CALT in subsection 2.1, Necessity of CALL 2.2, in-person interaction vs. computer-mediated communication 2.3, self-access center 2.4, blog 2.5, podcast 2.6, Facebook in language teaching 2.7, other tools of language learning 2.8, the virtual world 2.9, E-learning and distance education perspectives 2.10 and teacher training on CALL 2.11.

2.1 CALL and CALT

With the recent introduction of modern technologies, Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) has appeared as an attractive alternative to the traditional mode of teaching (Ehsani & Knodt, 1998). However, there is no widespread demarcation of CALL. Different academics illustrate it in their style. Leffa (2009) outlines CALL as,

A cultural artifact with the resource on its own, including higher connectivity and interactivity. It integrates with other learning community components, transforming how teachers and students work and think. From this common perspective, teaching and learning become a unified activity, distributed not only among the community members but also among the artifacts available in the environment (p. 40).

Beatty (2003) says that CALL is the process of using computers in learning, which results in the learner's language development. Timucin (2006) states that Computer-assisted language learning involves using technology in the form of a "computer and transformation process of the institutions where the changes take place" (p. 262). Computer-assisted language teaching (CALT) is the study of a function on the computer in language teaching and learning (Levy, 1997). It is now used routinely in various instructional situations (Fotos & Browne, 2004). As a result, teachers are increasingly essential to keep CALL skill that comprises both real-world skills and a thorough consideration of information technology (IT) theory. CALL authorizes learners to control their speed of learning and interaction with others (Fotos & Browne). Jones and Fortescue (in Gunduz 2005) narrate that in a CALL setting, a computer is an adaptable classroom aid that can be used both by faculties and students inside or outside the classroom in various ways. After analyzing all these definitions, CALL is an approach to teaching and

learning where computer and computer-mediated facilities present, reinforce and assess materials to learn and include interactive elements.

Computers have been recycled for language schooling since the 1960s in the US. The history of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) can be roughly divided into three main stages: Structural or behaviouristic CALL, communicative CALL, and integrative CALL (Warschauer, 2000).

Every step looks like a certain level of technology and a particular educational method. Computers have been recycled for language teaching for over three decades (Gunduz, 2005). For this reason, CALL certainly needs to be looked at in-depth of its story to comprehend its development. For example, Kern and Warschauer (2000) categorize the antiquity of CALL into three phases—behaviorist CALL, cognitive CALL, and socio-cognitive CALL.

2.1.1 History of behaviorist CALL

In this section, the investigator discusses how the old teaching method is replaced by behaviorist CALL chronologically and involves technology to implement this theory. The primary step of CALL programs, consisting of grammar and vocabulary tutorials and drills, returned to America in the 1960s when mainframe computers were in tendency (Kern & Warschauer, 2000, p. 8). Those programs were then mentioned as Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) (Gunduz, 2005). Bangs and Cantos (2004) state that the first CALL software was established at Stanford University. Some years later, in 1968, the University of New York developed CALL software for the German language. However, the most ambitious CALL project PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automated Teaching Operation), was propelled at the University of Illinois (Bangs and Cantos).

Photo 1: Early PLATO lab, 1975²

² Source: <http://etec.cflt.ubc.ca/510wiki/File:PLATOlabor.jpg>

The 1970s witnessed a revolution of CALL because of development in research related to the use of computers for scientific purposes (Gunduz, 2005). Between the 1960s and 1970s, the CALL programs contained repeated drilling on the same materials, positive and negative feedback, and focused on accuracy consistent with the behaviorist method (Kern & Warshauer, 2000). At that time, behaviorist theory was occupied as the theoretical base of CALL, and computers began to be considered a technical help and an alternative to outdated teaching.

2.1.2 Communicative and cognitive CALL

Communicative CALL is based on a cognitive approach in that learners build new knowledge by exploring their surroundings and employing their existing knowledge (Kern & Warshauer, 2000). Throughout the 1980s, the behaviorist approach was banned by the defendants of Communicative Language Learning (CLL), and personal computers were also creating more excellent opportunities for work (Gunduz, 2005). The computer provided tools and resources, but it was up to the learners to do something in a computer-generated environment. The focus was on more than what forms students learned from the computer but on how they did use the forms while functioning on computers (Gunduz, 2005, p. 198). By the 1990s, cognitive approaches began to criticize. The socio-cognitive approach to CALL moved the importance from learners' interaction with computers to learners' interaction with each other via computers (Kern & Warshauer, 2000). Technologically there was a significant development in computer networking. As a result, internet browsing, email communication, chat rooms, and presentation have become more popular among teachers and students (Bangs & Cantos, 2004). This approach led teachers to use "the more learner-centered and interactive method in the authentic social context" (Gunduz, 2005, p. 199). Students learned and utilized various language skills interactively and were enabled to use different computer tools for learning rather than visiting a computer lab once a week for quarantined exercise. Bax (2003) disagrees with the phases of Kern and Warshauer (2000) as he locates some flaws in the classification. So, he suggests renaming the stages to eradicate the confusion. He renamed behaviorist CALL as restricted CALL, cognitive CALL as open CALL, and integrative CALL as integrated CALL.

2.1.3 Socio-cognitive CALL

Hjørland (2004) says that socio-cognitive approaches stress the role of culturally produced signs and symbols and how cultural, historical, and socially created meanings mediate cognitive processes. Such an approach is beneficial for describing integrated cognitive and social possessions of systems, methods, functions, models, and socio-cognitive collaborations (Hemingway & Gough, 1998). Hjørland (2004) further states that in traditional cognitive science, the role of culture and society in cognition is marginalized; Understanding personal cognitive focus on symbolic representations is insufficient. Traditional cognitive science increased the importance of the semantic and pragmatic study to display how human and technological factors and organizational behaviors had been combined. With socio-cognitive methods to CALL, we transport from learners' interaction with computers to communicate with

other humans via the computer network. This new approach to CALL is based on theoretical and technological developments. Cognitive and social resources are shared. Thus, Gadomski (2002) mentions that it becomes crucial to understand how cognitive properties of the mechanisms of the socio-cognitive systems and invariant social interrelations are networked to establish their behavior. Theoretically, there has been the broader importance of meaningful interaction in authentic discourse societies. Technologically, computer networking has grown, allowing the computer to be used as a vehicle for cooperating human communication. Machines can play as mediation instruments that shape the ways we interact with the world (e.g., accessing and organizing data through databases, spreadsheets, and word processors). Word processors, for instance, facilitate the innovation, revision, and editing processes of writing, allowing rapid, easy (and reversible) reshaping of text. Gadomski (1997) narrates that systemic socio-cognitive metaphysics as focusing only on the observable (as well as by introspection) tasks of the human brain in cognitive and social relationships. Van Dijk (2009) defines discourse as a socio-cognitive edge for the discursive communication of relations between the mind and society.

Furthermore, the socio-cognitive method, as an interdisciplinary perspective, presents the systematic relationship between fluctuations of the semantic group and the socio-demography of a community (Robinson, 2010). The purpose of programs based on this socio-cognitive approach was to permit the learner to restructure the original texts and, in the development, to grow their constructions of language. Computer networking tolerates a powerful extension of the computer-as-tool, enabling access to other people, information, and data.

The computer can play numerous roles in language teaching and learning. It was invented on the mainframe as a tutor that delivers language maneuvers or skill rehearsal. The advent of multimedia technology on the individual computer aids as a space to survey and creatively impact microworlds. Furthermore, the development of computer networks now assists as a medium of local and global communication and a basis for authentic materials. This diversity of roles has taken CALL far elsewhere, the early "electronic workbook" variety of software that dominated the second and foreign language arena for years and has opened up new domains in foreign language teaching.

2.1.4 Social constructivism

Lev Vygotsky's (1978) theory of social constructivism (in Pritchard and Wollard, 2010) states that human learners depend on social communication for stimulus, challenges, and shared activity to promote thinking and engagement with ideas and knowledge. "Knowledge is profoundly a social activity" (Pritchard & Wollard, 2010, p. 34). Pritchard and Wollard (2010) determine three significant points from this theory. People around the learner have a central role in learning; they influence how learners see the world, and specific tools affect learning and intellectual development progress. Likewise, Randall and Thornton (2001) also agree with some essential concepts of the Vygotskian theory of learning. It is to be noticed that they connect this theory to teacher education, reflecting teachers as learners and teacher educators as a skilled individual. Their points are as follows-

- *Knowledge is constructed by interacting with a learner and a more specialist individual.*
- *Initially, knowledge exists on an inter-psychological plane (in social interaction), then transferred to an intra-psychological plane (in learners' minds).*
- *Learning of new ideas or "appropriation" occurs when the new designs are moved from the inter- to intra-psychological level.*
- *For each learner (here teachers), some concepts and skills exist 'on the edge' of their knowledge, known as their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). They can deal with these concepts or skills if they get help from more experts (like teacher educators or advisors).*
- *Helping a student-teacher through ZPD and "appropriate" a new concept is called scaffolding. The advisor can assist teachers in this process through discussion. (Randall and Thornton, 2001)*

Beck and Kosnik (2006) think that social constructivism is an approach that can help deal with the challenges and tensions of teacher education since it encourages all the members of a learning community to present their ideas actively while remaining open to Others. Based on that, the institution and authorities play an essential role in the development of teacher education. Clarke and Hollingsworth (in Geijsel et al., 2009) say that it is crucial to consider teachers as learners and the institution as a learning community for teachers' development. Beck and Kosnik (2006) believe that teacher education is so vital that authorities should give it more time, resources, and efforts to develop teachers' experience and professional skills. Constructing own knowledge is also vital in social constructivism, as new knowledge can only be learned by linking it to the existing culture (Dewey in Beck and Kosnik, 2006). Conversely, Geijsel et al. (2009, p. 410) believe that since social constructivism views learning as a process involving every member of a learning community, teachers' participation in decision-making can add to the teachers' sense of "self-efficacy" and thus motivate their learning. The authors also mention that psychological factors and background knowledge are vital for education, and the organizational organization also matters in learning.

Student-teachers should have time and encouragement to reflect on their learning (Beck & Kosnik, 2006). With backing and support, teachers develop a teaching style that fits their needs and talent. As an example of a teacher's construction of pedagogy, Beck and Kosnik also argue that teachers' approach to technology in education. Their main point is that teachers who are comfortable with technology tend to make it central in their way of teaching. In contrast, those with a negative experience with technology pick discussion, reading, and so forth as their primary teaching tool. They again mention that though the teachers must use technology as much as possible, "allowing differences to degree facilitates optimal teacher development and performance."

2.2 Necessity of CALL

Nowadays, language teaching, learning, and all walks of life depend on technology. For this reason, the researcher discusses the necessity of computer-assisted language learning in this subsection.

Lai and Kritsonis (2006) mention that computers and language programs connected to them can give learners more freedom than outdated language classes. Lee (2000) positions that teachers should include the computer in the second language classroom as it can-

- *Motivate students better than the traditional method of teaching.*
- *Enhance learners' accomplishment.*
- *Rise authentic resources for study.*
- *Inspire more significant interaction among teachers, students, and peers;*
- *Stress individual needs.*
- *Increase global understanding.*

Lai and Kritsonis (2006) consider that a computer can provide learners with many fun games and communicative actions that decrease learners' stress and anxiety. Through communicative activities, computer-assisted language learning can help learners improve their linguistic abilities, affect their attitudes toward language learning, and shape their self-confidence. Robertson et al. (in Lai and Kritsonis, 2006) note that computer-assisted language program learners have higher self-esteem ratings than regular students.

Taylor and Gitsaki (2003) study that in a well-designed computer-assisted language program, the teachers can get necessary information regarding learners' development and provide feedback according to learners' necessity. Likewise, students can get authentic materials at school or home, which can be accessed 24 hours a day by connecting to the internet (Lai & Kritsonis, 2006). Introvert or quiet learners will be benefited from individualized technology-assisted learning, and academic learners can also work at their speed to attain a higher level (Lai and Kritsonis).

Warschauer (1996) argues that in the late 1980s, computer-assisted language programs started to become popular in the USA for teaching confirmation. The author considers some motivations the teachers get from computer-assisted teaching, including the desire to provide reliable communication partners, the acknowledgment of the importance of cultural exchange, and "the aspiration to teach new learning skills to the language marginal students."

2.3 Computer-mediated communication (CMC)

CMC is an umbrella term that denotes human communication via computers (Simpson, 2002). Piloting a study on 16 ESL students of a community college in Hawaii, Warschauer (1996) comes up with the following conclusions,

- *During in face-to-face conversations, one or two students appear to dominate the floor; CMC features a more balanced contribution, with each student sharing their thoughts equally; students can find explicit themselves comfortably and artistically during the electronic discussion;*
- *They use more proper and complex expressions in an electronic debate than face-to-face argument. It may help them to obtain a more sophisticated communicative ability.*

- *Japanese students hardly participate in face-to-face discussions, whereas they participate more equally in online debates. Instead, it emphasizes the significance of students' cultural backgrounds.*
- *The students who lack verbal fluency participate more in the online discussion.*
- *Online discussions have few interactional features, such as questioning, confirmation check, and rephrasing, often found in face-to-face interaction. (Warschauer)*

Pillettieri (2000) states that students feel less anxiety about participation during chatting, stimulating them to produce more of the target language. Chatting can also progress in sociolinguistic and interactive competence. Kern (in Pillettieri 2000) also says that students use various discourse buildings in electronic discussion. The verb form and clause type variety are more significant in an electronic debate than in an oral discussion. Pillettieri (2000) thinks that network-based communication (NBC) can perform an essential role in the development of analytical capability because, in this medium of communication, students have more time to practice and monitor the "interlanguage" (p. 83). He also says that synchronous NBC tasks should be goal-oriented and planned so that all participants are necessitated to communicate with each other for the successful completion of the assignment. However, Chun and Plass (2000) stress the sociolinguistic phases of language as they imagine that by having the opportunity to communicate through a different medium, learners are challenged to process information beyond their grammatical and syntactic competence.

The students involved in synchronous communication, mainly online conversation, realize that they need to think and perform as quickly as they do in face-to-face interaction. Weininger and Shield (2001, p. 89) believe that CMC is "constrained by temporal limitations." Schewinhorst (2002) discovers the repetition of messages in synchronous communication though technically, it is redundant since the previous notes are available on the screen. However, the author states that redundancy may be used to get more time for decoding the last message. Formulaic languages are also used more frequently in CMC than face-to-face interaction to save time while typing (Levy, 2008, p. 7). To confirm active CALL, teachers must balance approaches, resources, and tools to meet learners' needs in a particular context (Levy). To accomplish that balance, the instructors must know how to organize technological resources and combine them with face-to-face teacher-student and student-student interaction (Levy). In this regard, Sotillo (2000) can be cited as,

In the hands of professors who know what they are doing, online instruction is superior to face-to-face interaction. As a result, the synchronous electronic discussion is more efficient regarding time on task than ordinary classroom discourse, and the decrease in teacher domination of studies creates more opportunities to produce more complex language (p. 83).

However, Levy (2008) considers that the broad claim about the advantage of CALL should be examined with some "skepticism" because of the difficulty of language and language learning and the variety of students and learning strategies (p. 2). There have been fewer studies on an asynchronous interface than synchronous communication, probably because of the confounding variables (Levy, 2008). Amid the few reviews, Sottilo (2000, p. 104) studies that

students tend to focus on accuracy and form in asynchronous communication. In contrast, they only concentrate on meaning and fluency in synchronous communication, but still, many grammatical and spelling errors are found in asynchronous communication. Finally, Sottilo's (2000) study finishes that synchronous and asynchronous communication influence learners' attention differently and affect both language learning and production.

2.4 Self-access center

A Self-access Center (SAC) is not just a collection of materials; in its place, it combines several learning elements that deliver learners with a different kind of learning environment. Self-access language learning is a method of education, not an approach to teaching (Gardner & Miller, 1999). Self-access Centre can benefit all language learners as it is not culture-specific or age-specific (Gardner and Miller). Self-access Centre is a powerful tool to increase learners' capacity for independent and lifelong learning (Miller et al., 2007). Gardner and Miller also uncovered in a report that learners were very confident about the benefits of the Self-access Centre. Malcolm (2004) considers effective coordination among SAC administrators, staff, instructors, and students vital. Finally, he proposes that students can actively establish and maintain SAC in several ways, like managing resources, providing input in material design to make it suitable for their context, and so on.

Institutions' attitude is essential to establish a self-access center. In a highly structured institution, introducing a self-access center must be included in its policy (Jones, 2001). The institutional influence becomes significant where funding is required for a self-access Centre (Jones). Teachers and other decision-makers need to learn how self-access centers can be used in language teaching and replicate how it might work best in their context (Miller et al., 2007). Gardner and Miller (1999) postulate that a Self-access Centre can be of three types based on its structure of support. They are structured, semi-structured, and unstructured.

- *Structured SAC: Complete guidance is given to learners on entering the system and moving through it.*
- *Semi-structured SAC: Learners choose their materials and skills to work on but can ask for guidance if needed.*
- *Unstructured SAC: Learners must decide on their learning and monitor their progress.*

Nevertheless, SAC cannot replace a teacher (Jones, 2001). In its place, it generates new and vital roles for teachers, which they need to adopt or adapt. No self-access system is better than any other. It is modified to suit the context where it occurs. So, what works well for one group might not be appropriate for another group (Gardner & Miller, 1999). They propose different self-access systems with new names like Telephone sales, Mobile shops, Market stalls, Bring and buy sales, Postal sales, Boutique, Video-rental shops, Technology shops, and many more (p.58). Amongst them, "Telephone sales" is a system where learners interact with their teachers by telephone or email and get access to resources through their computer and internet, which is suitable for students.

2.5 Blog

Eastment (2005) says blogs are just online diaries where an individual can write their thoughts, reflection, or whatever they choose, with an option for the readers to post comments. Bella (2005) states that a weblog or blog is a website that can be created and updated quickly. People can publish in a blog instantly without knowledge of HTML (HyperText Markup Language) programming. For making the simple definition, Barlett-Bragg (2003) postulates that a blog is a collection of entries usually written by a single author and presented in reverse chronological order. Weblog entries are made by typing directly into the browser.

Moreover, all types of formatting like spacing, italics, bold, and underlining creating links can be done without any knowledge of HTML or FTP (File Transfer Protocol). So, anyone who can type, copy and paste can build and maintain a blog (Campbell, 2003; Godwin-Jones, 2003). The incredible growth of blogs can be attributed to the simplicity of creating and maintaining a blog (Barlett-Bragg, 2003). The accumulation of writings and other content in a blog generate a record of learning and resource for others (Campbell, 2003). A weblog is very interactive, as readers can post comments on any given entry, and threaded discussion can occur if the chosen software supports it (Campbell). By way of a limitation of a weblog, Godwin-Jones (2003) argues that entrances are accessible in chronological order but not in the order of content (p. 14). Campbell (2003) mentions the following three uses of weblogs that can be utilized for learning outside the classroom. Finally, in the next three-paragraph, the researcher discusses three types of blogs.

The Tutor Blog: It can perform three functions. Firstly, learners and parents can find information about course outlines, assessments, homework, and assignments' due dates, in the tutor blog. Secondly, it can be used as a portal where the teacher can post different materials and websites for learners' self-study. It also fosters learner autonomy. Thirdly, the blog can be used to give voice to someone's feelings and thoughts. Finally, the students can post their comments regarding any classroom activity. Thus, the teacher can also keep track of the student's improvement in writing.

The Learner Blog: Individual learners or groups can run this blog. A learner blog may be best suited for reading and writing classes. A typical reading assignment can be followed by comments from all the learners, where the students get writing practice. The Class Blog is a joint effort between the teacher and students. It can be an open space for students to express their thoughts about classroom activities. Class blogs may be helpful for project-based language learning, where learners can advance research and writing skills by being asked to generate an online source for others. It also can be as a virtual classroom for international students, where students from different countries will get access and publishing rights in this blog.

Soares (2008) postulates that the learner blog is a personal library where students will get reference materials, books, and many more for further study (p. 518). She also argues that learners' written works get published in the blog, so they are more concerned about their writing. She also mentions that the learner blog can be used as an online portfolio where students can

return to their previous work and measure their continuous progress during a writing course. Finally, about learner blogs, Barlett-Bragg (2003) says that since the content becomes the learners' sole responsibility, it may lead learners to deep learning.

Stanely (in Soares, 2008, p. 520) believes that a class blog is best used as an "extra-curricular extension of the classroom" that encourages the learners to think in-depth about the topics discussed in a classroom. Soares (2008, p. 520) believes that the best advantage of using a blog in the language classroom is that several groups of learners can interact worldwide through blogging. The interaction engages in the authentic use of the target language and sharing of culture, thoughts, feelings, and values that make learning more concrete and enjoyable (Soares). Kavaliauskiene et al. (2006) locate that using a blog in EFL writing classes makes learners feel that their writing is not only for their classmates or teachers but for the whole world, thus raising their language awareness (p. 221). They directed their study on the first-year students of Mykolas Romeris University who were learning English for a specific purpose. From their research, Kavaliauskiene et al. (2006) observe the following issues,

- *A blog allows learners to learn at their own pace, overcoming their fear of making errors and enhancing self-esteem.*
- *It can increase learners' motivation because of their novelty and diversity.*
- *Students get feedback not only from their teachers but also from the other readers of the blogs.*
- *Learners can return to their past performance in a blog and compare it with their present works. Thus, they can measure their improvement (p.227).*

Horvath (2009) recognizes blogs as a way of developing community bonding and individual autonomy in reading and writing courses at the tertiary level (p. 8). Godwin-Jones (2003) considers that a blog can be productive for project-based language learning (p.14).

2.6 Podcast

The word "podcast" originated from the term "pod" (acronym of Personal On-Demand) and "broadcast" (Smythe & Neufeld, 2010, p. 488). Pozzobon (2008) defines 'podcast' as regular audio or video program accessible via the internet and can be downloaded to a computer or personal device so that the user can view or listen to it anytime (p. 112). However, Smythe and Neufeld (2010) give a more technical definition of the podcast. They say a podcast is a web 2.0 digital social networking tool (like blogs, Facebook, and Youtube) that provides a platform for user-generated content, often using portable media players like iPod or MP3 players. Though many institutions have banned these accessories since they cause distraction among the students, students outside the schools are "infused" with this technology (Lee, McLoughlin, and Chan, 2007, pp. 124). Therefore, using these applications in the classroom may inspire learners to be involved in learning new things. A podcast can be in finding several websites like BBC or specialized software like Apple's iTunes (Pozzobon, 2008). One of the main attractions of a podcast is that learners can create their podcasts (individually or collaboratively) to reach an authentic audience (Smythe & Neufeld, 2010, p. 489). It does not require in-depth knowledge

of technology, and the product is reusable and portable and keeps learners engaged in a creative learning process for an extended time (Lee, McLoughlin, and Chan, 2007).

A podcast can be of unique types as Stanely (in Pozzobon, 2008, p.113) comes up with three types of podcasts: official podcast (created for general people), teacher podcast (created by teachers to help students), and students podcast (produced by students often with the help of teachers). It is well-defined from this report that teachers can create their podcasts and engage the students in producing them that conform to Erben, Ban, and Castaneda (2009, p. 18). The third principle of "creating an effective second language learning environment" that urges to give learners classroom time to use their English productively. With this tool, teachers can ensure that their students are listening to authentic content, at least for a period that will help them attain proficiency (Pozzobon, 2008, p. 113). Moreover, the podcast does not confine the students to passive listening; instead, it makes them participate actively in producing (Pozzobon). Dudency and Hockly (2007) define that the teachers can record their class lectures and publish them on the university website for the students who miss those classes.

2.6.1 How to create and use a podcast.

Smythe and Neufeld (2010) state that GarageBand software is widely used to create a podcast on Apple computers. Using this software, the students can control their podcast's sound effects and music. Chartrand and Pellowe (2007) make two podcasts with the help of their pupils following the steps mentioned below,

- *At first, they brainstormed some crucial points like the level of the targeted learners, the number of podcast episodes, and the kind of conversation.*
- *Secondly, they scripted conversations for the students of beginner and intermediate levels.*
- *Also, they use an Apple computer (iMacG5), an Edirol UA-3FX USB audio capture unit, and an Audio Technical microphone to record the conversations.*
- *Lastly, they use GarageBand 3, iTunes 7, and Sound Studio 3 software to edit and mix the recordings.*
- *Finally, they modified the pace of dialogues based on the learners' level. For the beginner level, they included a slow-paced version of the conversations, whereas, for the intermediate level, they used a faster release, and the dialogues tended to be longer.* (Pellowe)

Conversely, there are only a few websites where one can upload their podcast free of cost. Since podcast needs a vast memory because of the audio or video files, most websites charge for disk space and storage usage (Pozzobon, 2008). Pozzobon says that the site called Podbean proposes the opportunity of creating, listening, and subscribing to a podcast without any cost. It is to be distinguished that the users can use only 100MB of space free of value on this website.

2.7 Social networking website: Facebook

Social networking websites are new forms of CMC. Knobel et al. (1998) mention that computer-based learning is not just the simple existence of hardware and software; in its place, it requires the "coming together" of people in education mediated by the network. Blattner and Fiori state that Facebook is the fastest growing and best-known internet site, with over 100 million members. Veer (2010, p. 158) positions Facebook as a "hip, hot and happening site" where members can "witness" each other's life by viewing and sharing abundant quantities of information. Nowadays, Knobel's learning network has engaged in the form of Social Networking Communities (SNC) (Blattner & Fiori, 2009, p. 19). Blattner and Fiori (2009, p. 19) say Facebook is more "sophisticated" than many other SNCs like MySpace, Friendster, Blackboard, WebCT, Angel, and others. Blattner and Fiori (2009) think that Facebook can be a powerful learning tool since it allows its user to experience various patterns of interaction. To explain, Veer (2010, p. 65) notes that on Facebook, people can duplicate different types of real-life conversation as they can poke a friend, give a virtual hi or hello, write on somebody's wall, and send cyber-gifts. Facebook offers several forums for students to find a job, roommate, or textbook (Blattner & Fiori, 2009). Students or instructors can build a link for any particular course and request other students to join that link, which allows them to collaborate and exchange knowledge outside the classroom. The instructor can post important notices like the time and place of the next class, discussion topic, assignment deadline, email address, office hours, and many more. Joining any group is an exciting and favorite feature of Facebook (Blattner & Fiori, 2009). Veer (2010) notices that this feature can be used in a language classroom to promote constructive thinking.

Recent surveys have revealed that Facebook can positively impact student-to-student and student-to-teacher relationships (Mazer et al., 2007). Mazer and his colleagues (2007) have discovered that by accessing social networking websites, learners can find a common interest with peers and instructors, leading to a comfortable interaction and learning environment. O'Sullivan (2004) and his co-authors conclude that the students who have access to instructors' web pages containing "self-disclosed" information have a high level of motivation and develop a positive attitude towards the course and teacher. Therefore, SNC, like Facebook, can be a valuable tool to shape a community among students and teachers. For this reason, Blattner and Fiori (2009, p. 21) believe that recognizing an SNC's academic opportunities is essential for students and teachers. In addition, instructors need to comprehend that Facebook is an essential part of students' daily "e-routine"; so, if a teacher can use it for providing guidance, "it will be an invaluable advantage to their educational and social experience" (Blattner and Fiori).

Facebook can also grow up with learners' pragmatic competence (Blattner & Fiori, 2009, p. 22). Pragmatic competence incorporates the knowledge of speech acts and the ability to use a language accurately in a specific context (Eslami-Rasekh, 2005). It is a fundamental characteristic of language education. Kasper and Rose (2003) further explained this definition by adding that "pragmatics deals with how speakers and writers accomplish goals as social actors who respect social norms to attain interpersonal relationships with interlocutors." Facebook permits its users to execute meaningful interaction with the speakers of their native language and other words that give them access to practical information on various topics

(Blattener & Fiori, 2009). Accordingly, Facebook can be measured as an innovative tool to develop learners' socio-pragmatic awareness and competence in a second or foreign language. The authors stress that Facebook groups allow learners to experience constant and reliable communication through a discussion forum. Kasper and Rose (2003) also coincide with them and recommend that learners can use their observation power to understand the real-world practices of any community on Facebook.

2.8 Other social networking sites

There are some other tools for language learning, like email (2.8.1), skype (2.8.2), listserv (2.8.3), and Wiki (2.8.4), which can help to learn English as a foreign or a second language.

2.8.1 Email

Email stances for electronic mail allow users to exchange electronic messages and computer files from one computer to another (Erban et al., 2009). Like a pen-pal, students can have a key-pal with whom they can interchange email. Nagel (1999) points out that exchanging email among classroom students stimulates them to participate, and it does not necessitate being very expert in using a computer.

2.8.2 Skype

Skype allows users to make audio and video calls over the internet and to a landline (Eaton, 2010). Calls to other Skype users are free, and perhaps for this reason, in the mid of 2010, Skype had more than 124 million users who made 95 billion calls, of which almost 40% were video calls. If a computer is connected to a large screen or projector, Skype can educate a large class where the teachers and students might be in different places (Eaton).

2.8.3 Listserv

Listserv allows people with a common interest to join and partake in an organized and moderated email discussion group (Erban et al., 2009). Teachers can use existing listservs or form a personalized and closed listserv for their class or group. Learners can exercise English in this discussion forum on many topics, such as English grammar, conversational English, English idioms, varieties of English, and so on (Erban).

2.8.4 Wiki

Wiki is a cooperative website that can help students to advance their writing skills (Holtman, 2009, p. 30; Erban et al., 2009, p. 122). Wiki is created from the Hawaiian language, which means "quick" (Erban et al., 2009, p. 134). It allows members to post new writings and edit existing posts (Holtman, 2009). Consequently, the teachers can check students writing and provide feedback on Wiki (Holtman).

2.9 The virtual world: distance education

With the progress of technology, learning has become such an attempt where the location is less critical. For this reason, distance education has become popular in the education

kingdom. Davey (in Carter and Elseth, 2009, p. 444) outlines that distance learning is a formal educational process with teachers and students separated by time and distance. Wilson (in Carter and Elseth, 2009, p. 444) postulates that "distance learning is an educational approach that integrates technology, connectivity, curricular content, and human resources" to teach students outside a traditional classroom. Learning is no longer restricted to the four boundaries of a building but can take place anywhere and anytime, facilitated by digital information and communication technology (Kluge & Riley, 2008, p. 128). The advent of online 3D virtual worlds poses many exciting opportunities and challenges for teachers. Gesche (2009, p. 525) terms this 3-D world a "Virtual Third Space," coined initially by Bhabha (in Gesche, 2009, p. 526). He also says it is a space where people can "construct, reconstruct and negotiate identity," and the identity is provisional rather than fixed. Kluge and Riley (2008, p. 128) have cited the virtual world as "Metaverses" where inhabitants can design their avatars, create their environment, and function in a way that resembles the real world. The acceptance of the virtual world is increasing day by day. Linden Lab's "Second Life" (SL), one of the leading virtual worlds, has grown from 230,000 consumers in 2006 to 8.5 million in 2007, and it has been predicted that 80% of the active internet users will take part in the virtual world by the end of 2011 (Kluge & Riley, 2008). Now people do not only interact in SL but also trade there with the "Linden dollar." They can buy an island, house, office space, and many more worldwide (Coffman & Klinger, 2007). Language learners cannot get a real-life environment to practice their target language, but virtual worlds like Second Life can deliver learners with that platform (Sherblom et al., 2009). Gesche (2009) thinks virtual learning communities have become famous for several reasons. Such as providing a new platform for language learning, creating an exciting "trans-cultural communicative space,"; facilitating inter-cultural communication, and providing opportunities for real-world interaction. Broadribb et al. (2009), Kluge and Riley (2008), and Coffman and Klinger (2007) consider the opportunities and significance of the virtual world in education,

- *The virtual atmosphere has the potential to immerse the learners in the learning process fully.*
- *It allows learners from diverse places to collaborate on the same topic and use their imagination and creativity to perform any duty.*
- *The educator can make the learners for the complex and interconnected global society in a virtual world.*
- *In a distance education program, novices can have a sense of participating in a classroom through the virtual world.*

Carter and Elseth (2009) believe learners get more engaged in Second Life because they can mimic real-life actions and do a lot more that is not imaginable in a natural setting, like flying without any transportation, visiting museums, the gothic cathedral, dangerous and new places, and whatnot. They further believe that while visiting these places, learners meet and talk with people who exist in the real world, motivating a factual situation to converse. Despite having much potential, using a virtual world for education is challenging both from a student's and a teacher's viewpoint. Participation in the virtual world requires learners to have strong knowledge of computers and the internet (Kluge & Riley, 2008, p. 131). Teachers and parents

often frowned at Second Life since they think of it only as an online game (Carter & Elseth, 2009). There is a need for more competent and trained teachers who can plan and coach courses in virtual space (Swertz et al., 2009). Gesche (2009) also says that planning language classes for a virtual setting requires careful technical and personal preparation. Sherblom et al. (2009) discover that teachers and students experience numerous challenges in a virtual world, like gaining access, managing the internet and Second Life commotion, and coping with computer problems. Cost is another challenge for the implementation of virtual world education. It necessitates a high-speed net connection with modern computers (Kluge & Riley, 2008). In Second Life, though the primary account is free, producing any educational presence costs \$9.99 monthly (Kluge and Riley). Burden issues remain a question in the virtual world (Bugeja, 2008). Many illegal acts like virtual violence, harassment, and assault occur in Second Life, and whether a teacher will be responsible must be resolved (Bugeza). Moreover, some students may find the world so exciting that they may get distracted from the educational purpose (Kluge and Riley).

2.10 E-learning

E-learning or electronic learning is a technology-driven learning system where all the learning and teaching activities are carried out via a network and electronic devices. (Patra et al., 2010). In Bangladesh, there are a few studies on the e-learning context, and the existing studies focus basically on inclusive learning and teaching rather than on language teaching. From the viewpoint of Islam and Selim (2006a), e-learning was first introduced in Bangladesh in 1956 via radio broadcast, and it was expanded by Bangladesh Open University (BOU) in 1992. Nevertheless, it has been quite a long time, and it still needs to catch up in using modern ICT (Islam & Selim, 2006b). They (BOU) mainly deliver their lessons via television and radio, but if they make them available online, students can access them anytime from anywhere (Andersson, 2008). Though Bangladesh is now connected to "the information super-highway" through submarine cables, adding a new dimension to the expansion of e-learning in Bangladesh (Islam & Selim, 2006b, p. 103). Nevertheless, e-learning poses both prospects and challenges for developing countries like Bangladesh (Islam & Selim, 2006a).

2.10.1 Scenarios of e-learning for Bangladesh

Patra et al. (2010) mention the following benefits of e-learning in the Bangladeshi context,

- *In a country of more than 160 million populations, it is not imaginable for the Bangladesh government to make infrastructure to admit all the students. By initiating e-learning programs, a few institutions can provide education to many students.*
- *Bangladesh's government has announced to build of an ICT-based digital Bangladesh, and e-learning is crucial to that goal.*
- *E-learning is very cost-effective since it does not require any classroom, and students do not need to come to class or purchase reading materials. All the reading materials can be provided through the internet.*
- *Online registration and advising save time both for the students and teachers. Many schools and universities have started to perform the formalities of filing online.*

- *E-learning provides self-learning opportunities for students, and they can continue working beside their studies.*

Akbar (2005) mentions that the demand for higher education is increasing. Still, many students drop out after their higher secondary school due to various reasons like poor socioeconomic conditions and a shortage of universities in many areas. He thinks that e-learning can meet the demand for higher education and better learning materials for these students, ensuring quality output.

2.10.2 Challenges in e-learning

E-learning is now a new concept for Bangladeshi learners (Akbar, 2005). Numerous challenges need to be faced presenting e-learning. For example, Akbar (2005) says about computer and internet connection unavailability. His viewpoint, except for the urban areas, computer, and internet connection is not accessible for ordinary people in many areas. Islam and Selim (2006a) also think so on that point. They find out from their study that the poor socioeconomic condition of Bangladesh might suggest an enormous challenge for the implementation of e-learning. Andersson (2008) remarks that an educational setting impedes the execution of e-learning. She reports her study in two developing countries—Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, where she realizes that the students in developing countries are used to an authoritarian classroom setting. In such a situation, initiating e-learning courses will be very challenging, and the challenge for students is both technology and the construction of the educational setting. She also comes up with a lack of flexibility in the curricula, learners' lack of responsibility for their learning, time management, and the administration's indifference to the failure of the e-learning program in Bangladesh. Akbar (2005) thinks that local authorities have yet to accept e-learning facilities in the Bangladeshi framework. Thus, he advises that with high technology, a user-friendly environment is also necessary for the success of e-learning. Andersson (2008) finds out that a lack of trained teachers to conduct e-learning courses is another problem to be considered. Moreover, Akbar (2005) highlights that most of the materials used for e-learning are developed in the western context. Accordingly, developing local materials that apply to the Bengali language and culture is significant in implementing e-learning.

2.11 Teacher training

Teachers are, broadly, learners because they learn twice—once for themselves and again for students (Khan, 2005). Although in recent times, teacher training has got the consideration, it is still a significant problem area in Bangladesh. Rahman (1998) says exercise is obligatory only at the secondary level. There is no pre-service training for primary, higher secondary, and tertiary teachers. Sultana (2005) uncovers in her report that only 36% of higher secondary school teachers have teaching training, but further inquiry shows that they have a wrong conception of teacher training. They believe seminars, workshops, and conferences as training. Quader (2005) mentions that teachers at college, degree, and master's levels under the National University undergo training for three months before entering the classroom. Still, the practice is neither extensive nor intensive. However, he thinks that life is becoming very

competitive in the present world, and in this competitive world, teachers need to be trained to carry out their work correctly. Likewise, Sultana (2005) says that compared to public schools, private schools give more importance to teacher development. However, the constant changing in the workplace on the part of teachers and the continuous replacement of teachers by the authorities show that none of the parties is satisfied with the present situation. So, her opinions are that teachers take control of their development to cope with the "complex, competitive and ever-changing world of teaching." She especially desires the private schools to launch and support teacher training programs that will maintain the quality of education, leading to the growth of schools. She further mentions in her article that schools should arrange seminars, conferences, and workshops for teachers and students' betterment besides providing training. Teachers may require designing, implement and evaluate a CALL activity. Therefore, it is becoming vital for teachers to be familiar with CALL opportunities inside and outside the classrooms (Jones, 2001, p. 361; Fotos & Browne, 2004, p. 3). Jones (2001, p. 362) consider that technology and computer cannot replace teachers; instead, it assigns teachers different roles, like a facilitator, organizer, guide, material designer, and monitor. Thus, language teachers must play these roles appropriately and consistently with their CALL training. Various types of research (for example, Kessler, 2006, p. 22) propose that there is scarcely any formal course or program to assist teachers interested in CALL. Accordingly, they avoid using technology in their classroom. Those who are enthusiastic attend seminars, workshops, and conferences to satisfy their enthusiasm by questioning or discussing with the more experienced people (Kessler, 2006, p. 24). Kessler (2006, p. 24) thinks that the "formal language teacher preparation programs" neglect to prepare their graduates with the knowledge of technology. Levy (1997) advocates ongoing support to appreciate and implement CALL effectively.

However, there is broad backing for teachers to use technology; the question is what type of training is necessary. Some colleges of education have already combined necessary computer skills such as keyboarding, mouse skill, and working with menus and sub-menus in their courses (NCATE, 2008). Knowledge of electronic communication, like email, discussion board, and file sharing, are essential to collaborating with students and colleagues (Kessler, 2006). Fotos and Browne (2004) stress using the internet and CMC in today's academic environment. Likewise, Hirvela (2006, p. 234) also emphasized CMC to be integrated into teacher training as it promotes collaboration and, at the same time, produces an archive of valuable comments and opinions that teachers or teacher educators can access anytime from anywhere for further clarification. Son (2002) emphasizes more sophisticated skills like video conferencing, chatting, and developing web-based materials, blogs, and other forums that enhance classroom and distance learning. Green and Tanner (2005) also inspire distance teacher education programs because they allow trainees to use their "multiple intelligence." Ebsworth et al. (2004) have a different understanding of teacher education. They used only videotapes for their training program, and they got a positive response from the teachers. In their application, in addition to advisors' feedback, the trainees get self-feedback when they watch their videotapes, and they enjoy not only it but also review their language use.

Conversely, Daud (in Kessler, 2006) advises teachers to expect technology to handle only some of their teaching problems. Egbert et al. (2002) find out that teachers often need help

using technology despite having knowledge and training on CALL because of some obstacles. Accordingly, the main impediments are time, curricula and administrative restrictions, and insufficient resources. Therefore, it can be assumed that in addition to teacher training, hardware, software, technical assistance, curricula, administrative support, and, last but not the least, emotional support are the resources required to implement CALL (Egbert, 2002). Jones (2001) notices that administrative and classroom duties prevent teachers from being enthusiastic about training on CALL. Even if they are provided with training, they may need more time to put their new knowledge into practice (p.365). He further mentions that if CALL teachers enhance, a curriculum may feel interested in it.

The literature review on Computer-Assisted Language Teaching disclosed that most of the studies in this field were conducted in Western countries where English was the first language. On the other hand, only a few research was conducted in countries where English was a foreign language, mainly in Bangladesh (Afrin, 2014, p. 70). The researcher analyses some of the most related studies on this research topic. For example, Dashtestani (2012) surveyed Iranian EFL teachers "perspectives on CALL, and he found that the attendees had positive attitudes toward the use of CALL in EFL courses. Teachers believe that CALL is beneficial to increasing students' motivation, autonomy, self-confidence, and learning multicultural competence. In addition to that, CALL is considered relevant, facilitative, interactive, and time and energy efficient in EFL teaching (p. 60).

Park & Son (2009) mention that teachers of CALL have positive and approving attitudes toward using computers in the classroom. They think the machine is that kind of technology that helps to teach students, and they get help in various ways. Using a piece of equipment, students will have learning experiences in genuine and authentic contexts. Atkins and Vasu (2000) believe that teachers are more conscious of using computers in the classroom. As a result, they think computers play a significant role in EFL learners.

On the other hand, Lam (2000) also states that teachers are interested in using computers and have personal beliefs about the advantages of using equipment in the classroom. It also helps teachers decide using technology. Kim (2008) also finds out those teachers "beliefs about language teaching and learning. The teacher's ideas about language teaching and learning also affected their perceptions and expectations of computers. Teachers do not believe computers can develop all four skills equally. Instead, they expect to use the internet and multimedia through a machine to help students' reading comprehension" (p. 251).

Karl (2011) narrates the significance of using technology in the classroom. She points out a difference between learning from and learning with an approach seen very clearly in the philosophy of technology education versus educational technology. From her point of view, she says that technology education is based on that technology, where the primary focus is on computer science courses and computer programming. Technology is the tool to acquire more knowledge about a specific subject, the educational technology shifts to achieve cognition and higher order of thinking instead of drill-and-practice necessary skills (p. 21). Reeves (1998) says that "learning from media and technology, the student becomes the tutee, and the

technology is the tutor" (p. 2). So, he thinks the approach is tutoring students on drill and practice skills and delivering immediate feedback on student performance. Educational technology contains various content areas taught in school and uses technology to support learning in these different areas (Reeves, 1998, p. 2). Karl (2011) assertions some positive stances on implementing technology-based education in the classroom. From her point of view, she argues that the researcher's thoughts are positive. Students learning tasks did not change dramatically as the study progressed, but the researchers observed other significant changes. These changes are as follows:

- *Teachers began working in teams and across disciplines.*
- *Classrooms became a mix of traditional and constructivist instruction.*
- *Students became more collaborative than before.*
- *Teachers altered daily schedules to allow more time for student projects.*
- *Teachers began to use alternative assessment forms, such as performance and portfolio based.*
- *Technology encouraged a student-centered environment and cooperative learning.*
- *Teachers often used more complex tasks and materials in their instruction, and*
- *Teachers realized that teaching and learning with technology occur over time (p. 24).*

Warschauer (2002) finds out that the use of technology in the classroom. He has done an ethnographic study with language learners, in Hawaii-including immigrants, international students, and native Hawaiians. It denotes that the participants view technology not as a secondary, optional tool but as a critical added value to language education. In other words, students in technology-intensive language classrooms simultaneously learn language skills and valuable information literacy (p. 455). Seileek (2004) examined the effectiveness of two mediated techniques - cooperative and collective learning - designed for teaching and learning oral skills, listening, and speaking. He also observed students' attitudes toward using a CALL approach and techniques for teaching oral skills. Finally, the study finds that cooperative computer-mediated technology is a practical method for learning and teaching oral skills."

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Theoretical framework

The computer-assisted language learning theoretical framework, which discovers the detailed findings that support this research, can be assembled based on the following justifications:

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) can lead to a society in many ways. In one scenario, a computer-literate parent may discover a pleasant reward and mistreatment system with sirens and melodies to inspire a teenager to learn whatever the parent can get from the computer, maybe even a foreign language: thus, the foundation legend of the Transparent Language. In another scenario, a perceptive language and literature professor may observe instructional software in another field, economics, and recognize its applicability to the language learning enterprise. Others may have commenced in the kingdom of testing and evaluation, first on paper and face-to-face but in due course also by computer adaptive means. Moreover, other experts founded their credentials in Linguistics and Philology before stumbling upon a network and applying their talent to CALL. It does not need the pioneering expertise of a century ago to obtain or progress someone else theory of language learning. In broad strokes, most approaches can be embodied in a field limited by Pavlov's dog salivating to the sound of a bell, structuralism, generative grammar theory, the natural method, parallel distributed processing" (PDP), and Cognitive theory.

The aged and most potent modern learning theories inevitably returned to Pavlov and are methodized for twentieth-century audiences by B.F. Skinner (1904-1990). The behaviorist model starts with the empiricist axiom that all psychological data should be limited that is observable. On that base, the idea upholds that human and animal learning closely resemble one another. Furthermore, the human child's mind is not a tabula rasa (blank slate). There pre-exist certain functions for every action they do other than suckling. Also, it is as tricky and complimentary as the use of language. Then learning of language, just like anything else, can be adept by experience, specifically by orders of stimulus and response. "Conditioning" is the automatic production of a proper or expected response upon any given stimulus. It is the concern of extensive experience in which the relations between stimulus and response are encouraged and reinforced. Learning comprises the cultivation of these relations. Language is nothing more than an ostentatious response mechanism established through years of conditioning across critical periods in human growth. Studying the theories can be inferred that CALL can be used in two distinct phases (Warschauer, 1996): Behaviorist and Social Constructivism or Development Theory. In the following subsection (3.1.1), the researcher discusses Behaviorist theory and paragraph 3.1.2, Social Constructivism Theory.

3.1.1 Behaviorist theory

"Behaviorism was, and is, a moment primarily in American psychology that rejected consciousness as psychology subject matter and replaced it with behavior" (Leahey, 2000, p.

686). Behaviorism associates learning with behaviors that can be observed and measured. Reinforcement is the key to successful transfer through behavioristic learning, and a strong emphasis on the stimulus, the response, and the relationship between them (Danley, James, Mims & Simms, 2014). They show it in the figure:

Figure 2: The definition of Behaviorism³

Behaviorism was established in the 1880s and evolved in the twentieth-first century and beyond. Although behaviorism has been severely studied, behaviorists need help agreeing on a definition for behaviorism and identifying the actual behaviorists (Mills, 1998). The publication of *The Behavioral Learning Theory* by Watson in 1913 was responsible for the movement towards behaviorism and away from functionalism. This publication studies the relationship between organisms and their environment (Overskeid, 2008). Most psychologists have agreed that psychology is the study of human behavior; the only scientists that consider themselves behaviorists today are those who are followers of Skinner (Leahey, 2000). "The behaviorism of Watson and Skinner is based on a positivistic approach to science, that is, a reductionist view in which all that can be addressed is the relation between sensory stimuli and the corresponding unique response" (Webb, 2007, p. 1086). However, Skinner eventually realizes that humans go beyond just responding to the environment. He finds they also react to the situation based on prior experiences (Skinner, 1974). Rotfeld (2007) suggests that "psychologists 'invented' behaviorism itself as a basis for theoretical explanations, prediction, and testing" (p. 376). From its inception, the term behaviorism provides a "direction for social science research that will allow control and measurement of all relevant variables by ignoring human thought or cognition" (p. 376).

The history of behaviorism in teaching and learning technology can be found in a teaching machine constructed by Skinner in 1958. Skinner's teaching device is a rote-and-drill machine where individual instruction is presented as a book; the device is housed, displayed, and offered programmed instruction. This teaching device is a form of early technology compared to today's essential educational software. How the Teaching Machine is used is described by Skinner (1958): "In consuming the device, the student denotes to a numbered item in a multiple-choice test. S/he presses the button corresponding to his/her first choice of answer. If s/he is right, the device moves on to the next item; if s/he is wrong, the error is tallied, and s/he must revive to create choices until he is correct" (p. 971). Though essential, it is easy to observe the similarity between teaching technology and many of today's educational software programs. Like teaching devices, computer software designed for students helps to reinforce

³ http://faculty.mercer.edu/codone_s/tco363/2014/behaviorism.pdf

learner behavior. Skinner's primary work and findings with the teaching machine can be applied to modern-day computer programs; they are fundamentally similar. Skinner's teaching technology connects to today's digital world, which can be generalized and described as the roots of behaviorism.

Behaviorists supposed that meaning exists in the world differentiated from individual experience. All instructional areas are framed in concrete, behavioral, and observable terms. In this method, the instructor focuses on the presentation and interaction. Teachers work with individual students when they need additional help. The student's role is to absorb instructional presentations and material and use them to create performances that indicate the attainment of correct mental models. Structured assignments are directly connected to the learning objectives. There needs to be more cohort discussion in this model of direct instruction. Assessment and evaluation are based on individual tests and performances to demonstrate mastery of entities, activities, and procedures.

Many aspects of behaviorism have led to the development of critical instructional technologies (Sutton, 2000). Examples of behaviorism in online instruction are educational software and computer-assisted education. Drill and practice tutorials are designed to reward students "through an encouraging comment before moving on to the next learning objective" (Shield, 2000, p. 1). Shield concludes that "the student's mastering of basic technological terms, descriptions of components, and understanding of the theory behind technical processes can be achieved through structured programs delivered through software programs or similar media" (p. 1). Current behaviorists believe students learn by memorizing chunks of information before higher-level, problem-based learning occurs (Shield, 2000). Shield (2000) believes that much of today's curriculum focuses on these memorized bits of information and concludes that behaviorist practices are still relevant in today's digitized world.

Behaviorist CALL was applied in the 1960s and 1970s when the Audio-lingual method was mainly used and delivered to students with drills and practice. This model used the technology as a tutor, presenting exercises and non-judgmental feedback.

Behaviorist CALL is grounded on the communicative approach; communicative CALL emphasizes more on using forms rather than the forms themselves. The outspoken CALL programs deliver skill practice in a non-drill format through language games, reading, and text reconstruction. This approach still uses technology as a tutor, although it gives students choices, control, and communication. Another CALL model used for communicative activities includes technology as a stimulus, as in programs that inspire writing or discussions, and which may not be specifically designed for language learners. Finally, communicative CALL also uses technology as a tool in programs that do not offer language material but permit the learner to comprehend and use the language, such as word processors, desktop publishing, spelling, and grammar check programs, for instance, in process writing.

The current method is integrative CALL, grounded on multimedia computers and the Internet. These technological growths have transported text, graphics, sound, animation, and

video to be retrieved on a single low-cost technology. These resources are all related and called 'hypermedia,' enabling learners to steer through CD-ROMS and the Internet at their pace and path, using diverse media. (Wesley et al., 1985, p. 12-16)

3.1.2 Social constructivism (development) theory

Lev Vygotsky and Piaget

Social constructivism theory (Social Development Theory) is developed by Lev Vygotsky (1978). His learning approach emphasizes social and cultural collaborations in the learning method. Vygotsky positions that education is co-constructed and that individuals learn from one another. He excluded the assumption made by Piaget that it was imaginable to separate learning from its social setting. He supposed that constructivists such as Piaget had overlooked the fundamentally social nature of language and thus failed to recognize that learning is a combined process. Piaget's theory identifies that development precedes learning. At the same time, Vygotsky (1978) experienced social learning precedes development, asserting, "Every role in the child's cultural development shows twice: first, on the social level, and later, on the single level. The researcher discusses this in the following few paragraphs of Vygotsky's Social Constructivism Theory.

Lev Vygotsky (1896-1934) is a Russian Psychologist who gains international attention with his 1962 publication of his Social Development Theory (SDT), one of the foundations for constructivism. Constructivism has a point of view that is presently measured as the more popular of the theory in "education policies, education models and education practices focus on constructivism" (Brown, 2006, p. 109). Fosnot (1996) suggests that constructivism views learning as an interpretive, recursive, and building process by which active learners interrelate with the physical and social world. Kruse (1998) reinforces Fosnot's views on constructivism because he notes that this methodology positively affects students' ability to enhance their knowledge.

Vygotsky's Social Development Theory (SDT) introduces two essential characteristics:

- *Cognitive development is limited to a certain extent or within a specific range at any given age.*
- *An individual's full cognitive development requires social interaction.*

Three themes support Vygotsky's SDT principles: Social Interactions, The More Knowledgeable Other (MKO), and the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Vygotsky's theory of cognitive development is primarily related to the more complex cognitive activities of children that are governed and influenced by the principles:

Figure 3: Social Constructivism Theory (Vygotsky, 1978).

Social Interaction

According to Vygotsky, cognitive, conscious scholarly activity results from reciprocal communication exchanges between persons and society. Just as society is modeling the individual, the individual is shaping society. Beginning as children, we can only study by collaborating with things or people. Instead, we progressively grow and develop through investigation, communication, and observations with others. Moreover, social interactions play a vital role in our cognitive development as we age. Vygotsky believes that event is preceded by social evolution stating: "Every role in the child's cultural development shows twice: first, on the social level, and later, on the single level; first, between individual (inter-psychological) and then internal the child (intra-psychological)" (Vygotsky, 1978, p. 150). Recapping social interchange is required for learning, and social communication is needed to function and become fully developed.

More Knowledgeable Other (MKO)

According to Vygotsky (1978), much meaningful learning by the child happens through social communication with a skillful tutor. The tutor may model behaviors and deliver verbal instructions to the child. Vygotsky denotes this as cooperative or mutual dialogue. The child obtains to understand the actions or instructions provided by the tutor and then adopts the information, using this to guide or regulate their performance. This tutor is also categorized as More Knowledgeable Others (MKO). When we have something innovative to learn, we often

search for a knowledge expert to help us gain further information and apply new skills. We seek a mentor or, as Vygotsky would say, a More Knowledgeable Other (MKO). The MKO is an individual that has a greater understanding or a higher skill level than the learner concerning concepts, methods, or tasks. While the MKO can be a peer, a younger individual, or even technology, the MKO is often a tutor, coach, or older adult. Although self-initiated learning and finding can be effective, learning becomes progressively productive and promotes cognitive expansion when supported by a more knowledgeable other.

Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)

Vygotsky specified that a child respects an adult's example and steadily improves the ability to do positive tasks without help or assistance. Vygotsky's often-quoted explanation of the zone of proximal development grants it as "the gap between the real developmental level as determined by sovereign problem solving and the level of possible development as determined through problem-solving underneath mature guidance, or in cooperation with more capable peers." Vygotsky, among other educational specialists, trusts the role of education to be to deliver children with experiences in their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), thereby enhancing and progressing their learning. The MKO works with Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The ZPD is a gap analysis. The learning implementer identifies the learner's ability to execute a task independently and at what point the student will need MKO support and guidance to complete a task. Finally, Vygotsky claims that learning occurs in the space between independence and requiring guidance, the ZPD.

As a visual for the ZPD, consider an internal circle that denotes what a learner already knows and the outermost circle that represents what the student does not know. The middle circle signifies what the learner can attain or discover independently. Learning ensues in the internal circle, bridging unconventionality and complete support. Within this zone, the learner is most receptive to instruction and schooling from the MKO. The MKO should deliver guidance and allow the learner to mature their skills. By fostering independence, the MKO will support the learner in gaining higher psychological functions more quickly.

All these theories stay useful based on Computer-Assisted Language Learning, as above-mentioned; therefore, their inclusion in the research.

3.2 Conceptual framework

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is not alien to the academic world. This research's conceptual framework comprises two components that specify the critical elements of learning English as a Foreign Language. First, the research structure and purposes will vary significantly according to the defined components. Second, technological knowledge indicates what skills the foreign language learner acquires and the knowledge that underpins those skills. Third, the expertise used in computer-assisted language learning is often recognized with proficiency in a structured understanding of the foreign language. This understanding reflects both the central role of the old teaching language design and, possibly, also the more traditional viewpoints about language learning held by many CALL designers who have approached the

task from the fields of technological intelligence and the Internet world. More recently, computer-assisted language learning systems explicitly attempt to develop communicative competence, particularly in high-tech world learning environments.

Moreover, some Language Learning Websites will teach the students what they know and need to learn about the materials used. This knowledge can involve the checking of errors made, as well as the learning goals that are adequately met. This model of what the students know serves as valuable input to the checking element of the research. The activity uses continually upgraded materials to check language use and faults regarding underlying structural language misunderstandings, which they disclose in the tests or exercises. This information is used to evaluate students' progress and determine the most effective mode of presentation and explanation. Besides, the site model can be designed to consider other learners' capabilities, including learning strategies and limitations due to the learner's knowledge.

First, the Behaviorist theory is related to the study that John B. Watson coined. Behaviorism is a learning theory accompanying the idea that behavior can be coordinated or improved based on the former or subsequent responses to behavior. So, in the learning practice, a behavior will happen if given the right setting, and a behavior is merely likely to reoccur based on the effects that follow, either reward or punishment. An advantage of Behaviorism is the capacity to clearly define the planned behavior and then create a setting to measure the behavior, help the behavior, and foster reoccurrence. From a methodical standpoint, behaviorism seeks humble explanations of human behavior. For example, a teacher provides a substantial list of practice problems for students to help them learn Algebra.

Figure 2: Behaviorist theory by Watson (1913)⁴

⁴ http://faculty.mercer.edu/codone_s/tco363/2014/behaviorism.pdf

Reflect on an online algebra class. First, the instructor makes a video and posts the video in the online classroom showing the student how to resolve an algebra problem; then, the problem will be allotted to the student. The student is asked to design a video of their procedure to solve the drawback. The student is told that if they answer the problem, they will receive an immediate automated medal. With ten electronic medals, they will obtain extra credit in the course. It is a new algebra problem for the student. None of their previous learning has equipped them to complete the problem. What will they do? It depends on their previous knowledge of math. The student will apply their previous math policies to solving this equation. Assume the student has ten attempts, learned and unlearned responses, and the student solves the math problem through this procedure. The time it took the student to solve the problem was 15 minutes. Once solved, the student receives an electric medal. The next time students are given the problem, they make fewer mistakes and solve it in 5 minutes. In three trials or less, the student can quickly solve the type of problem. The student's ability to complete the problem with increased speed is a function of frequency and regency (Watson, 1930, p. 204). In the language classroom, assignments should be structured so that desired student behaviors can be defined and directly scaffolded by the ascribed work. The student's developmental behavior and growth should be noticeable, and desired student performance should be rewarded. As an example, based on the related research,

Figure 5: Behaviorist theory followed by Watson (1913)

Finally, Vygotsky's (1978) theory of social constructivism has been related to this study. Vygotsky's theory of cognitive development is primarily concerned with children's more complex cognitive activities that are governed and influenced by some principles in the present research. MKO refers to school teachers who are more knowledgeable persons than

Figure 6: Social Constructivism Theory (Vygotsky, 1978).

The students and ZPD refer to the learnable matters in school with their colleagues and teachers. Beck and Kosnik (2006, p. 8) think that social constructivism is not just an abstract idea; it can play a significant role in solving the problems and tensions teachers face in teacher education. According to Vygotsky (1978) and Beck and Kosnik (2006), all the learning community members must present their ideas powerfully while remaining open to others' opinions. Each concept or thought can be expressed by connecting it to the existing knowledge; new approaches must be based on the old ones since learning or teaching is a gradual process rather than a sudden initiative (Randall & Thornton, 2001). So, providing new knowledge based on their experience is crucial. Beck and Kosnik (2006) claim that with encouragement and support from the learning community, student-teachers begin to develop their pedagogy that fixes their needs and talent. Society or town has to play a vital role in this gradual learning process to teach, as Brophy (in Beck and Kosnik, 2006, p. 9) states that a well-developed community could positively influence teaching. Beck and Kosnik (2006) postulate that teachers should receive high-quality training while improving working conditions and resources to enhance their experience. Institutions should spend more on training than they used to pay before (p.8). The teacher's primary role should be to motivate the children to create knowledge through personal experiences (Rummel, 2008).

Vygotsky thought that cognitive development happens due to social interaction, which is fundamental to the learning experience. This experience can occur online (for example, over widespread social media instruments like LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Blog, Wiki, and so on) or offline (through group discussions).

Figure 7: Social Development Theory by Vygotsky. Elements for Constructing Social Learning Environments.⁵

This study discusses what kind of support the teachers get from their schools to develop their teaching skills and whether the authority is cooperative enough to spend money to improve their teachers' competence in using computers and technology to teach better.

⁵ <https://www.upsidelearning.com/blog/index.php/2010/03/10/elements-for-constructing-social-learning-environments/>

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the philosophical underpinning and methodological tools and techniques selected to understand phenomena in the field under study. The research design is considered plans and procedures to conduct research (Creswell, 2009). It will include the philosophical assumptions that underpin the process of knowledge production. These elements will set the scene for selecting the research site, which considerations are prioritized when sampling, and finally, which the participants are. A discussion of research methods will follow, where the focus is on interviews and observations, with an emphasis on the role of the researcher in data collection. Finally, a particular concern will give to research with students due to the necessity of acknowledging them as meaningful actors and future societal leaders. Further on, how data is analyzed and interpreted will be explained, and finally, the ethical consideration essential to acknowledge when in the field, researching with natural persons will be discussed.

This chapter entails the research design and the nature of the approach used; methods of data collection that employ the ethical issues considered during the project also embeds in this chapter. The population and sampling technique is also found here. This chapter also entails data collection tools. Lastly, the chapter tackles validity and reliability, ethical issues, and challenges.

4.2 Research design

The study employs a qualitative research strategy in which the recognition of words emphasizes rather than relying on numbers in statistics. The qualitative method makes it possible to explore the life views of participants, contrary to the quantitative way, where numbers will give generalizations about a phenomenon but need help understanding the event in depth. Within naturalistic and interpretive inquiry, there are diverse methodologies for interpreting meaning, each of which has its philosophies, principles, and methods of interpretation. Understanding the ontological and epistemological assumptions of the naturalistic and interpretive paradigm, Glaser and Strauss developed a rigorous and systematic methodology for collecting and analyzing qualitative data. This methodology is termed Grounded Theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Grounded Theory methods are:

A set of flexible analytic guidelines enables researchers to focus their data collection and build inductive middle-range theories through subsequent data analysis and conceptual development levels. A grounded theory approach encourages researchers to remain close to their studied worlds and develop an integrated set of theoretical concepts from their empirical materials that synthesize and interpret them and show processual relationships (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008, p.204).

Unlike other naturalistic and interpretive research methodologies, which aim to describe and explore phenomena investigated, Grounded Theory explains in-depth what happens in such

events. The main feature of Grounded theory is that it is an ongoing interaction process between the researcher and the studied area. The process involves collecting and analyzing data concurrently, i.e., the researchers start analyzing data as soon as the data collection commences, without waiting until all information gathers (as is the case with other interpretive research methods) to start the analysis. This feature helps the researcher to be very close to his/her participants (Goulding, 1999; Birks & Mills, 2011). Understanding adequate knowledge and the nature of social entities in the social world are embedded in underlying philosophical assumptions: epistemology and ontology. Different kinds of worldviews create the basis for the selection of approaches and procedures for the collection of data. Hence based on philosophical assumptions, the researcher attempts to understand the social world of the participants through an interpretive and constructivist lens.

Breidlid (2013) states 'epistemology' as the 'theory of knowledge,' meaning "the nature, scope, and sources of knowledge," or how "people view and make sense of the world according to what they have learned and what they believe" (p.2). Chilisa (2012) says epistemology inquiries into the nature of knowledge and truth. It asks, what are the sources of knowledge? How reliable are these sources? What can one know? How does one know if something is true? Kvale & Brinkmann (2009) state that epistemology is the philosophy of knowledge and seeks to discover sufficient knowledge within a setting. Breidlid (2013) states that Western science and expertise enjoyed a hegemonic global position between 1400-1600 AD. Since then, Europe's superiority has been perceived, contributing to military, economic, political, and epistemological domination over countries in the global South (p.7).

Interpretivism provides one lens in understanding and originates from the concept of 'Verstehen,' "which means understanding and refers to the uniquely human capacity to make sense of the world" (Patton, 2002, p. 52). It implies that the researcher attempts, through interaction and observations, to understand how participants perceive their social reality by being empathic and reflecting on the socio-cultural context (Patton). The intellectual tradition stemming from interpretivism is the phenomenology philosophy, which is concerned with understanding and describing the world the way participants understand and describe it (Creswell, 2009; Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Within these positions, a qualitative inquiry entails thus to listen and interact with individuals to understand their subjective meaning of the world and hence to be able to describe their social reality the way it is experienced by them (Creswell, 2009).

Ontology is the philosophical assumption necessary to bear in mind when studying social phenomena. It involves understanding the nature of existence (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Chilisa (2012) defined "Ontology as the body of knowledge that deals with the essential characteristics of what it means to exist" (p. 20). In a qualitative inquiry, understanding what is real can be viewed from a social constructivist perspective. Social constructivism understands the social phenomenon as continually influenced by social actors through interactions (Bryman, 2008). The idea has roots in the work of Berger and Luckmann (1991), who asserted that human beings and society have a dialectic relationship. It implies that social interaction between human beings influences notions and understandings of phenomena. It, in turn, is reflected in the

individuals who adapt to the institutions or cultures that are continuously fashioned and constructed. Qualitative research with a constructionist lens hence understands the social world as constructions. It means that there is not one definite truth, which involves that the presentation of an account is colored by the involved participants and the meaning they construct together and in interaction with the researcher (Bryman, 2008).

Through an interpretive constructivist position, the researcher is considered a traveler, one that encourages individuals to talk about their study (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). In qualitative research, the researcher is considered the main instrument in the research process (Kvale & Brinkmann). It is to social constructionist thought, where new meanings are created through interactions. The researcher brings in her worldviews and interpretations and thus presents one account of reality. Thus, a value-free investigation is desirable, but whether it is realizable can be discussed. Consequently, the researcher must reflect on ethical and personal issues during the process (Creswell, 2009).

In this study, the investigator tries to investigate how individuals experience the circumstances in which they learn and teach and their perception of the role and outcomes their participation in the classes can have in their lives. Qualitative research offers an understanding of people's lived experiences, attitudes, meanings, and behaviors and gives an opinion to those who participate (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2011), which is some of the core issues of the research. The inquiry in his study focused on understanding an educational experience within a social world. Thus, it aimed to describe, explore, and interpret the teaching methods currently used by technology in Bangladesh, as well as the factors that influence their choice of teaching methods. Consequently, he uses the tools of Grounded theory not for theory generation but because they allow concurrent analysis and iteration. This choice was dependent on the assumption that the tools of Grounded theory would provide a better understanding and interpretation of the area under investigation since the mechanisms of Grounded theory permit the researcher to go beyond simple description and exploration of a study to an explanation of it. It has been important also the outset of the study to make a clear ontological and epistemological position, i.e., to clarify that position as regards the study was a relativist and subjectivist to allow the examined issue to be understood relatively according to the outcome of the interaction with the participants of the study.

Moreover, whereas the traditional interpretive research methods follow a linear mechanism in conducting and analyzing a study (i.e., a researcher starts collecting data and then analyses it), the methodological procedure of Grounded theory is a circular mechanism that helps a researcher to conduct and analyze data concurrently (Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Denzin & Lincoln, 2008; Birks & Mills, 2011; Arthur et al., 2012). Thus, such a circular mechanism permitted us to be very close to the sample and investigate the research issues in-depth by collecting data from the interviews and then supplementing the interview data with data from the questionnaires. The researcher also collects additional data if the examined issues need more explanation by conducting further interviews (iteration) or referring to the documentary sources and using behaviorism and social constructivism theory as a theoretical framework for analyzing data and discussing the findings.

The study also theorizes ethnographic research methodology as 'deep hanging out.' The phrase 'deep hanging out' also hints at a contrast between methods of cultural anthropology and political science (Gusterson, 2008, p.93). It emphasizes methodological interests more unique to the ethnographic combat, such as gaining access to the fieldwork, doing semi-structured interviews, participant observation, and navigating the ethical obligations of fieldwork (Gusterson, 2008, p.94).

4.3 Research process

The figure below displays the overall operation of the study, from the selection of the site to the data analysis. In the following text, the researcher elaborates on all choices made during the process, which have been determining factors of knowledge production.

Figure 8: Research process

4.4 Location selection

The research topic is computer-assisted language learning at higher secondary Schools in Bangladesh, so research sites are selected in Bangladesh. The researcher always wanted to balance the data from a rural area and an urban area, so that might get the primary feature of his research topic because the urban area has more facilities than the rural area.

The investigator leaves Norway to do his fieldwork in Bangladesh and lives in his home in Dhaka. He takes preparation for fieldwork, makes an interview guide, and sends it to supervisor Merethe Skårås. She gives some advice and instruction and finalizes the interview guides. Then he selects two higher secondary institutions: one from Dhaka city and another from Comilla Division's rural area near Dhaka district so that he can go there from his residence. Another reason to select Comilla is that one of his friends works there so that he can get easy access to the school. Another school selects from Dhaka city, where he is a director. However,

he did not work on his research site or in a different branch, so students do not know him, and he introduced them as a researcher from Norway who came only to do research.

4.5 Gaining access

For the research sites of Comilla, the researcher contacts his friend, and after getting the green signal, he goes to his research site. He lives there with his friend and his friend's two colleagues. They, all three, live there in an apartment. On the first day, the principal does not present at the school, so he waits for the next day. The next day he meets the principal and submits his papers to the principal and tells him his purpose why he comes here. The principal receives his documents and tells him to come tomorrow. The following day he tells the researcher, yes, go ahead. Then the researcher starts his observation in school B first. It was from July the third week to the fourth week.

In the same way, he goes to school A in Dhaka city and submits his papers to the principal. The principal discusses the management committee and replies to the researcher, yes, go ahead. The investigator observes two classes here each day from August first week and second week, and he gets access to his research sites; he does not face the mentionable problem.

4.6 Sample selection

The study uses stratified random and purposive sampling procedures, which involve randomly selecting the sample to fulfill the research goals (Bryman, 2008). Informants are thus chosen due to the potential of being information to the issue under study (Patton, 2002). Because qualitative research seeks to understand a phenomenon detailed and in-depth, the sample size is small, whereas the larger sample size, selected randomly, is imperative in quantitative research (Patton). Because the sample size is small in qualitative research, there is a reduced generalization ability. However, the overall goal of qualitative research is not to be able to generalize about a phenomenon but rather to result in knowledge about "the particular description and themes developed in the context of a specific site" (Creswell, 2009, p. 193).

Within a stratified sampling, the study employed a combination of different strategies. According to Patton (2002), it can benefit the sample because research often serves multiple purposes. The sample selection is facilitated by criterion sampling, which involves the participants being chosen because they fit predetermined criteria relevant to the research questions (Patton). Criteria are students studying in two schools in Dhaka and Comilla and participating at higher secondary levels. The other participants are selected due to the schoolteachers and principals under the study. The figure below illustrates the informants and their relevance to the research.

Figure 9: Participants' relevance to the research.

Criterion sampling is combined with opportunistic or emergent sampling since flexibility shapes a large part of the fieldwork, with emerging opportunities that are adjusted to and taken advantage of. The study is planned and designed in Norway, where relevant literature is read to prepare for fieldwork. However, there are limitations on how much one can expect from a research design before entering a site since many elements must be changed during the process (Creswell, 2009). The researcher should hence be flexible and respond to uncertainties and changes that may occur (Scheyvens & Storey, 2003).

In the study mentioned earlier, the researcher selects two schools using area sampling, then collects the sample by stratified random sampling proportionate for the focus group interview. Conducting an individual interview has no opportunity to make stratified sampling commensurate. However, because of limited time, he decided on a sample size of around 24 persons as it is a qualitative study method with limited observation and interviews as the preferred method.

The sample can be Principals, Language teachers, and students. The table below shows the overall sample.

Table 1: The overall sample.

Sample	Size	Female	Male	Total
Students	16	8	8	16
Language Teachers	6	0	6	6
Principals	2	0	2	2
Total				24

The interview involves six English language teachers, two principals, and sixteen students. Nowadays, there is increasing use of focus group interviews. So, the investigator conducts four focus group discussions among the student participants. It is two female students' groups and two male students' groups. So, he selects four focus group discussions (16 student participants) and individual interviews (6 language teachers and two principals). From school A, he chose humanities section higher secondary first-year boys' students (second-year students are unavailable then) and business studies section A girls' students. After observing the class lesson, he selects an element by a simple random selection procedure with the help of participant TA2. He selects four male and four female participants for two focus group interview sessions. Using the same process, he chooses from school B four male participants and four female participants with the help of teacher participant TB1 for two focus group interview sessions. Unfortunately, the researcher does not get any female teachers or principal participants.

4.6.1 Research Participants

Here is a general description of the research participants interviewed at the two sites. They are 44 organized in three tables; one for students (Focus Group Interviews, student number 1-4 group 1 and 5-8 group 2), one for English language teachers, and one for the principals. Twenty-four people are interviewed: sixteen students (four focus group interviews), six English language teachers, and two heads (individual interviews).

Each of the coming three tables mentions a reference code for the participants, which will be used in the findings chapter to specify who says what. For example, find appendix # 4, a more itemized list of code names given to each participant. An example of such code is SA1; when the system starts with S/T/H, it refers to student/teacher/head, A/B refers to school, and the number at the end refers to a specific student, teacher, or administrator.

In the first table below, the students are described; what gender they are and whether they are in their first or second year of higher secondary school, gender, age, and academic qualification.

Table 2: Students participants

STUDENTS	School A (8 students, two focus groups: 1 & 2)	School B (8 students, two focus groups: 1 & 2)
Reference (code name) in thesis	Focus Group 1: SA1, SA2, SA3 & SA4,	Focus Group 1: SB1, SB2, SB3 & SB4,
	Focus Group 2: SA5, SA6, SA7 & SA8	Focus Group 2: SB5, SB6, SB7 & SB8
Gender	Four females and four males	Four females and four males
Age	16 to 17 years	16 to 17 years
Year in HSC	All are in year 1	All are in year 1

Academic background	Bangladeshi Public Education is called general education, and all students have already passed the secondary school certificate (SSC).	Bangladeshi Public Education is called general education, and all students have already passed the secondary school certificate (SSC).
---------------------	--	--

Information on the six English language teachers interviewed in the two research sites can be found in the following table, along with gender, age, education, and work experience.

Table 3: Teacher participants

TEACHERS	School A (3 Teachers)	School B (3 Teachers)
Reference names (code name) in the thesis	TA1, TA2 & TA3	TB1, TB2 & TB3
Gender	3 males & 0 females	3 males & 0 females
Age	TA1: 40 years, TA2: 29 years & TA3: 25 years.	TB1: 28 years, TB2: 45 years & TB3: 50 years.
Academic background	Honors with a Master in English Language and Literature	Honors with a Master in English Language and Literature
Work experience: this job	TA1: 15 years, TA2: 3 years & TA3: 1 year.	TB1: 5 years, TB2: 20 years & TB3: 25 years.

Information on the two leading members the researcher managed to interview can be found in the following table. Aside from the information on gender, age, and academic background, subjects they teach or have taught.

Table 4: Head of institutions participants

HEADS (Principals)	School A (1)	School B (1)
Reference names (code name) in the thesis	HA1	HB1
Gender	Male	Male
Age	HA1: 52 years	HB1: 49 years
Academic background	Honors with a master in Arabic Language and Islamic Studies	Honors with a master's in political science.
Other subjects taught roles (had) in the current school.	Principal and Islamic Studies teacher.	Principal and Social science teacher.

4.7 Semi-structured observation

The interview can be an efficient way to construct knowledge, but there are limitations regarding how much one can learn from what people reveal through talk. Only some aspects of a phenomenon can capture through interviews; it is thus imperative to consider other methods for accurate knowledge production. "Observation is a powerful tool for gaining insight into situations. As with other data-collection techniques, observation engages issues of validity and reliability (Cohen et al., 2018, p. 562). Borrowing from Patton (2002), "To understand the complexities of many situations fully, direct participation in and observation of the phenomenon of interest may be the best research method" (p. 21). Hence, listening, watching, reflecting, and engaging with students and teachers through participant observation can provide insight into lifeworld (Mayall, 2008). Where interviews can give ideas to subjective meanings, observations can contribute to externally observable behaviors (Patton, 2002). Therefore, interviews as a research method supplement with observations to describe the context where people live. According to Marshall and Rossman (2016), observation is more than just looking. It is looking (often systematically) and consistently noting people, events, behaviors, settings, artifacts, and routines. According to Patton (2002), this methodological triangulation strengthens a study by using multiple methods to investigate a phenomenon. Direct observation is imperative for a holistic understanding; one does not have to rely on other sources and can see elements of the context that can take for granted by the participants (Patton). The researcher can hence discover factors overlooked by those living in the setting. Denscombe (2014) states that it can be systematic and structured or take some less structured form, such as participant observation (p. 205). Observation allows an investigator to collect first-hand, 'live' data from naturally occurring social situations rather than, for example, reported data (Wellington, 2015). Nevertheless, although observations can give valuable contributions to data collection, the researcher should also, according to Patton, bear in mind that their observations are value-laden perceptions. It is necessary to acknowledge this kind of reflection.

Actively participating in the life of the observed means going where the action is, getting one's hands dirty, participating where possible in actual program activities, and getting to know program staff and participants on a personal level- in other words, getting engaged personally to use all of one's senses and capacities, including the capacity to experience affect no less than cognition. (Patton, 2002, p. 48)

The above quote implies that one researcher must fully engage in the participants' realities, which naturally occur in this research process. Bryman (2008) has suggested that the inquirer will feel forced to participate in the studied activities since a lack of involvement can send signals questioning her commitment to the setting, resulting in losing credibility. When the researcher starts observation, he informs the participants and takes permission from the teachers' participants, and they provide him with their class routine, where he mentions the class time and room number. He attends school A, two teachers' classes, and the students are first-year humanities boys' section, 20 students, and business studies girls' section A, 45 students. Likewise, he observes at school B in the first year. There are 65 students in one section (language class takes place with all students' science, business studies, and humanities), and

three teachers take classes. So, he informed all three teachers previously and took their class routine.

Participant observation, the essence of the deep hanging out, denotes a research method in which researchers join in the flow of daily life while also taking notes (Gusterson, 2008, p. 99). His observation takes place in two ways, one is taking notes, and another is audio recording; however, He does not take all 30 class hours of audio. Instead, he records only a few audios during the observation time.

4.8 Interview preparations

After finishing the observation, take preparation for the interview. The researcher checks his mobile video recorder for capturing video records and contacts with the teachers. First, he arranges focus group interviews in school A and organizes them at their school. Then teachers' participants and finally, the principal. Similarly, he arranges in school B. students are eager to participate in their interview.

4.9 Interview guides

Before taking the interview, the researcher prepares three different interview guides for group discussions (students) and individual interviews (teachers and principals), which he sent to his supervisor Merethe Skårås. She suggested making some necessary changes. After editing, he takes it as the final interview guide.

4.10 Setting

A research interview is considered a professional conversation with certain power symmetry between the interviewer and interviewee (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). It is thus not an everyday conversation between equal partners but rather a conversation facilitated with techniques for the interviewer to get insight into the participants' meanings relevant to the issue under study (Kvale & Brinkmann). It is attempted through semi-structured interviews, which provide the interview setting with a guide to cover topics of interest (Kvale & Brinkmann).

The qualitative researcher is considered a traveler who meets and interacts with people and encourages them to talk about their experiences (Kvale & Brinkmann). Data collection is conducted in a natural setting, where the role of the researcher is to get insight into the participants' lifeworld by talking and interacting (Creswell, 2009). Knowledge is thus constructed between the researcher and the researched, in line with social constructionist thought. An important consideration, based on the non-naturalistic setting of the interview, is that the outcome can result in artificial knowledge, where the interviewer asks questions, and the interviewee politely responds (Greener, 2011). It is thus vital to reflect upon elements of the interview that accomplishes or fails to enhance the reliability of interviews as a method. It is particularly urgent to emphasize how power has influenced the construction of knowledge.

Power is innate in human conversation and relation, asserted by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). It implies that the total elimination of power from a conversation is impossible. Thus,

the researcher is responsible for reflecting on the power asymmetry between him and the participants. When interviewing students, it is imperative to recognize the power relations that emerge from the setting. Although the investigator does not consider him an authority, he has to acknowledge that he probably is from their point of view.

In line with the phenomenological assumption, the social researcher is concerned with how individuals make sense of the world (Bryman, 2008). Thus, the researcher is responsible for gaining access to participants who feel comfortable in a space natural to them since the researcher should strive to make the interview setting as naturalistic as possible (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009).

All three different interviews are arranged at school, both in school A and school B. According to social bindings, it is not possible to take an interview outside the schools and not possibly arrange all students outside the school. To arrange everything the teachers' participants help him a lot. The focus group interview setting is their regular classroom in schools A and B. After finishing their regular class, he informed them to wait for the interview, which takes a maximum of two hours in each group. Finally, the researcher interviews four focus group interviews (School A, two groups, and school B, two groups). In each group, there are four students (mentioned earlier).

The teachers are interviewed informal setting (in school) since it is difficult to contact them outside the school. The context might influence their responses as they are diplomatic while talking formally. The interview session took 15 to 20 minutes. The principals' interviews are also taken in their offices. Since they are in a structured environment surrounded by other staff and sometimes colleagues, they are very diplomatic while talking. However, they answer all questions whatever the investigator asks them and cooperate with him a lot. They know the researcher is also a teacher, so they always help him find actual data.

4.11 Interviews

The researcher discusses here in this subsection different kinds of interviews. 4.11.1 Students' interview or Focus Group Discussion and 4.11.2 teachers and principals' interview or individual interview.

4.11.1 Focus group discussion

A Focus group interview is a qualitative method for data collection. A focus group is "a group involved of individuals with definite characteristics who focus discussions on a given topic or issue" (Anderson, 1990, p. 241). Denscombe (2007, p.115) states, "focus group comprises of a small group of individuals, frequently between six and nine in quantity, who are brought collected by a trained researcher to discover attitudes and perceptions, feelings and ideas about an issue." Rice & Ezzy (1999) claim that Bogardus.⁶ In 1926 primarily explained

⁶ Emory S. Bogardus (1882-1973), in full Emory Stephen Bogardus, served as President of the American Sociological Society in 1931.

group interviews in social science studies. Throughout World War II, Merton⁷ They also have expanded focus groups to analyze people's answers about war-related information and the effectiveness of the soldiers' training contents. In the 1950s, market investigators began to use this method to gather more precise information about consumer product likings. (Denscombe, 2007; Patton, 2002; Wisker, 2001; Anderson, 1990). After that, focus group interviews spread broadly to social inquiry. However, Rice and Ezzy (1999) argue that between 1950 and 1980, focus groups vanished from social research disciplines. Morgan (1997) asserts that this technique should be addressed by the original supporters and researchers who generally favored other procedures. However, focus groups have recently become popular among qualitative investigators in social sciences. Casey and Krueger's (2000) opinion focus group delivers "a more natural environment than that of a separate interview for participants are persuading and influenced by others- impartial as they are in physical life" (p.11). Focus group discussion intentions to collect high-quality data in a social setting (Patton, 2002) to understand a particular problem from the viewpoint of the participants of the research (Khan & Manderson, 1992). The subject of why and when focus group discussion should be used is very significant. Firstly, focus group discussion may be valuable when the investigator needs more information about the subjects. Focus group offers "an ironic and detailed set of data about insights, opinions, stances and impressions of people in their own arguments" (Stewart & Shamdasani, 1990, p.140). Also, focus groups are primarily beneficial when a researcher aims to discover people's understanding and experiences about the subject and the causes behind their thinking patterns. (Kitzinger, 1995).

Focus group interviews are "naturalistic rather than natural events and should not leave to chance and situation" (Bloor et al., 2001, p. 57). The researcher shows a critical role in arranging, conducting, and governing the focus group process. The experienced and skilled moderator verifies the data quality generated through focus group discussion. Several ideas need to be considered at the planning stage.

First, the researcher studied the objectives of the focus group. He contacts the participants beforehand and makes them aware of the goal of the action. Selecting a suitable class of persons for the focus group is vital. It is essential to decide who can provide the preferred information. Occasionally one single group of individuals can deliver the required data. However, it should not be limited to one target person when some may be related to the problem (Anderson, 1990). The time and location of the discussion should be decided to keep in view the suitability of the participants. It is also to confirm that the place is obstruction-free. Deciding what and how many inquiries are to be asked is essential for each interview. The inquiries may have both content and process functions. Concerning content, five or six interview questions are comprised in many focus group interviews. Still, much conversation can occur because of the group process, and the investigator asks more than that, consulting his supervisor. Anderson (1990) gives some strategies for composing the questions for focus groups: focus group questions are always open-ended, interview guides must be "qualitative"

⁷ Robert K. Merton, full Robert King Merton, and the original name are Meyer Robert Schkolnick (1910-2003), an American sociologist whose diverse interests included the sociology of science and the professions, sociological theory, and mass communication.

and quantifiers, avoid items that have a likely 'yes' or 'no' answers, use of the directive method is avoided to know the motives behind a particular standpoint or reaction of the participant, consequently 'why' question is not usually asked, a large number of queries may be outlined through brainstorming, and then maybe reduced to problems as required and the item should be arranged in a natural flow.

As regards the characteristics of the participants, it usually is believed that participants may allocate some common attributes so that communication may happen to an optimum level and situations may be avoided where a person dwarf or withdraw. However, there needs to be more view among the experts on whether homogeneous or heterogeneous group best serves the purpose of focus group discussion. Several authors (Dawson et al., 1993; Morgan, 1997) claim that if the subjects belong to the same communal and cultural setting, e.g., age, sex, religion, socio-economic background, occupation, and educational background, ethnicity, it will confirm the free-flowing, open and sincere discussion among the contributors. Instead, some writers (Anderson, 1990; Khan et al., 1991) believe that the heterogeneous group arrangement of the focus group works pleasantly. Moreover, the investigator must inquire as to what nature of the group— homogeneous or heterogeneous may best realize the objectives of his study. So, the researcher arranges a homogeneous group with the same sex, age, occupation, and educational background group for better data.

With slight differences, many authors (Anderson, 1990; Denscombe, 2007; Morgan, 1997; Patton, 2002; Ritchie & Lewis, 2003; Stewart & Shamdasani, 1990) advise that the size of the focus group should range from six (6) to twelve (12) participants. It is claimed that if the number is less than six, it is easier to deliver the synergy needed. The data gained may need to be more affluent and abundant, and one or two persons may try to control the discussion. Conversely, managing a group with more than twelve participants is intrinsically challenging. The group may break down into factions, and participants may need help finding adequate opportunities to talk in a big group. However, small focus groups can be used when the topic needs to be explored with greater strength and where participants have long and substantial knowledge to share with the group (Anderson, 1990). Previously he mentioned that in this research, four participants participated in each group.

Like other qualitative methods, the focus group members are not selected randomly. Preferably a purposive sampling method is usually used (Dawson et al., 1993; Morgan, 1997; Patton, 2002). The investigator selects the participants who suit the topic/ problem under study. Purposive sampling assists the researcher in finding the information-rich cases that may best crop the essential data. The question of how many focus group interviews are desired to confirm the proper coverage of the topic is fundamental. In most situations, the saturation system is applied. It means that researchers usually gather data until they get essential new information. Anderson (1990) witnesses that the first two groups mainly give significant further details, and the discussion is chiefly tired when the researcher gets into the third or fourth session.

Starting the session with several transitional periods is highly desirable. At this stage, participants can be positioned at ease by serving them refreshments and engaging them in small

talk. However, talking about the critical issue of the focus group interview should be avoided. The researcher starts the formal group session by thanking the participants for coming and concisely stating the group's purpose. They may also be informed earlier about why they are nominated for the discussion. Finally, the researcher emphasizes the rules of secrecy and invites them to ask queries if they want any.

As the process develops, the moderator presents the questions one by one. To facilitate the interaction between the group participants, the researcher continually delivers probes and pauses and involves participants in discussion without expressing any value on the answers received (Anderson, 1990). Rice and Ezzy (1999) advise that a focus group may be held in the mother tongue of the subjects. A bilingual moderator or translator may be used if the researcher and participants' languages are diverse. The researcher researches his home country so that he can use his translation without a translator or bilingual moderator. As a general regulation, the average duration of a focus group is two hours (Rice & Ezzy, 1999). With exceptions, the focus group discussions are primarily directed for one and a half hours. Ultimately, the researcher should thank the members for their valuable contributions to the study. Anderson's (1990) point of view, providing a summary of the conversation to the members is undesirable because achieving consensus is different from the aim of a focus group but exploring maximally the various perspectives held by participants.

For data analysis, it is essential to record the discussion truthfully. The participants' answers may be recorded generally in two ways: It is taking notes and tape recording. Note-taking is required for an interview. A moderator or assistant moderator may record the conversations in written letters. The recorder must not indicate the value of their responses to the group members and must not note only the best answers (Anderson, 1990). When taking notes, writing time references in the margin, and highlighting or underlining the specific significant points is beneficial. So, the researcher uses mobile audio and takes notes; the audio recorder is activated beforehand and then starts the session and takes notes.

In notetaking, the note-taker may need to be more capable of recording everything discussed within the group. Recording discussion by tape recorder is vital and mostly advised for all the focus groups (Rice & Ezzy, 1999). It is recommended that an inconspicuous recording device should be used so that the group atmosphere may not be troubled. The use of tape recording gives the benefit of accessing a complete record of a rich data source. On the limitation side, it is always laborious to listen to the tape. Taking written notes is applicable even when a tape recorder records the discussion.

The method of data analysis must begin immediately after the group sessions end. Anderson (1990) has given some helpful advice for data analysis. He sympathizes with looking first for major principles and making a list of them, considering words and the contextual background of their use, trying to scrutinize the strength of the reactions or feelings, and striking stability between detail and conciseness.

Anderson (1990) detects two critical types of reporting focus group data: Conducting analysis and reporting a summary of the principal thoughts; second, giving the subject's words verbatim. Which method is to be used depends on the researcher's purpose and projected readers. Anderson prefers combining narrative synopses with actual quotes that explain the participant's views in his or her own words. Focus groups are generally helpful when they are consistent with the research objectives. However, Merton et al. (1990) recognize the four criteria for judging the focus group's quality: range, specificity, depth, and personal context. Consistent with Krueger (1998), factors that regulate the effectiveness of focus group interviews are clarity of objective, appropriate setting, adequate resources, enough subjects, skilled moderator, challenging questions, and honoring the participants. Gorman and Clayton (2005) classify some strengths of the focus group interviews. Rich qualitative data can be gathered with reasonable speed since focus group sessions require only an adequate time commitment from participants and mediators. Depending on the number of interview guides and the difficulty of the issues, between one to two hours are sufficient for most interviews. Focus group members can see what is being done and almost invariably accept that the process is appropriate. Members are encouraged to converse with each other rather than merely respond to the mediator. This way, the range and complication of attitudes and viewpoints can emerge. Focus groups deal with an opportunity for instant feedback or clarification on one's perspective, with the contributions of other group participants. They enable a researcher to consider what is said and gestures, facial expressions, and other non-verbal interactions. Focus group interviews can allow a researcher to explore the unimagined aspects of the problem under study.

Several boundaries are associated with the focus group interview (Gorman & Clayton, 2005). It is significantly challenging to get people together on time for the group session (Gibbs, 1997). A few vocal participants may control other participants during a group interview. Due to the nature of group conversation, some members may conform to other participants' responses, even if they disagree. Sometimes it is very problematic for the researcher to find the group with the required features. However, the success of a focus group is only good if the moderator is skilled in handling group interaction.

Focus group interviews entered academic and social research in the 1980s. His focus group aims not to reach a consensus about, or solutions to, the issues discussed but to bring forward different viewpoints (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009) on computer-assisted language learning. Focus group interviews are lively collective interactions, which may bring more cognitive interviews ahead.

4.11.2 Teachers and principals' interview

The researcher discusses the teachers' and principals' meetings in this section. In the following subsection, he discusses teachers' and principals' interviews.

Teacher's interview

A semi-structured interview is the second method for this research, and with this form of the method, the investigator develops interview guides thematically and enthusiastically. After observing 15 class hours, he interviews six English language teachers from two higher

secondary institutions. He tries to talk to three female teachers and three male teachers. However, there are no female teachers at all. Teacher interviews are held in the teachers' standard room after leaving all other teachers in schools A and B.

Principals interview

Moreover, principals' meetings are held after teacher interviews at the principal's offices. Finally, the researcher captures the video of all teacher and principal interviews with his mobile phone and keeps it on his laptop. Previously, he took permission that captures video of the whole interview sessions.

4.12 Data analysis

There is no substitute for intimate engagement with data. Researchers should consider data as something to cuddle with, embrace and get to know better. They are reading, rereading, and, once more, forcing the researcher to become intimate with the material. People, events, and quotations continuously sift through the researcher's mind. (Marshall & Rossman, 2011, p. 210)

As the above quote suggests, analyzing data is an intimate affair that demands an iterative process of reading and reflecting. The multi-method approach employs in the study, including field notes, reflective notes, thoughts, and insights, provides a large amount of material for analysis. Due to the few analytic measures in qualitative inquiries, it knows where to start and what to look after too much work (Bryman, 2008). Codification materials are not fixed, as with quantitative research, but there are some broad guidelines. The below figure shows the process of analysis that guided his research method.

Figure 10: The process of analysis.

With the overwhelming amount of material obtained from a qualitative research inquiry, it is imperative to keep a record of the interviews and notes taken along the process (Marshall & Rossman, 2011). Thus, all documents are labeled with the date, time, and participants' names involved. It eases the iterative process and enables an organized analysis course. To reduce material into relevant themes, the researcher uses elements of grounded theory when coding. The working definition of grounded theory is "theory derived from data, systematically

gathered and analyzed through the research process" (Bryman, 2008, p. 541). It implies that the selection of the abovementioned elements will, because of the analysis and coding process, merge into developing a new theory. Charmaz (2006) distinguishes between two forms of coding: initial and focused coding. From the coding process, he finds salient themes that the informants repeated, revealing their importance in the participants' lifeworld while reducing the material's richness into codes. He writes analytic memos to describe how the data are coming together. Writing is a large part of the qualitative research process in helping to reflect and analyze thoughtfully, as the researcher needs to be fully always immersed in the process (Marshall & Rossman, 2011). Finally, based on the themes, it becomes possible to merge the data of students, teachers, and principals and connect their experiences to the theory.

Grounded theory is the method of theory origination used in data analysis. According to Cohen et al. (2011, p. 599), grounded theory is contrived to "build and generate theory rather than to test an existing theory." The grounded theory method, therefore, obtains to develop a theory from the scientifically collected and examined data. Nonetheless, existing theories and literature have enhanced understanding and describe the findings in chapter 5.

Throughout the analysis process, the researcher uses a bricolage technique, i.e., a mix of analytical tools (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015), to produce meaning from his data. Kvale and Brinkmann (2015) argue, "the outcome of this form of meaning generation can be in words, in numbers, in figures or a combination of those" (p. 268). Therefore, his analysis comprises reading throughout the material, remarking on specific passages of interest, open coding (Cohen et al., 2011), considering and highlighting statements based on themes, and employing statements and the frequency of each participant in a table. This latter method finds commonalities, patterns, similarities, and differences among the three institutions that conform to Cohen et al.'s (2011) understanding of qualitative data analysis. Therefore, the table's fundamental purpose is not to form statistics but to see the common themes among girls and boys. Even though using numbers in qualitative research is controversial, Maxwell (2010) still contends that scientific data helps construct claims such as 'many,' 'most,' 'often,' and 'some' more precisely. What he here appeals to as 'quasi-statistics' turned out to be the periphery for studying the challenges and resources in this research and producing a more detailed analysis.

Now having described the considerations that have shaped the research process, the researcher gives attention to the final and most essential factors in this research. The reviews ensure the well-being, protection, and interest of the research participants, along with the quality of the study.

4.13 Ethical concerns

Hammersley and Atkinson (2007) tilt five critical ethical issues that characteristically concern ethnographic studies; the privacy of the participant; do not harm; getting informed consent; exploitation of those studied, and possible consequences for future research. The investigator needs to go into detail on all five. However, they are worth mentioning as they are imperative to reflect on when preparing and conducting Global South fieldwork. To the best of

his capability, he has tried to carry out his research according to all five ethical issues. However, there are some features of researching the Global South. He cannot deny having an adverse effect. The power relations between him as a researcher and those being 'researched' is compulsory when doing research. This unequal power relation might never be as observable and indisputable. In history, research has gotten a negative nuance and reputation in many areas of the Global South (Smith, 2012).

With research comes issues of colonialization, globalization, exploitation, westernization, and inequality, among other negative impacts. The researcher's presence in urban and rural areas called for deep reflections on his position in the society he is studying, his role as a researcher, and the power that comes with it. He strives to follow the "no harm" principle during his fieldwork. Scheyvens, Nowak, and Scheyvens (2003) explore that to "not harm" is not enough, that research should have the opportunity to do good, and that the research should include empowerment of the informants. Hugman, Pittaway, and Bartolomei (2011) advise participatory action research to ensure the inclusion and empowerment of informants. With participatory action research, the method is only participatory when it is collaborative, and the power between researcher and research is equalized (Cohen et al., 2011). Complete impartiality between his informants and he is challenging to obtain, and he cannot claim to have conducted participatory action research. Time and resources are also a factor that limits this probability. The power disparity between the researcher and researcher is divided into two levels; real difference and perceived difference (Scheyvens, Nowak, et al., 2003). The real difference is what was most evident throughout his fieldwork as education and clearly illustrates the difference in what they strive for and what he may take for granted. The perceived difference is present in the minds of the informants and the researcher in the sense that one might feel inferior and the other superior (Scheyvens, Nowak, et al., 2003). Research should then refrain from strengthening suppressive emotions or giving the informants the feeling of powerlessness. Emphasized by Scheyvens, Murray, et al. (2003) is the significance of examining his motivation for the fieldwork, being aware of his biases, examining his position as a researcher in the given society, and reflecting upon the power disparity. However, his research topic is relatively sensitive, so he can avoid facing too much power imbalance. In the following subsection, 4.13.1, he discusses informed consent, which explains the participants' privacy.

4.13.1 Informed consent

Before going to the field, the researcher wrote a detailed letter of consent aimed at his different aged participants, containing information about the research and their rights as informers. All research participants are above the age of 16 and entitled to participate without parents' consent and have, therefore, made their choice on their behalf. For his research to be ethical, all informers must consent to participate based on fully understanding both risks and benefits of the contribution. As Hugman et al. (2011) state, desperate for assistance and seeming to agree to contribute in the hope of benefitting in some way or another, it is urgent to explain with simple words and to confirm with the participants whether they fully comprehend or not. Significantly, all the participants are aware of their relationship with him and his role as an investigator in this context, which clearly explains their potential towards the situation and even the different unequal power relations. Underlying all effort during his fieldwork is the principle

of "not harm" (Hugman et al., 2011; Wood, 2006). Wood explores that informed consent aids in confirming that he is an investigator who "do not harm." Hugman et al., however, in their investigation, claim that the principle of "not harm" is insufficient without assimilating respect, beneficence, and justice. What Hugman et al. propose is that the study goes beyond gathering consent to including the participants in the research. While time and resources are limited and participatory research is hard to carry out, he attempts to make other aspects of his exploration as comprehensive as possible, mainly by giving data and gathering informed consent.

During the first period in higher secondary school A, he understood that his consent paper was too advanced and severe to understand student participants. After presenting the informed consent to four students, he comprehends that he must both give information about the research and gather their consent verbally, which turns out more effective and inclusive for the participants since they become a part of the conversation on how, where, and why. He must shorten his language throughout the procedure and ensure they understand the gist to avoid misunderstandings and vagueness. Confidentiality and the integrity of the participants are provided throughout the fieldwork their secrecy. The identity of all his participants is kept anonymous in recordings and inquiry, and they have all code names in this research project.

The investigator tries to maintain confidentiality for the participants' replies, which he always preserves. He maintains the informed consent of participants to interview by fully explaining the intentions behind the study and the research process, so they are not cheated. As he does his research in his home country, he transcribes and gives it to the participants, who sign so that the transcription of interviews becomes authentic. He also informed the participants of their right to withdraw at any time. Finally, he gives his findings to those participants and schools participating in this study.

4.14 Trustworthiness in the study

This research project uses 'trustworthiness' to assess the findings. As an umbrella phrase for validity and reliability (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015), trustworthiness is to label these aspects of his study, hence the actual value of his findings. Integrity and relevance are substitutes for validity and reliability in calculating qualitative research. The researcher contends that validity and reliability are notions that fit best to evaluate qualitative studies like this research project owing to the emphasis on validity and reliability to practice the same methods and indicators in numerous research projects. Assessing validity and reliability can be observed as concepts closer to the pragmatist worldview where reality is viewed as 'hard,' single, and available for investigators to understand, making the ideas more appropriate in qualitative research. The operationalized meanings used in this study project will not straightforwardly be transferred to other research projects because the investigator, people contributing, the lived experience and knowledge the informants and the researcher has at the time the research is carried out, and the setting will be different. When using semi-structured interview guides, several of the questions asked during the individual interviews vary from one conversation to another depending on the responses and assertions from the interviewees. Even if another researcher should use the interview guide, they would likely not find the same follow-up questions relevant because the answers might differ. The new researcher would also interpret things differently than he does.

An investigator should decide to interview the same people interviewed in this study. In that case, their answers will most likely be somewhat different in the following interview because they might have established new understandings during and after the discussions done in this research (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015, p.3 & 15; Bryman 2016, p.33 & 374-375, 384; Cohen et al. 2018, p.6). Trustworthiness (in this research), which focuses on the informers' life experiences and the lived world, lies in the researcher's ability to represent their subjective reality (Cohen et al., 2011). However, as there always are validity threats that may question the trustworthiness of his study, he adopts some aspects that may guarantee validity. The limited time with the participants during his fieldwork may impact the participants' answers. He will get personal, thorough explanations if he conducts a long-term ethnographic study (Maxwell, 2013). At the same time, the concept of 'thick descriptions' (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015; Cohen et al., 2011) or 'rich data' (Maxwell, 2013) where he, as an investigator, is provided with sufficient context to be able to make meaning of behaviors, lived experiences of the participants and their presence in the settlement, might increase the validity of the research. Triangulation lies in the mixture of methods, namely his observations and interviews, as well as his diverse sets of data (Cohen et al., 2011), hence the number of interviews and discussions and the variety of age and educational institutions of the participants, which give rich and in-depth data about their lived experiences. Using numbers, or 'quasi-statistics,' also makes the amount of information and my claims of phenomena in his findings more precise and explicit (Maxwell, 2013).

However, there is still a risk of validity threats, such as researcher bias (Cohen et al., 2011; Maxwell, 2013). To eradicate threats to the trustworthiness of his research, he records and transcribes all interviews and checks for errors by re-listening to the recording (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015), as he does not get to confirm member checks. Re-listening and ensuring the transcription and translation quality generates rich data and reduces some bias as he let the pragmatic data lead toward a grounded theory. The interview guides he asks during the interviews and group discussions and their wording (ref. Appendix # 1, 2, and 3) may also influence the trustworthiness of his research (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). At the same time, he says that his interview guides him to research what he intends to study, namely the participants' perception of their own lived world.

In this study, the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability, dependability, and authenticity are virtual channels. The following subsections will explore how these aspects have pertained to the study.

4.14.1. Transferability

The researcher is responsible for giving the correct presentations of the information the individuals give. It can be achieved by writing convincing narratives that capture many perspectives of a theme which will help describe the setting realistically, ensuring the study's transferability (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Transferability is like external validity, how research findings can be transferred to other contexts (Bryman, 2016, p.384). The researcher has described the research context, theoretical perspectives, and research methods in a way that allows the reader to assess whether the research findings can be transferred to other contexts.

When viewing reality as multiple and socially constructed, he has done his best to ensure that the research has been carried out in line with the best research practices and to transfer the knowledge acquired during the course on research methodology in the master's degree into the whole research process.

To better certify that the research findings are transferrable to other contexts, the research has included twenty-four respondents than expected in ethnographic research; he has focused on two schools. He has also shared the research purposes with his interviewees, contacts within the schools, and researchers he knows (Bryman, 2016, p.384). This process starts with the research proposal shared with relevant contacts and possible research participants. He gets relevant and valuable feedback and advice from his supervisor and colleagues for the different processes. Finally, to give readers a possibility to assess if he has been able to carry out the research in line with best research practices, he has also carefully described the methods used here in this chapter and how these are in line with the literature on research methods.

However, it is also important to admit that when researching technology-assisted language learning and teaching, the transferability of conclusions arrived at can be challenging. This thesis has shown that people with students are extremely homogenous; however, there must be a universal understanding of computer-assisted language teaching and learning.

4.14.2. Credibility

Credibility narrates whether the findings are believable. To form the credibility of the outcomes, the researcher tries to ensure that the research is carried out in line with best practices. It has also been important to share the findings with the informants and other interested people from the research sites where the research is carried out. In this way, he can get confirmation that what he has understood and emphasized in the findings is in line with how members of the researched community understand their situation. This form of member validation, or respondent validation, has allowed him to share the research and the findings (Bryman, 2016, p.384). At the end of the research findings, he returned to his research sites, showed their data, and discussed with the participants in February 2019. In this way, the participants have an opportunity to their data and to confirm or disconfirm the data and provide new perspectives to the research process. In their feedback, almost all interviewees confirmed that the research reflects their opinions and presents the situation as it is on the ground in the two schools.

4.14.3. Conformability

To ensure the conformability of the research, the investigator s critically assesses if his values and theoretical perspectives have influenced the research process and the conclusions arrived at to the extent that can make the research findings less trustworthy. It is reflected throughout this thesis. To allow readers to critically assess if his theoretical perspectives, presuppositions, and values have influenced the research to the extent that makes the findings less trustworthy, he has included a section describing his position as a researcher. It is also essential to recognize that no researcher can be completely objective (Bryman, 2016, p.384).

4.14.4. Dependability

The dependability of conclusions arrived at is parallel to reliability in qualitative research. To ensure dependability, the researcher has carefully written a comprehensive research log that documents and describes in detail the whole process of the research project. In addition, an anonymized version of the research log and all transcribed interviews will make available to assess if his theoretical approaches are justifiable and if the methods used are relevant and carried out according to the best research practices. In addition, it enables a sort of 'audit' of the research process, and the conclusions arrived at are more comprehensive than the criteria for evaluating reliability (Bryman, 2016, pp. 385-386).

4.14.5. Authenticity

To ensure the authenticity of the research, the researcher is, throughout the research process, and especially when synthesizing the findings and during the analysis, critically assessed to what extent different opinions and perspectives presented to him by the interviewees are captured and understood. He has also assessed if the research can help the research participants value different perspectives and understand their context better. It is done in discussions, and in one of the questions, the participants are asked to give anonymous responses (Bryman, 2016, p.386; Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, p.279).

It has been more challenging to assess if the research has sensitized and empowered participants to act to change their situation because the research process has been time limited. It may only be visible if the participants work after the research has been disseminated. The final thesis is submitted to the university. However, once, one participant will comment that some of the concepts described are advanced and difficult to understand. For example, the participant asks if an easy-to-read version of the thesis will be published. He is promised to write and share an easy-to-read version of the thesis and share this with all interviewees in addition to sharing this thesis. By doing this might be more likely that some people will have access to information that can inspire them to act (Bryman, 2016, p.386).

4.15 Limitations

Therefore, this research will not rely on only random sampling methods and will not represent the total population of language teachers, principals, and students in Bangladesh. Instead, the researcher will be able to attest to the reliability or validity of the secondary data. Thus, the secondary and interview data will be generalizable to the entire population of Bangladesh. This study will emphasize using qualitative criteria, which concerns validity and reliability, as outlined in credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Finally, the proposed research will be helpful to for EFL teachers to know about the practical ways of using technology in classrooms; the government agency will be able to understand the actual situation of classroom teaching by using technology and the possibilities and challenges of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in Bangladesh.

Research has consistently shown the value of computer-assisted language teaching and learning in every stage of education, mainly when applied appropriately, incorporating comfort,

enjoyment, and increased confidence in using a computer. However, unless tasks are explicitly tied to learning objectives, students do not recognize their instructional value and perceived CALL activities as doing more harm than good. Instead, studies should focus on studying the effects of CALL tasks. For example, research studies should look at tasks designed to develop one of the four specific skill areas, culture, motivation, or test preparation. These tasks must be clearly defined, and instructors and tutors must be trained to implement them effectively.

5. FINDINGS

This chapter presents the empirical data from the investigator's fieldwork and findings from the focus group discussions for students (sixteen higher secondary students divided into four groups) and eight individual interviews (six language teachers and two principals). The researcher organizes the data into five main categories: the purpose of technology use, technology for language teaching and learning, teachers' role in using technology, language websites for learning language, and suggestions and future possibilities based on the interview guides. He introduces the data chronologically, such as students, teachers, and principals. His research sites were two different schools: one in an urban area and the other in a rural area.

The first section (5.1) describes why people use Technology, significantly higher secondary students, based on their (students) experiences, teachers' experiences, and how often they use technology. The second section (5.2) points out how much students and teachers use technology to learn and teach English as a foreign language. The third section (5.3) describes the teachers' role in influencing using technology and data from focus group discussions. The fourth section (5.4) narrates the purpose of websites to learn a foreign language. Finally and the fifth section (5.5) describes how to improve the computer-assisted language learning situation in Bangladesh and how the future computer-assisted language learning setting will be in Bangladesh.

5.1 Purpose of using technology

Collected data from the focus group interviewees discusses in subsection 5.1.1, and individual interviewees' data from the teachers discusses in paragraph 5.1.2. Data from the individual interviewees, the principals, is unrelated to section 5.1.

5.1.1 Students' perspective of using Technology

One of the focus group participants (SA1) describes her purpose of technology use, that she can use a computer and smartphone at school. Using these devices, she learns a language, uses Facebook and podcast, and plays games. Another participant (SB2) also describes her feeling about using technology. She uses a computer and smartphone to enjoy different facilities to cope with modern techniques to get positive feedback (something good for the students). The new age depends on technology; with it, it is possible to fulfill their dream. Moreover, modern technologies are essential in learning a foreign language (SB2).

Another focus group participant (SA6) describes the purpose of technology use and that it has made their lives comfortable and facilitative; these devices have made their daily work easy and risk-free. She uses these devices for communication and entertainment and uses these devices for finding information, research, acquiring knowledge, scientific matter, distance communication, information exchange, and language learning (SA6).

SB8 does not use a computer, but he uses a smartphone and says that he does not use a computer but a smartphone. He uses it for communication, as a language-learning tool, and as

entertainment. SA2 also says like SB8; however, they are in a different group. She does not use ICT for language learning and communicates with their friends and family within a moment. Using these devices, she can do social work and browse the internet on Facebook and Twitter; by doing this, she learns a new language.

5.1.2 Teachers' perspective of using technology

"Many schools in Bangladesh arranged multimedia classes so they can take their class with technology" (TB3). One interviewee, TA2, describes the purpose of technology use, "At present, these types of technology-based class is possible in our college as it is arranged for the students and the teachers" (TA2). "We use Communicative language teaching (CLT method) to teach English, so we try to focus their language skills first. And for developing listening skills, we are obliged to use a multimedia class" (TA3). One individual participant TA1 says that in their classrooms in a country like Bangladesh, such kinds of use of technology are less. However, nowadays, it is being increased. TB1 describes his experiences with technology use and says that it is a technological period, our country has different technology, such as computers and mobile phones, and he uses a mobile phone. He has downloaded different dictionaries, similar words, and various topics most beneficial for his students and him. He applies these things in the classrooms for the benefit of students. (TB1)

TB3 describes that depending on the classroom situation, sometimes he uses smartphones and multimedia devices. TB2 says that the purpose of technology use with disheartening; they use various types of technologies according to the classroom situation. In rural areas, most students need help understanding what technology is. He motivates them to draw attention. He uses some pictures, audio, and videos using smartphones. These are difficult because they need to have available devices. As a result, they need to practice language learning. (TB2)

5.2 Technology for language teaching and learning

The researcher organizes data in subsection 5.2.1 for the students' interviewees and 5.2.2 for the teachers' interviewees. Principals are not entitled to discuss the technology for language teaching and learning, so they have yet to participate here.

5.2.1 Students' perspectives

One focus group participant SA1 describes technology for language learning; English is an international language. Everyone uses this language all over the world. So, it is the essential and primary thing to learn this language now. The influence of the English language is seen in technologies everywhere in the world. Technology can be a prodigious basis for learning the English language. (SA1)

Another focus group participant SA2 says that they use the internet for study in college, such as making an assignment, developing listening skills, and so on (SA2). SA3 also says they can learn English using TV, smartphones, and computers. She further says they can make friends from other countries via the internet and speak with them to develop language skills.

Another focus group participant SB6 says, "Now the world is called a global village for the sake of technology. We can learn language by using technology via the internet" (SB6).

SA6 says that English is difficult for them because of their mother tongue (different structure, so they need help learning English). Pronunciation is essential to learn, and it is not easy to learn pronunciation. Technology makes learning pronunciation and meaning easy. Technology plays a vital role in their life. (SA6)

One of the focus group interviewees says that using technology is very important to learn a language. They come to know various kinds of linguistic devices. If they make a mistake, they can solve it using technology, and sometimes it corrects automatically. They learn their mother tongue from childhood, but English is not their mother tongue. So, it is different for them to learn. They use technology to know the word's meaning and synonym. (SA7)

One of the focus group participants, SA8, says that to learn the English language, he can use technology and surf the internet by which he will get a solution to all his problems. For example, they can learn a language using Google, YouTube, Listserv, weblog, Facebook, and so on" (SA8). SB4 says technology can help them learn a language in many ways, such as watching YouTube videos for pronunciation or learning grammatical rules. They can also find synonyms or antonyms and learn how to write a paragraph, letter, and application from the web.

5.2.2 Teachers' perspectives

Teacher participant TB1 says that for language teaching, he uses multimedia classrooms and projectors to help the students improve their learning capability (TB1). One of the teachers' participants, TB2, says, "We can use a laptop and the multimedia classroom. One room is allotted for the students and decorated with technology. We can gather all the students in that room and take language classes there."

Photo 2: Only one room for taking a multimedia class which one of the teachers' participants mentions in school B (Photo credit AHM Abul Kalam Azad).

5.2.3 Homework

There was one interview guide about technology-based homework for the teacher participants, and the researcher got some data from them, which he describes below.

SB2 says that they can give them (students) homework like a paragraph or composition, not only they can give assignments related to technology (SB2). Another participant TB1 says that,

He always gives students homework and tells them to use technology. He keeps them consistently busy and gives them similar words and vocabulary. If the students develop their capability in English, they can get acceptable results and get routine jobs in the country or a competitive world. So, he keeps them giving operative words for the students, such as listening, reading, writing, and speaking, so they can use technology. (TB1)

SA3 presents his opinion about homework that now is the age of globalization, so most students have their Android mobile phones or laptops. He inspires them to practice English online, like pronunciation, listening, and speaking. They are very clever and can use them without hesitation because they are upper-level students, ages 16 to 18.

5.2.4 Internet and social network

The focus group discussion has an interview guide to discuss the internet and social network, and student participants represent their opinions. The investigator discusses below:

SA1 says that the well-being of technology spreads in their everyday life. The web is one of them, which is part of their daily life. She always uses the internet positively, and she gets great benefits from it. SA2 describes that learning a language using social media like Facebook, Twitter, Blogs, Podcasts, and WhatsApp is essential. There are lots of social media on the web, and there is some free online course on social media. They can use these sites to learn a foreign language. SA3 describes the importance of social media from her point of view; social media is essential to learn a language or English. Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, linked in, and different blogs are called social media. These websites inspire them to learn the language. They can make a group to learn a language by using social media, making foreign friends, and learning English. (SA3)

5.3 Teacher's role in using technology

One discussion was about how much teachers influence students to use technology, and they answered differently. The researcher discusses the data below:

SA1's views about teachers' role in influencing students using technology to learn a foreign language, their teachers sometimes influence them to learn a language using technology. They (teachers) always help them how to take help from technology for learning a foreign language. SA2 also describes her opinion, "Our teachers influence us to learn language by using technology and solve different types of difficulties. Teachers can solve grammatical problems like vocabulary, synonyms, and antonyms. Besides, we can find our solution using technology" (SA2). SA7 also says that language teachers inspire her to use technology in many ways. They teach them how to use Technology, how to search language websites and the

importance of learning a language. However, SA6 gives his opinion negatively. For example, it says that teachers do not influence him to learn a language using technology, and some teachers need to be more skilled in technology-based teaching.

5.3.1 Problems in using technology

There is one interview guide for teacher participants. What problems do teachers face when taking a multimedia class or implementing computer-assisted language teaching? The researcher gets available answers from the teacher participants and principal participants. He discusses the data below:

TA2 expresses his experiences and says, "We have the limitation of using a computer and do not have an excellent arrangement to give training for teachers. We have no available spaces." Furthermore, they have the little scope or need more time to think about using a computer, and they have so much load to take the class (TA2). TA3 also says that,

It is a widespread problem in Bangladesh because we need more instruments like computers and projectors, so we face many questions. Not only village students but also city students cannot always use multimedia in their classroom, so in English language learning, they cannot get the right way or lesson in their class for the lack of instruments. (TA3)

TB1 describes, "Ours is a developing country, not developed. Our country has many problems, and the electricity problem is one of the most common problems. When we use computers, we feel some electricity shortage" (TB1). Another participant also mentions the lack of electricity, "Sometimes we face lack of electricity and other logistic problem" (TB3). Two heads say almost the same about problems in using technology. HA1 said that our country's multimedia projectors and other devices are unavailable, and sometimes electricity is cut off. They cannot buy a generator because of the monetary problem. As a result, without electricity, teachers cannot teach students with technology. Instead, the government will take the initiative to make electricity available in the future. HB1 says, "Our institution locates in a rural area; for this reason, we cannot continue our multimedia class well because of load shedding. Sometimes we cannot get an internet connection properly."

5.3.2 Mobile technology for language learning

Bdnews24.com published a report referencing Bangladesh Telecommunication Regulatory Commission (BTRC) about mobile phone users and says more than 140 million people use the mobile phone out of Bangladesh's population of 160 million. So, it is a crucial tool for learning a language and a communication device. Almost 75 percent of participants responded to the mobile phone. Student participant SA1 says, "Mobile data brings everything in our hands. We can learn a foreign language by using mobile internet and mobile applications. These mobile applications and websites can help us learn English easily" (SA1). Another focus group participant SA2 says her point of view is that mobile internet brings everything in their hand. They can learn a foreign language by using mobile internet and mobile applications. These mobile applications and websites can help them learn English quickly (SA2). Another student participant SA3 says that mobile internet is beneficial to learning English, whereas he

watches TV programs to learn English. In class VIII, he watches a TV program and learns English. He can pronounce English words by using a mobile phone. He can speak English fluently now (SA3). All respondents emphasize the mobile phone as a learning tool. So, the researcher only mentions some of their comments here.

5.4 Language website for learning a language

There are some language websites, and the researcher has an interview guide about the language website, and they speak out about the language sites. There are many websites to train teachers and students to learn English. These websites discuss how to learn the English language and some practical exercises. For students' benefit, there are many practical classes, audio, and videos (SA1). "We can get a total solution to learn language by using language websites," says SA2. SA6 states, "English language learning websites are Google speak. Bangla to English dictionary, English to Bangla dictionary, and Google translation. He uses these apps to learn a language." Another focus group participant SB1 says that by using technology, he can browse language learning websites and gather knowledge about learning a language. Furthermore, he can communicate with world-famous language teachers (SB1).

On the other hand, SA3 answers that he does not use language-learning websites. However, in the future, he will use it. He knows that if he uses a learning website, he will be an English language expert and learn correct English. SA4 says that he does not use any language website to learn the English language (SA4), and says that he does not use language websites, but he watches English news on TV, Talk-show and reads English newspapers.

5.4.1 Distraction from a particular website

The investigator discusses distraction or diverting from a specific site with focus group participants. They participate in it and give data from their experience. He explains here that data.

SA2 says from her experience that when she searches for learning websites to learn a language or others, some unexpected web pages come to her, and sometimes she becomes curious about those websites. As a result, she browsed these websites instead of her expected websites. However, SA3 affirms that when she searches English language learning websites, sometimes she goes to other websites which are also learnable. It is not good but it happens. Another focus group participant SA6 says that in search of language learning websites, sometimes, she gets different film websites like porn or something like that, and sometimes she watches it. One of the participants, SB4, states about distraction, "When I search language learning program, I see some attractive and beautiful websites which attract me very much, and I browse these pages sometimes."

5.4.2 Comparison of web and physical materials

There is a comparison interview guide between web material and physical language learning materials for focus group participants, and they discuss that willingly. The researcher places that data here. SA1 says that internet materials are more natural and realistic than physical elements. It benefits the students, and he surfs the internet to search for different

websites to learn a foreign language. Internet materials are more useful and accessible than using physical books. Buying physical books takes too much money. (SA1)

SA3 said, "Internet-based materials are more authentic than printed books because it changes from time to time. So, internet-based materials are more effective than hard copies" (SA3). SA5 says differently: Internet-based study is more accessible than physical books. A teacher can teach easily using a projector, and he/she sends us teaching materials so the students can learn from them. Absent students can also get class materials via the internet. SA6 mentions, "Internet-based educational materials are more useful than those printed books. Students can learn quickly and remember many days the educational matter which determines by using the internet or technology, where we can see video and picture" (SA6). Almost all participants say internet-based teaching materials are more comfortable and practical than physical books. So, the researcher only writes quotes from them.

5.5 suggestions and future possibilities

At the end of the discussion, there are two questions about how to improve computer-assisted language learning and what and how the following language learning settings will be. First, almost all participants suggest enhancing computer-assisted language learning, and they talk about future possibilities for computer-assisted language learning in Bangladesh. In subsection 5.5.1, the researcher discusses implications and 5.5.2 future opportunities for CALL in Bangladesh. In the two paragraphs, he organizes data chronologically from focus group interviews, teachers' interviews, and principals' interview data.

5.5.1 Suggestions

Here the researcher provides data from focus group interviewees, and hopefully, all participants will give tips to improve technology-based language learning. However, he discusses a few of them. One of the focus group participants, SB4, says that if they want to improve computer-assisted language teaching in Bangladesh, they must learn how to operate technology-based language learning applications and must be conscious of the necessity of technology and how to use technology correctly and correct program (SB4). SB3 says her point of view, "Improving computer-assisted language teaching and learning, and we have to be aware of technology operating, usage of technology, to be attentive in learning a language to identify the misuse of technology" (SB4). SA6 describes,

To spread technology-based teaching and learning environments, we must be aware of people and related persons so that they can use technology. Technology and technology-related equipment will be available and cheaper. Also, the internet and internet devices will be available more reasonably and with excellent speed. (SA6)

SA2 says that if a country improves its technological knowledge and provides available facilities for students, teachers, and general people, language learning systems using technology will also automatically be enhanced. Our country needs to catch up in using technology compared to developed countries. The government can take the initiative to build ICT and arrange training and workshops so that students can get more facilities to learn a language

(SA2). SA3 suggests that to increase technology-based education; they must emphasize technology so that every student can get the facilities to use it. They must enrich social media with different kinds of learning tools. Schools and educational institutions can serve more technical support to the students to learn a language. Furthermore, they can train students to use a computer and other tools. (SA3)

The researcher collects data from teachers' interviewees and discusses some data from teachers' interviews. TB3 says, "We can take help from the computer in the teaching-learning process, and we can implement a new method to teach speaking and listening skills, and we can make lesson plans using technology." TB1 describes his suggestion that this is a competitive world and this is a technological period. Anyone who wants to utilize computer-assisted language teaching and learning must know how to use the first computer and other technological programs (TB1). TA1 describes that,

We cannot use modern tools and devices like computer technologies just now, for Bangladesh is developing or developing the country. Still, it is optimistic that Bangladesh is advancing and developing daily. A day will come when we will be able to do that, and everything will teach with the help of technologies, modern technologies like a computer; then, we will be able to do what our students expect from our nation or expect from us. (TA1)

TA3 suggests that every school should have a self-access center or language club and should manage a debating club in English. They should provide helpful information or materials for students. After appointing a teacher, management should give their training five or seven days. So, they can develop their technological skills. TA2 says that humans always love to learn spontaneously, and if we use a computer in our daily work, despite not having the intensity to use equipment or technology for being compelled, one day we will learn. Day by day, they will progress, and the country will benefit.

5.5.2 The possibilities of future language learning

In this subsection, the researcher discusses the opportunities for future language learning data from the respondents. Most participants gave their opinion on the following language learning environment, and he presented some selected data chronologically from the focus group, teacher respondents, and then principals. Focus group participant SA2's dreams for future language learning:

We developed ICT so that all people can get the facilities for IT. A new and developed education system allows all students to get technological facilities. If we can develop our technology, our education system will automatically expand. All education will be entirely free so all pupils can get education facilities. (SA2)

SB2 describes her future language learning environment, "Language learning in future will not be the same as present time, it will be changed. So, we must be kept fit for a future challenge. Language learning is fundamental to face the future competitive environment" (SB2). Now he discusses here collected data from the teacher participants. One of the

interviewees, TA2, says that today's children are the nation's future; what someone is doing does not matter; we should think about students. Total generation depends on students. If we can make them available technology, they will grow up with proper education (TA2). TA1 says that it is hopeful that Bangladesh is advancing and developing day by day. A day will come when we can do that, and everything will teach with the help of modern technologies like a computer. TB1 describes Bangladesh as a developing country, not a developed one. There are lots of problems in our country. First, teachers must train. Otherwise, we cannot grow in language teaching and learning situations. These are the deplorable situation in our country. If we can teach our students and teachers, we can expect good language teaching and learning situations in Bangladesh. (TB1)

TB2 says that English language learning will improve in Bangladesh. Students are interested in learning English because they use mobile, laptops, and computers. If they want to operate these technologies, they must learn English. So, in the future, most students will get an excellent environment to learn English.

The researcher interviewed two heads of institutions interested in implementing the CALL program. Their opinions are almost similar. They have some limitations, although they always try to manage everything for computer-assisted language teaching, and they hope to improve their language teaching classes. For example, one of the institution heads of HA1 says that English is a foreign language; as a foreign language, there is no way to present students straightforwardly. Computer-assisted language teaching has many forms, such as multimedia projectors, mobile, laptops, and smartphones. If we teach the students with the help of these devices, students will enjoy the class, and they will learn quickly.

They suggest improving computer-assisted language teaching and learning program in Bangladesh. HB1 says that all teachers must be skilled in teaching with computers and multimedia. If there is any lack, they must train up. We have some infrastructural deficiencies, so we must overcome these limitations. For example, we have 15 to 16 hundred students but only one multimedia classroom. If we overcome these limitations, we will teach students well. (HB1) HA1 says, "Now is the digital age, what we call computer age; there is no alternative option without a computer. Our teachers need suitable training so that they can compete with the competitive world."

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Overview

In this chapter, the researcher discusses and analyzes the results from the data and findings presented in chapter five of this research. This discussion and analysis of the results depend on his interpretation and description of the learning process, which is based on his experiences, observation, and reflection on the situation as it unfolded in the research process and the perceptions and views of the participants in this research. In this discussion, he also incorporates related aspects, theories, and concepts from various scholars where necessary to support his analysis of the results.

6.2 Discussion based on research questions

The research attempts to find the answers to three central research questions. First, the researcher discusses these three questions here according to the participants' replies. So, the participants' replies are connected to the investigated questions from the researcher's perspective.

6.2.1 How and to what extent do teachers and students use technology

The first question explores how and to what extent teachers and students use technology in the language teaching and learning process. The findings show that both schools provide computer and multimedia facilities in the classrooms to some extent. However, they can only provide computer and multimedia facilities in some classrooms, and teachers need more ICT skills to guide the students to learn a foreign language using technology. School A provides multimedia and computer facilities, with only five classrooms for language teaching and learning out of 51. However, it uses for language learning and computer teaching.

On the other hand, school B makes these facilities only in one out of 60 classrooms and uses them for other subjects. So, teachers and students only sometimes use technology in the language teaching and learning process, and they use it occasionally. Four teachers gave students homework that needed technological support; however, they did not always provide it. As a result, most teachers use computers and multimedia in their language classrooms for specific reasons.

However, the teachers who use computer and other technology also does not use them to the same extent. Some teachers use it frequently, while others use it sometimes and have limited users. Some teachers use it to show videos and for listening and speaking classes. Outside the classroom, the teachers depend on the internet to collect lessons and other teaching materials in some extreme cases, but they need to follow a specific website. Finally, they search on Google to find a suitable site. Some teachers use smartphones for listening and speaking classes because all classes have no computer or multimedia system.

They also face problems downloading materials from the internet, finding the appropriate website, dealing with the virus, handling devices like printers, scanners, projectors,

and many other issues. Most teachers are unaware of different e-tools for language teaching, as the findings show that only a few teachers know about podcasts though they have yet to use them in their classrooms. Facebook and blog are popular among teachers. Still, they never imagine or encourage to use them for teaching because they are informal, non-academic, and distracting elements for learning. Some teachers agree that Facebook and blog can use for education, and only one teacher uses Facebook for teaching purposes. However, it is apparent from the findings that teachers must be aware of the modern amenities of technology that make their language classes more interactive and enjoyable.

Also, their IT skills should emphasize or evaluate when recruiting. The interviews with the heads reveal that the schools need to consider teachers' knowledge of computers before hiring them. HB1 says that the prospective candidates must give a multimedia presentation where their IT skills are evaluated. From the responses, the language teachers need to be more up to date with computers and other technologies. Some teachers suggest that before training, the authority must understand the necessity of IT, and the schools' infrastructure needs to be improved. The heads are also very interested while discussing training in language teaching skills with technology. They agree to arrange training if their teachers need it, and they feel that training will be necessary or helpful for teaching language. So, it may be possible for them to arrange training on CALL for their teachers, and the heads are hopeful of improving their language classes with technology and the internet. However, they mention the shortcomings that they need to be able to enrich all their classrooms with technologies.

From the students' perspective, many use computers or smartphones. However, they only use these devices sometimes for language learning. They sometimes use technologies to communicate with others and use Facebook, Twitter, and Linked in. Comparatively, in some cases, they use technology more than those teachers; however, many students need to learn how to use these devices for language learning. For example, almost all students want to use technology for language learning purposes; if their teachers can adequately motivate them, for example, if the teachers become trained and technology-oriented, students can use these devices for language learning.

6.2.2 What are the challenges of computer-assisted language teaching and learning

The second research question deals with the challenges of using technology in language teaching and learning. One teacher says he has too much class load, so they cannot make their lesson useful with technological devices. Another teacher notes that more instruments are a big problem in implementing technology in the class. Two teachers mention the electricity problem. They have yet to take multimedia classes. In contrast, when they arrange one multimedia classroom for taking language classes, sometimes the electricity cuts off, and they have no generator or IPS facilities.

The heads also say that load shedding is one of the significant problems in teaching language learners in combination with technologies. One chief also says that internet speed is also another big problem. Internet still needs to be available in our institution; sometimes, internet speed is plodding, and it is tough to continue online classes with the speed we get.

Making the teachers comfortable using computers and technology has no alternative to training. In this regard, all teachers believe exercise is necessary to develop ICT skills. Training can help them to understand the advantages of CALL and to know the use of different CALL software and e-tools. All teachers preferred collaborative training or workshop programs involving IT or CALL experts. This type of training session will be more practical. It can be one day to one month longer. For example, one teacher adds that ELT, TEFL & TESOL training can be more operative for language teaching classes. On the social or religious restriction to use the internet and other devices, teachers of school A say that they do not face any problems or bindings.

On the other hand, teachers at school B say that they face this kind of problem and try to remove it by consulting female students' parents; male students have no restrictions. So, it assumes that the rural area has some religious or social restrictions on using technology for female students. All six teachers think the self-access center or language lab is essential for language learning. Unfortunately, none of the schools has a self-access center or language lab where students can learn languages at their pace using technology.

6.2.3 What are the prospects of computer-assisted language teaching and learning

The third research question discusses the prospects of using technology in future language teaching and learning. Almost all focus group participants believe that all language lessons will be multimedia, teachers will be ICT skilled, and all the classrooms will be technology equipped. One focus group participant says that Google would be more effective than the present situation in learning the language. All teacher participants say that technology will be available in schools and that the learning and teaching environment will be technology-based and web-based. One teacher participant says that everything (language teaching-related matters) will be taught with the help of technologies, modern technologies like computers and smartphones. The heads investigate the schools' existing facilities and their plan to improve them. They try to increase more for computer-assisted language learning, but they need available funds to enhance these facilities. Finally, the heads express their eagerness to listen to their teachers' and students' needs in the future.

6.3 Discussion based on the theoretical framework

In this section, the researcher discusses the related theory to the participants' answers mentioned in the theoretical framework. He also relates the section with the findings and theory discussed in the theoretical framework chapter. The findings of the central research questions suggest that since students are eager to use technology, teachers need the training to teach students properly. Therefore, the teachers are responsible for language teaching and teaching how to use technology for language learning.

First, epistemology. It is a part of philosophy that questions how much we know what we know. As philosopher endeavors to answer questions, they develop responses grouped in different institutes of thought. "These institutes of philosophical thought are rather forced; they are simply labels developed to show the resemblances and distinctions among the numerous responses philosophers acquire" (Johnson, Musial, Hall, Gollnick, & Dupuis, 2008, p. 102). Four well-known logical institutes of thought are idealism, realism, pragmatism, and

existentialism. Every one of the beliefs mentioned above has implications for education. The idealist trusts that the instructor is central to learning. Therefore, idealist minds emphasize speech, conversation, and replication. The realist sees the instructor's function as an individual who presents content in a methodical and organized technique. Contemporary pragmatists are behind standardized examinations, episodic textbooks, and specialized curricula for each discipline. The pragmatist stresses applying knowledge—using ideas for problem-solving. Realists and idealists are most closely related to behaviorists' theory of learning because they trust in a standardized curriculum centered on academic disciplines. Therefore, pragmatists desire an interdisciplinary curriculum and are most closely related to constructivists' theories about how students' study best (Johnson et al., 2008).

Also, the beginning of the 20th century ushered in a new school of behaviorism. Behavioral psychologists believe that "only perceptible, quantifiable, outward behavior is worthy of epistemological investigation" (Bush, 2006, p. 15). Because there appeared to be a link between the effects of strengthening on learning, scientists were considered connectionists reflecting the relationship between stimulus and response and conditioning. In other words, scientists believe all students can learn the same information given the appropriate environment. For example, the most recognized behaviorist of the time was B. F. Skinner, who believed that all learning was measurable through observing changed behavior. As scientific studies in psychology "continued to test the connection between stimulus and response (and classical and operant conditioning), limitations on the explanations of changed behavior developed a rift within behaviorism" (Bush, 2006, p. 16).

Moreover, according to Morrison, Ross, and Kemp (2004), the behaviorist learning theory emphasizes the effects of external conditions, such as rewards and punishments, in determining the future behaviors of students. The behaviorist learning theory focuses mainly on objectively observable behaviors and discounts mental activities. This approach emphasized the "acquisition of new behavior" (Bednar, Cunningham, Duffy & Perry, 1992, 150). Behaviorists believe that all behavior results from an individual's responses to outer stimuli (operant conditioning). In other words, behaviorists supposed that the peripheral situation contributed to shaping a personality's behavior. Behaviorists also believe that the setting triggered a specific behavior, and whether the behavior happens is dependent upon how a person is affected by the behavior.

Another point is a school setting, teachers use affirmative and negative reinforcements to either reward or punish a student's behavior. The behaviorist learning theory trusts extrinsic motivators such as grades, prizes, and privileges, as well as acknowledgments and praises, to ensure the replication of the intellectual activity or behavior. Teachers who follow the behaviorist learning theory would linearly present lesson objectives. In doing so, the teacher would offer hints or cues to guide pupils to a wanted behavior and then use consequences to strengthen the desired behavior. Behaviorists begin by introducing lower-level cognitive skills. The construction of higher-level cognitive abilities follows it. The problem with this type of direction is that lessons are concentrated on learning skills in isolation (Gonzalez, n.d.). Those who conflict with the behaviorist theory supposed that these theories failed to consider the

inspiration the mind has over behavior. Therefore, instead of involving learners in solving problems, behaviorists use processes of direct instruction (i.e., lecturing and teaching skills in isolation) and evaluate their learning based on their answers to questions on verbal or written tests. "After being the dominant paradigm in American psychology for some decades, behaviorism was overtaken by various research results that yielded anomalies revealing its limitations as an overall account of psychological functioning" (Wakefield, 2007, p. 170). As the field of psychology continued to evolve, researchers began to reject behaviorism and seek ways to identify cognitive processes in learned behaviors (Fisher, 2008). This led to the development of the field of cognitive science, which "includes the study of thinking, perception, emotion, creativity, language, consciousness and learning" (Harman, 2008, p. 76).

The most crucial theory is social constructivism theory; it also emphasizes the role of teachers and heads as it asserts that every learning community member can influence the teaching and learning process (Beck & Kosnik, 2006; Geijsel et al., 2009; Pritchard & Wollard, 2010). When we have something new to learn, we often seek a knowledge expert to help us gain new information and apply new skills; we seek a mentor or, as Vygotsky would say, a More Knowledgeable Other (MKO) (Yarbrough, 2019). Students need guidance; the ZPD is a gap analysis where the learning facilitator identifies the learner's ability to perform a task-independent and at what point the learner will require MKO support and guidance to complete a task (Yarbrough, 2019). Vygotsky (1978) argues that it is the space between independence and requiring advice, the ZPD, that learning occurs.

Figure 11: Zone of Proximal Development by Vygotsky (1978).

Meanwhile, the teachers of Bangladesh need to be made aware of the technology. They only use technology for a minimal purpose, and teachers need to use the computer properly for various reasons like lack of facilities, knowledge, and training. This finding conforms to Andersson's (2008) research that in developing countries like Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, the shortage of trained teachers is one of the obstacles to implementing computer-assisted language learning. Kessler (2006) also says that teacher preparation programs must remember to prepare their students with the necessary knowledge of technology. The situation in Bangladesh is very similar to Kessler's (2006) finding since the teachers need to familiarize themselves with using e-tools like Facebook, blogs, listserv, wiki, and podcasts for language learning. According to the theory of social constructivism, new knowledge should provide to the teachers based on

their previous knowledge (Beck & Kosnik, 2006). So, providing teachers with training is vital to develop teachers' professional experience. Training in IT would help them to be proficient in using technology for teaching. Their suggestion ranges from basic computer knowledge to sophisticated skills like creating a blog, developing a website, and producing a podcast.

Finally, Hagen (1993) determines that the successful execution of new technology into the language classroom requires special pre-condition: support of senior management, a whole-school approach, technology-literate teachers, technician support, a designated language learning accommodation (for example, soundproofing) and a budget for staff training, materials development, and the purchase of good-quality course material. Sharma & Barret (2007) also say that the lack of available funds affects technology usage in language learning. The factors cover the attitude of teachers and learners to technology, learners' level affecting the appropriate use of technology, teacher training related to the novelty of the technology, teachers' and learners' availability to access technology, and the cost factor of providing new technology. Hirvela (2006) and Son (2002) emphasize these skills for teacher education. Jones (2001) and Egbert et al. (2002) find that their administrative and class works often impede teachers' interest to CALL training.

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

7.1 Introduction

ICT can immensely help a dynamic teacher by enhancing the dual capacity of both learning and teaching. The present Government of Bangladesh has shown a solid commitment to introducing ICT in all fields, including education. Initiating a computer-assisted language program can be an auspicious beginning of that process. However, it is crucial to have trained teachers implement a computer-assisted language learning (CALL) program. In Bangladesh, CALL is an entirely new concept, and teachers may need to be more competent in teaching CALL programs. The schools also may not provide the necessary logistics required for CALL. So, this research aims to find the answers to the following research questions,

- *How and to what extent do teachers and students use technology in teaching and learning processes related to language learning in Bangladesh?*
- *What are the challenges of computer-assisted language teaching and learning in Bangladesh?*
- *What are the prospects of computer-assisted language teaching and learning in Bangladesh?*

Answering the above questions, the researcher randomly selects participants from the mentioned schools. The investigator interviews eight students, three language teachers, and one principal from each school. The interview is structured based on some interview guides. After collecting all the data, they are analyzed based on mixed research methods related to behaviorist and social constructivism theory.

7.2 Summary of the findings

The findings suggest that the schools need more facilities for CALL program implementations. Among the two schools, one school offers computer and multimedia in 5 classrooms, and the other has one multimedia classroom for English language teaching classes and other subjects. Still, the teachers often need more maintenance to use them. The principals give definite answers about their infrastructure. They admit that their facilities need to improve for the CALL program, but they are trying to provide more facilities for language teaching and learning classes. Teachers must be more competent in using computers, other technologies, and the internet. They face many problems while working on the computer. Many teachers deny that Facebook, blogs, and other social networking sites have proven beneficial for language teaching in much research. So, the language teachers at higher secondary schools in Bangladesh must update with CALL and recent technologies. So, training on CALL is necessary for language teachers. All teachers need CALL training, and the researcher advises training with CALL experts and IT professionals to arrange a successful training program. Furthermore, selected school principals show a positive attitude towards the training program.

7.3 Contribution to research

Since CALL is a new concept in Bangladesh, more research needs to be conducted in the Bangladeshi context, especially in higher secondary schools. So, this work can be a piece of literature on CALL in the Bangladeshi framework. The researcher has discussed different issues of e-learning in this research. Future researchers can take help from this thesis if they want to work on CALL. The relation between CALL and teacher's education also emphasizes in this thesis, which may help the researchers interested in teacher education and teacher educators.

7.4 Practical implication

After reading this dissertation, the readers will get introduced to different technological equipment and their role in language teaching and learning. The teachers can use these tools in their language classes. The study emphasizes the role of school authority in implementing CALL. So, the principals will realize their responsibility if they read this research work. They will also understand teachers' expectations and problems regarding computer-assisted language teaching. The researcher has proposed some suggestions for CALL training here. So, if any school wants to organize training or workshop for their language teachers, they can consider these suggestions. This study presents the overall situation of CALL at higher secondary schools in Bangladesh. So, the government and policymakers can visualize the actual scenario and take the necessary steps for this situation.

7.5 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following suggestions can be considered for the successful implementation of computer-assisted language learning and teaching:

- *The authorities need to rethink the necessity of technology for language teaching.*
- *They can include the requirement for ICT skills in their job advertisements that will encourage teachers to be ICT literate.*
- *The teachers should propose to the authority to establish required CALL facilities instead of depending on them.*

7.6 Further studies

This study focuses on two higher secondary schools in Dhaka city and another in the Comilla division (rural area). So, further studies can be done on the school situated in different areas in Bangladesh and can be covered more schools. This study only concentrates on two higher secondary schools' students, teachers, and two principals' points of view. Future researchers can include more school students, teachers, and principals' opinions. The research focuses on the necessity of teacher education and training required for computer-assisted language learning for better language teaching. However, according to Jones (2001), learners' knowledge and training in computer and ICT skills are also crucial for computer-aided language classes. So, one can further research learners' practice of CALL application.

7.7 Conclusion

Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is technology's critical role in the language classroom (Ehsani & Knodt, 1998). It uses computers and related facilities to enhance learning (Ehsani and Knodt). Though CALL started its journey in the 1960s based on the theory of behaviorism (Warschauer & Kern, 2000), it is quite a new dimension in Bangladeshi education. According to several researchers (Jones, 2001; Kessler, 2006), successful implementation of CALL requires trained teachers and the cooperation of the heads. So, this study endeavors to discover the existing facilities available in Bangladeshi higher secondary schools, the language teachers' knowledge of technology, and principals' attitude toward the execution of CALL. After the study, the investigator finds that all the schools need sufficient facilities for CALL, and the principals are conscious of the issue. The teachers also need to be made aware of the facilities of CALL.

Different tools of CALL (like Facebook, blog, podcast, and others) have yet to discover to them. They know about these tools only as social networking sites and consider them informal and non-academic. However, most teachers agree on the necessity of CALL training, while some try to refute the idea of training due to workload. When the researcher asks the principals about this matter, they respond positively. They are trying to enrich their institutions with technology, but they have available fund problems. They are willing to arrange a training program. However, this study presents some ideas the students, teachers, and principals propose for CALL. Based on the findings, in the Bangladeshi context, computer-aided language teaching will be successful only if schools can arrange available technology-enriched classrooms and provide teachers with training; other difficulties will demolish automatically.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Afrin, Naima (2014). Integrating Computer Assisted Instruction in the EFL Classroom of Bangladesh. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*. Volume 19, Issue 11, Ver. IV, PP 69-75.
- Akbar, M. S. (2005). E-learning in developing countries: Challenges and opportunities Bangladesh perspective. *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on E-learning for Knowledge-Based Society*. August 4-7, Bangkok.
- Akhter M. (2012). Computer assisted language teaching (CALT) in Bangladesh at tertiary level. Retrieved from: <http://dspace.ewubd.edu/handle/123456789/663>
- Anderson, G. (1990). *Fundamentals of educational research*. London: The Falmer Press.
- Andersson, A. (2008). *Letters from the field: E-learning students change of learning behavior in Sri Lanka and Bangladesh*. In Williams, R. and Remenyi, D. (Eds.). The proceedings of the 7th European conference on e-learning. Pp. 29- 37. UK: Academic Publishing Limited.
- Anwar, B. (2006). *Shikha Babosthapon Bishoyadi*. Dhaka: Ebong Porkashoni.
- Arthur, J., Waring, M., Coe, R., and Hedges, L.V. (2012) *Research Methods and Methodologies in Education*. London: Sage.
- Arts in Education Institute of Western New York (2002). Constructivist Learning Theory. Retrieved January 21, 2008, from, <http://www.artsined.com/teachingarts/Pedag/Dewey.html>
- Atkins, N. E. & Vasu, E. S. (2000). Measuring knowledge of technology usage and stages of concern about computing: A study of middle school teachers. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 8, 279-302.
- Bangs, P. and Cantos, P. (2004). What can computer assisted language learning contribute to foreign language pedagogy. *International Journal of English Studies-IJES*, Vol. 4 (1), 221-239.
- Barlett-Bragg, A. (2003). Blogging to learn. *Knowledge Tree E-journal*. Retrieved from http://knowledgetree.flexiblelearning.net.au/edition04/html/blogging_to_learn.html
- Bates, A. W. (1995). *Technology, Open Learning and Distance Education*. London and New York, Routledge, vii + 266 pp.
- Bax, S. (2003). CALL – Past, Present and Future. *System*, 31, 13-28.
- Beatty, K. (2003). *Teaching and researching: Computer-assisted language learning*: Pearson Education.
- Beck, C. and Kosnik, C. (2006). *Innovations in Teacher Education: A Social Constructivist Approach*. Albany: State University of New York press.
- Bednar, Cunningham, Duffy, & Perry (1992). Theory into practice: How do we link? *Handbook of research for educational communications and technology*.
- Bella, M. (2005). Weblogs in education. In B. Hoffman (Ed.). *Encyclopedia of Educational Technology*. Retrieved from <http://edweb.sdsu.edu/eet/articles/blogsined/start.htm>
- Berger, P., & Luckmann, T. (1991). *The Social Construction of Reality*. A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge. London: Penguin.

- Birks, M. & Mills, J. (2011). *Grounded Theory: A practical guide*. London: Sage Publications.
- Blattner, G. and Fiori, M. (2009). Facebook in language classroom promises and possibilities. *International journal of instructional technology and distance learning*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Bloor, M. et al. (2001). *Focus groups in social research*. London: Sage.
- Breidlid, A. (2005c). Ngugi's Matigari, a Non-Materialist Discourse and Post-Modernism. *The Australian Journal of Trans-national Writing*. Volume 1, February 2005.
- Breidlid, A. (2013). *Education, Indigenous Knowledges, and Development in the Global South*. Contesting Knowledges for a Sustainable Future. New York. Routledge
- Broadribb, S., Peachey, A., Chris, C. and West rap, F. (2009). *Using Second Life at the Open University: How the Virtual World Can Facilitate Learning for Staff and Students*. In C. Wankel and J. Kingsley. *Higher education in Virtual World: Teaching and Learning in Second Life* (pp. 204-218). Bingley: Emerald Publishing.
- Brown, T. H. (2006). Beyond constructivism: Navigation in the knowledge era. *On the Horizon*, 14(3), 108-118. Retrieved June 8, 2008, from ProQuest database.
- Bryman, A. (2008). *Social research methods*. 3rd edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods*. 5th edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bugeja, M. (2008). Second Thoughts about Second Life. *Education Digest*, 73(5), 18- 22.
- Bullen, M. (1997). *A Case Study of Participation and Critical Thinking in a University-Level Course Delivered by Computer Conferencing*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada.
- Bush, G. (2006). Learning about learning: from theories to trends. *Teacher Librarian*, 34(2), 14- 19.
- Campbell, A. P. (2003). Weblogs for use with EFL classes. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 9(2). Retrieved from <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Campbell-Weblogs.html>
- Carter, B. and Elseth, D. (2009). The usefulness of Second Life for language learning. In R. C. V. Mariott and P. L. Torres. (Eds.). *Handbook of Research on E- Learning Methodologies for Language Acquisition* (pp. 443-455). New York: Information Science Reference.
- Casey, M.A. & Kueger, R.A. (2000). *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research*. (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Charmaz, K. (2006). *Constructing grounded theory: A Practical Guide Through Qualitative Analysis*. Great Britain: SAGE Publications Inc.
- Chartrand, R. and Pellowe, B. (2007). ELTpodcast.com – A podcast and website for students and teachers of English language. *Proceedings of the 1st International Wireless Ready Symposium on Podcasting Education and Mobile Assisted Language Learning*. ISSN 1995-4557, <http://wirelessready.nucba.ac.jp/e proceedings2007.html>
- Chilisa, B. (2012). *Indigenous Research Methodologies*. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Chun, D. M. and Plass, J. L. (2000). *Networked multimedia environment for second language acquisition*. In M. Warschauer and R. Kern. (Eds.). *Network-based Language Teaching: Concepts and Practice* (pp. 151-170). Cambridge: Cambridge University press.
- Coffman, T. and Klinger, M. B. (2007). Utilizing virtual world for education: The implication for practice. *International Journal of Human and Social Science*, 2(1), 29-33.

- Cohen, L. & Manion, L. (2011). *Research methods in education*. (7th ed.). London: Routledge.
- Cohen, L. & Manion, L. (2018). *Research methods in education*. (8th ed.). London: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (Third). United States of America: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Danley, James, Mims & Simms (2014) *Behaviorism Theory and Its Relation to Instructional Design*. Retrieved from http://faculty.mercer.edu/codone_s/tco363/2014/behaviorism.pdf
- Darkenwald, G. & Merriam, S. B. (1982). *Adult education: Foundations of practice*. Cambridge: Harper & Row.
- Dashtestani, R. (2012). Barriers to the implementation of CALL in EFL courses: Iranian EFL teachers attitudes and perspectives. *The JALT call Journal 2012: Regular Papers*, 8, 55–70.
- Dawson, S. et al. (1993). A manual for the use of focus groups. *International Nutrition for Developing Countries (INDFC)*.
- Denscombe, M. (2007). *The good research guide for small-scale social research projects*. (3rd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2008). *Strategies of Qualitative Inquiry* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and Education*. New York, NY: The MACMILLAN Company.
- Dudeney, G. and Hockly, N. (2007). *How to Teach English with Technology*. Essex: Pearson Longman.
- Eastment, D. (2005). Blogging. *ELT Journal*, 59(4), 358-361.
- Eaton, S. T. (2010). How to use Skype in ESL/EFL classroom. *The Internet TSL Journal*, 16(11). Retrieved from <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Eaton-UsingSkype.html>
- Ebsworth, M. E., Feknous, B., Loyet, D. and Zimmerman, S. (2004). Tape it yourself: Videotape for teacher education. *ELT Journal*, 58(2), 145-154.
- Egbart, J., Paulus, T. and Nakamichi, Y. (2002). The impact of CALL institution on language classroom technology use: A foundation for rethinking CALL teacher education. *Language Learning and Technology*, 6 (3), 108-129.
- Ehsani, F. and Knodt, E. (1998). Speech technology in computer assisted language learning: Strengths and limitations of a new CALL paradigm. *Language Learning and Technology*, 2(1), 54-73.
- Erban, T., Ban, R. and Castaneda, M. (2009). *Teaching English Language Learners Through Technology*. New York: Routledge.
- Eslami-Rasekh, Z. (2005). Raising the pragmatic awareness of language learners. *ELT Journal*, 59(3), 199-208.
- Fadel, S. A & Bargi, A. A (2018). The Use of Humour in EFL Classrooms: Comparative Conversational Analysis Case Study. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*. Volume 9. Number 2, Pp. 262 -282. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol9no2.18>
- Fisher, P. (2008). learning about literacy: from theories to trends. *Teacher Librarian*, 35(3), 8-13.

- Fosnot, C.T. (1996). *Constructivism: Theory, perspectives, and practice*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Fotos, S. and Browne, C. (2004). *The development of CALL and current options*. In S. Fotos and C. Browne. (Eds.). *New Perspective on CALL for Second Language Classroom* (pp. 3-12). New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Gadomski, A. M. (1997). *Global TOGA Meta-Theory. The page since 1997*, Last small updating May. 2007, 2008. Retrieved from <http://erg4146.casaccia.enea.it/wwwerg26701/Gad-toga.htm>
- Gadomski, A. M. (2002). *High-Intelligence Paradigms*. Retrieved from <http://erg4146.casaccia.enea.it/HID/HI-def.htm>
- Gardner, D. and Miller, L. (1999) *Establishing Self-Access Center*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Geijsel, F. P., Slegers, P., Stoel, R. D. and Kruger, M. L. (2009). The effect of teacher psychological and school organizational and leadership factors on teachers' professional learning in Dutch schools. *The Elementary School Journal*, 109(4), 406-426.
- Gesche, A. (2009). Adapting to Virtual Third Space Language Learning Futures. In R. C. V. Mariott and P. L. Torres. (Eds.). *Handbook of Research on E- Learning Methodologies for Language Acquisition* (pp. 524-538). New York: Information Science Reference.
- Gibbs, A. (1997). Focus groups. *Social Research Update*, Issue 99, Winter 1997.
- Glaser, B. G. and Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The Discovery of Grounded Theory*. Chicago, IL: Aldane.
- Global Education Monitoring Report (2017/8). *UNESCO, 2017*. Paris 07 SP, France. Retrieved from: www.unesco.org/gemreport
- Godwin-Jones, R. (2003). Emerging Technologies: Blog and Wikis: Environment for Online Collaboration. *Language Learning and Technology*, 7(2). 12-16. Retrieved from <http://llt.msu.edu/vol7num2/emerging>.
- Gonzalez, J.C. (n.d.). Constructivism vs. direct Instruction. Retrieved January 21, 2008, from, *Harlandale Masters On-Line*.
- Gorman, G.E.& Clayton, P. (2005). *Qualitative research for the information professionals: A practical handbook*. London: Facet Publishing.
- Goulding, C. (1999). Consumer research, interpretive paradigms and methodological ambiguities, *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 33 Issue: 9/10, pp.859-873, <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090569910285805>
- Green, C. and Tanner, R. (2005). Multiple intelligences and online teacher education. *ELT Journal*, 59(4), 312-321.
- Greener, I. (2011). *Designing social research: a guide for the bewildered?* London or Cornwall: Sage Publications Inc.
- Gunduz, N. (2005). Computer Assisted Language (CALL). *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 1(2), 193-214.
- Gusterson, H. (2008). *Ethnographic Research*. In Klotz, A & Prakash, D. (Eds.), *Qualitative methods in International Relations: A pluralistic guide*. (pp. 93-113). NY: Palgrave Macmillan
- Hagen, S. ed. (1993). *Using Technology in Language Learning*. London: City Technology College Trust Limited.

- Hammersley, M. (2007). Ethnography: problems and prospects. *Evidence and Policy*, 1 (1), pp. 1-16.
- Harman, G. (2008). Mechanical mind. *American Scientist*, 96(1), 76-79.
- Hemingway, C. J., & Gough, T. G. (1998). *A socio-cognitive theory of information systems. RESEARCH REPORT SERIES-UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS SCHOOL OF COMPUTER STUDIES LU SCS RR*, (25), All-All,
Retrieved from
https://www.engineering.leeds.ac.uk/computing/research/publications/reports/1998/1998_25.pdf
- Hirvela, A. (2006). Computer-mediated communication in ESL teacher education, *ELT Journal*, 60(3), 233-241.
- Hjoerland, B. (2004). Domain Analysis: A Socio-Cognitive Orientation for Information Science Research. *Bulletin of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 30(3), 17-21.
Retrieved from <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bult.312/full>
- Holtman, L. (2009). Using Wikis in the teaching of a short course on history and philosophy of science. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 6(1), 29-37.
- Horvath, J. (2009). Hungarian students' blog in EFL: Shaping language and social connection. *TESL-EJ*, 12(4). Retrieved from <http://www.cc.kyoto-su.ac.jp/information/tesl-ej/ej48/int.html>
- Hugman, R., Pittaway, E. & Bartolomei, L. (2011). When 'Do No Harm' Is Not Enough: The Ethics of Research with Refugees and Other Vulnerable Groups. *The British Journal of Social Work*, Volume 41, Issue 7, October 2011, Pages 1271–1287,
<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcr013>
- Islam, M. N. (2023). Educational Discourses of Bangladesh: An Epistemological Evaluation of Primary Education. *IJISRT*. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7735516>
- Islam, M. T. and Selim, A. S. M. (2006a). Current status and prospect for e-learning in the promotion of distance education in Bangladesh. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE*, 7 (1), Retrieved from
<http://tojde.anadolu.edu.tr/tojde21/articles/islam.htm>
- Islam, M. T. and Selim, A. S. M. (2006b). Information and Communication Technology for the promotion of open and distance learning in Bangladesh. *Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development*, 4(1), 35-42
- Islam, S. (11 july, 2018). *Dhaka Tribune*.
Retrieved from <https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh/2018/07/11/digital-bangladesh-a-reality-now>.
- Johnson, J. A., Musial, D., Hall, G. E., Gollnick, D. M., & Dupuis, V. L. (2008). *Foundations of American education: Perspectives on education in a changing world* (14th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson Education Inc.
- Jones, J. F. (2001). CALL and Responsibilities of Teachers and Administrators. *ELT Journal*, 55(4), 360-367.
- Jones, P. W., (2007). Education and world order. *Comparative Education*, 43:3, 325-337,
DOI: 10.1080/03050060701556273

- Karl, L. C. (2011). *Elementary Teachers' Perceptions of Technology Proficiencies and Motivation to Integrate Technology in School Curriculum*. Washington: Walden University Press.
- Kasper, G. and Rose, K. (2003). *Pragmatics development in a second language*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Kavaliauskiene, G., Anusiene, L. and Maziukiene, V. (2006). Weblogging: Innovation for Communication in English. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 3(2), 220-233.
- Kern, R. and Warschauer, M. (2000). *Theory and practice of networked-based language teaching*. In M. Warschauer and R. Kern. (Eds.), *Network-based Language Teaching: Concepts and Practice* (pp. 1-19). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kern, R. and Warschauer, M. (2000). *Theory and practice of networked-based language teaching*. In M. Warschauer and R. Kern. (Eds.), *Network-based Language Teaching: Concepts and Practice* (pp. 1-19). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kessler, G. (2006). *Assessing CALL Teacher Training: What are we doing and what could we do better*. In P. Hubbard and M. Levy. (Eds.). *Teacher Education in CALL* (pp. 23-44). Philadelphia: John Benjamin.
- Khan, H. R. (2005). Perception of trainee teachers: Implication for effective teaching of English. *Stamford Journal of English*, 1 (summer 2005), 119-130.
- Khan, M. E. & Manderson, L. (1992). Focus groups in tropical diseases. *Research Health Policy and Planning*, Vol.7, No.1. 198 *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* Vol. 33, No. 1
- Khan, M.E. et al. (1991). The use of focus groups in social and behavioural research: Some methodological issues. *World Health Statistics Quarterly*, Vol. 414. Kitzinger, J. (1997). Introducing focus groups. *British Medical Journal*, Vol.311, 29 July.
- Kim, H. k. (2008). Beyond Motivation: ESL/EFL Teachers Perceptions of the Role of Computers. *CALICO Journal*, 25, 241-259.
- Kirovska, D. (2016). Do ESP Students Prefer Face-To-Face Instruction Over Digitally Embedded Instruction? Blogs vs. Reports? Debates vs. Online Discussion? *Science Direct. ELSEVIER. International Conference on Teaching and Learning English as an Additional Language, GlobELT 2016, 14-17 April 2016, Antalya, Turkey*. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/82524508.pdf>
- Kitzinger, J. (1995). *Qualitative Research: Introducing Focus Groups*. Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/15566389>, DOI: 10.1136/bmj.311.7000.299.
- Kluge, S. and Riley, L. (2008). Teaching in Virtual Worlds: Opportunities and Challenges. *Issues in Informing Science and Information Technology*, 5. Retrieved from <http://proceedings.informingscience.org/InSITE2008/IISITv5p127-135Kluge459.pdf>
- Knobel, M., Lankshear, C., Honan, E. and Crawford, J. (1998). *The weird world of second language education*. In I. Snyder. (Ed). *Page to Screen: Taking Literacy into the Electronic Era* (pp. 21-52). London: Routledge.
- Krueger, R. (1998). *Focus group: A practical guide for applied research*, London, Sage.
- Kruse, G. D. (1998). Cognitive science and its implications for education. *NASSP Bulletin*, 82 (598), 73-79.

- Kvale, S. & Brinkmann, S. (2009). *Interviews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*. (2nd ed.) Thousand Oaks, Calif.: Sage.
- Kvale, S. & Brinkmann, S. (2015). *Interviews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*. (3rd ed.) Thousand Oaks, Calif.: Sage.
- Lai, C. and Kritsonis, W. A. (2006). The advantages and disadvantages of computer technology in second language acquisition. *Doctoral Forum*, 3(1).
- Lam, Y. (2000). Technophilia vs. technophobia: A preliminary look at why second- language teachers do or do not use technology in their classrooms. *Canadian Modern Language Review*, 56, 389-420.
- Leahey, T. H. (2000). Control: A history of behavioral psychology. *The Journal of American History*, 87(2), 686-687.
- Lee, M.J.W., McLoughlin, C. and Chan, A. (2007). Talk the talk: Learner-generated podcast as a process for knowledge creation. *British Journal of Educational Technology*. 39(3), 501-521, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8535.2007.00746.x
- Lee, K. W. (2000). English teachers' barriers to the use computer-assisted language learning. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 6(12), Retrieved from <http://iteslj.org/Articles/Lee-CALLbarriers.html>
- Leffa, V. J. (2009). CALL as Action. In C. V. Mariott and P. L. Torres. (Eds.). *Handbook of Research on E-learning Methodologies for Language Acquisition* (pp. 39-52). New York: Information Science Reference.
- Levy, M. (1997). *Computer-Assisted Language Learning: Context and Conceptualization*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Levy, M. (2008). *Effective Use of CALL Technologies: Finding the Right Balance*. In R.P Donaldson and M.A. Haggstrom. (Ed.). *Changing Language Education Through CALL* (pp. 1-18). New York: Routledge.
- Mahrooqi A. R. & Troudi S. (2014). *Using Technology in Foreign Language Teaching*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/274380451>
- Malcolm, D. (2004). Why should learners contribute to self-access center? *ELT Journal*, 58(4), 346-354.
- Marshall, C. & Rossman, G. B. (2011). *Designing qualitative research* (Fifth ed.). United States of America: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2010). Using Numbers in Qualitative Research, Volume: 16 issue: 6, page(s): 475-482, [Doi.org/10.1177/1077800410364740](https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800410364740)
- Maxwell, J. A. (2013). *Qualitative research design: an interactive approach* (3rd ed. ed. Vol. 41). Los Angeles: Sage.
- Mayall, B. (2008). *Conversations with children: Working with generational Issues*. In P. Christensen & A. James (Eds.), *Research with children Perspectives and Practices* (Second Eds.). Great Britain: Routledge.
- Mazer, J. P., Murphy, R. E., & Simmonds, C. J. (2007). *I'll see you on "Facebook": The effects of computer-mediated teacher self-disclosure on student motivation, affective learning, and classroom climate*. *Communication Education*, 56(1), 1-17.
- Merton, R.K. et al. (1990). *The focused interview*. New York: Free Press.

- Miller, L., Shuk-Ching, E. T. and Hopkins, M. (2007). Establishing a self-access center in secondary school. *ELT Journal*, 61(3), 220-227.
- Mills, J. A. (1998). *Control. A history of behavioral psychology!* New York, NY: New York University Press.
- Morgan, D.L. (1997). *Focus groups as qualitative research*. Newbury Park: Sage.
- Morgan, D.L. & Krueger, R.A. (1993). *When to use focus groups and why*. In D.L. Morgan (ed.). *Successful focus groups: Advancing the state of the art*. Newbury Park: Sage.
- Morrison, G. R., Ross, S. M., & Kemp, J. E. (2004). *Design effective instruction*. Wiley Jossey- Bass. Hoboken, NJ.
- Nagel, P. S. (1999). Email in the virtual ESL/EFL classroom. *The Internet TSL Journal*, 5(7), retrieved on September 23, 2011 from <http://iteslj.org/Articles/Nagel-Email.html>
- National Education Policy (2010). Ministry of Education, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
- NCATE. (2008). Professional standards for the accreditation of teacher preparation institutions. Retrieved from <http://www.ncate.org/Standards/NCATEUnitStandards/tabid/123/Default.aspx>
- Newman, D. R., Webb, B., & Cochrane, C., (1995). A content analysis method to measure critical thinking in face-to-face and computer supported group learning. *Computing and Technology: An Electronic Journal for the 21st Century*, 3(2), 56-77.
- O'Sullivan, P. B., Hunt, S. K., & Lippert, L. R. (2004). Mediated immediacy: A language of affiliation in a technological age. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 23, 464-490.
- Overskeid, G. (2008). They should have thought about the consequences: The crisis of cognitivism and a second chance for behavior analysis. *The Psychological Record*, 58(1), 131-152.
- Park, C. N. & Son, J. B. (2009). Implementing Computer-Assisted Language Learning in the EFL Classroom: Teachers' Perceptions and Perspectives. *International Journal of Pedagogies and Learning*, 5, 1-25.
- Patra, C. C., Alam, M. Z. and Sobhan, M.A. (2010). Wimax Network Deployment for ICT Based E-Learning in Bangladesh: Challenges and Recommendation. *International Journal of Information System and Telecommunication Engineering*, 1(1), 39-46.
- Patton, M.Q. (2002). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods*. (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Pellettieri, J. (2000). Negotiation in cyberspace: *The role of chatting in the development of grammatical competence*. In M. Warschauer and R. Kern. (ed.). *Network-based Language Teaching: Concepts and Practice* (pp. 59-86). Cambridge: Cambridge University press.
- Pisel, K. (1995). An analysis of distance learning applications for joint training. *Journal of Interactive Instruction Development*. Summer, pp. 12-23.
- Pouzevara, S. L. and Khan, R. (2007). Learning communities enabled by mobile technology: A case-study of school based in-service secondary teacher training in rural Bangladesh. *Technical Assistance Consultant Report*. Project no. ADB TA, 6278-REG.
- Pozzobon, C. (2008). Podcast and Literature. *Entre Lenguas*, 13, 111-115.

- Pritchard, A. and Wollard, J. (2010). *Psychology for Classroom: Constructivism and Social Learning*. New York: Routledge.
- Quader, D. A. (2005). Teachers training for teachers of English: A project of National University. *Journal of the Institute of Modern Language*, 17 and 18, 1-27.
- Rahman, A. (1998). English teaching in Bangladesh: Problems and Prospects. *Journal of the Institute of Modern Language*, 8, 95-101.
- Rahman, M. M., Hamzah, M. I. M. Meerah, T. S. M & Rahman, M. (2010). Historical Development of Secondary Education in Bangladesh: Colonial Period to 21st Century. *International Education Studies (ICS)*. Vol. 3, No. 1. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/42386202_Historical_Development_of_Secondary_Education_in_Bangladesh_Colonial_Period_to_21st_Century
- Randall, M. and Thornton, B. (2001). *Advising and Supporting Teachers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Reeves, T. C. (1998). The impact of media and technology in schools: A research report Prepared for The Bertelsmann Foundation [Supplemental Material]. Athens Academy. Retrieved from http://www.athensacademy.org/instruct/media_tech?reeves0.html
- Rice, P. L. & Ezzy, D. (1999). *Qualitative research methods: A health focus Oxford*. Oxford University Press.
- Ritchie, J. & Lewis, J. (2003). *Qualitative Research Practice. A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. London/Thousand Oaks/ New Delhi: Sage, 336 Seiten, ISBN 0-7619-7110-6 (pbk), GBP 21,75/EUR 36,90
- Robinson, J. (2010). Awesome insights into semantic variation. *Advances in Cognitive Sociolinguistics*, 45, 85. Retrieved from <http://books.google.com>
- Robertson, E. B.; Ladewig, B. H.; Strickland, M. P., & Boschung, M. D. (1987). Enhancement of self-esteem through the use of computer-assisted instruction. *Journal of Educational Research*, 80 (5), 314-316.
- Rotfeld, H. H. (2007). Theory, data, interpretations, and more theory. *The Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 41(2), 376-380.
- Rummel, E. (2008). Constructing cognition. *American Scientist*, 96(1), 80-82.
- Shield, G. (2000). A critical appraisal of learning technology using information and communication technologies. *Journal of Technology Studies*.
- Said, Edward (2003). *Orientalism*. Penguin Group, London.
- Schewinhorst, K. (2002). Evaluating tandem language learning in the MOO: Discourse repair strategies in a bilingual internet project. *Computer Assisted Language learning*, 15(2), 135-145.
- Scheyvens, R. & Storey, D. (2003). *Development Fieldwork: A Practical Guide*. (R. Scheyvens & D. Storey Eds.). Padstow, Cornwall: Sage Publications.
- Scheyvens, R., Nowak, B. and Scheyvens H. (2003). *Ethical Issues*. In Scheyvens, R., Nowak, B. and Scheyvens H. (eds.) *Development Fieldwork. A Practical Guide*, London: SAGE Publications, pp. 139-166.
- Scheyvens, R., Murray, W. E., & Scheyvens, H. (2003). *Working with Marginalised, Vulnerable or Privileged Groups*. In R. Scheyvens & D. Storey (Eds.), *Development Fieldwork: A Practical Guide*. London: SAGE Publications.

- Schreiber, D. A. (1998). How to Maximize Use of Technology and Institutionalize Distance Learning Efforts. *14th Annual Conference on Distance Teaching and Learning*. August 5-7. Marriott, Madison West, Madison, WI: University of Wisconsin System.
- Seileek, A., (2004). Designing a computer-assisted language learning (CALL) program and testing its effectiveness on students' writing ability in English. Ph.D. Thesis, Amman Arab University for Graduate studies, Amman – Jordan.
- Sharma, P. and Barret, B. (2007). *Blended Learning: Using technology in and beyond the language classroom*. Oxford: Macmillan Education.
- Sherblom, J. C., Withers, L. A. and Leonard, L. G. (2009). *Communication challenges and opportunities for educators using second life*. In C. Wankel and J. Kingsley. (Eds.) *Higher Education in Virtual World: Teaching and Learning and in Second Life* (pp. 29-46). Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Ltd.
- Shield, G. (2000). A critical appraisal of learning technology using information and communication technologies. *Journal of Technology Studies*.
- Simpson, J. (2002). Computer-mediated Communication. *ELT Journal*, 56 (4), 414- 415.
- Skinner, B. F. (1948). *Walden Two* Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company.
- Sternberg, R. Applying psychological theories to educational practice. *American Education Research Journal*, 45(1), 150-166).
- Smith, E. (2012). *Secondary data*. In J. Arthur. M. Waring, R. Coe and L. V. Hdeges (eds) *Research Methods and Methodologies in Education*. London: Sage, pp. 125-30.
- Smythe, S. and Neufeld, P. (2010). “Podcast Time”. Negotiating digital literacies and communities of learning in a middle years ELL classroom. *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy*. 53(6), 488-496, doi: 10.1598/JAAL.53.6.5
- Soares, D. A. (2008). Understanding class blogs as a tool for language development. *Language Teaching Research*, 12(4), 517-533.
- Solichin, A. & Munandar, H. (2018). Improving learning access for students and teachers with e-learning system in the Mitra Bintaro Junior High School, Tangerang city. *ICCD (International Conference on Community Development)*, 1 (1), 2018, 1-7, E-ISSN 2622-5611. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33068/iccd.v1i1.2>
- Son, J. B. (2002). Online discussion on a CALL course for distance language teachers. *CALICO Journal*, 20(1), 127-144.
- Sotillo, S.M. (2000). Discourse function and syntactic complexity in synchronous and asynchronous communication. *Language Learning and Technology*, 4(1), 82- 119.
- Stewart, D.W. & Shamdasani, P. N. (1990). *Focus groups: Theory and practices*. Newbury Park: Sage.
- Sultana, S. F. (2005). Towards organizing a teacher development movement: Bangladesh perspective. *Stanford Journal of English*, 1, 69-76.
- Sutton, L. (2000). Vicarious interaction in a course enhanced through the use of computer-mediated communication. *Unpublished doctoral dissertation*, Arizona State University, Tempe.
- Swertz, C., Schultz, R. and Toifl, K. (2009). Language Teaching in Live Online Environments. In R. C. V. Mariott and P. L. Torres. (ed.). *Handbook of Research on E-Learning Methodologies for Language Acquisition* (pp. 509- 523). New York: Information Science Reference.

- Taylor, R. & Gitsaki, C. (2003) *Teaching well and loving it*. In Fotos & Browne (Ed.), *New perspectives on CALL for second language classrooms* (pp. 131-147). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Taylor, R. and Gitsaki, C. (2004). *Teaching well and loving IT*. In S. Fotos and C. Browne. (Eds.). *New Perspective on CALL for Second Language Classroom* (pp. 131-14). New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Timucin, M. (2006). Implementing CALL in an EFL Context. *ELT Journal*, 60(3), 262-271.
- Tucker, V. (1999). *The Myth of Development: A Critique of the Eurocentric Discourse*. In R. Munck and D. O'Hearn (eds). *Critical Development Theory – contributions to a new paradigm*. London: Zed Books.
- Van Dijk, T. A. (2009). *Critical Discourse Studies: A Socio-cognitive Approach*. Retrieved from <http://www.discourses.org/OldArticles/Critical%20discourse%20studies.pdf>
- Vavrus, F., (2009). The cultural politics of constructivist pedagogies: Teacher education reform in the United Republic of Tanzania. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 29: 303-311.
- Veer, E. A. V. (2010). *Facebook: The Missing Manual*. Sebastopol: O'Reilly Media.
- Vygotsky, L. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological processes*. Harvard: Library of Congress.
- Wakefield, J. C. (2007). Is behaviorism becoming a pseudoscience? Replies to Drs. Wyatt, Midkiff and Wong. *Behavior and Social Issues*, 16(2), 170-190.
- Warschauer, M. (1996). Comparing face to face and electronic discussion in second language classroom. *CALICO Journal*, 13(3), 7-26.
- Warschauer, M. (1996). Motivational aspects of using computers for writing and communication. *Telecollaboration in foreign language learning*, 29-46.
- Warschauer, M. (2000). "CALL for the 21st Century" *IATEFL and ESADE Conference*, 2 July 2000, Barcelona, Spain. Retrieved from <http://www.gse.uci.edu/markw/cyberspace.html>.
- Warschauer, M. (2002). A Developmental Perspective on Technology in Language Education Author. *TESOL Quarterly*, 36, 453-475.
- Warschauer M., Zheng B., Niiya M., Cotton S. & Farkas G. (2014). Balancing the One-To-One Equation: Equity and Access in Three Laptop Programs. *EQUITY & EXCELLENCE IN EDUCATION*, 47(1), 46–62, 2014, University of Massachusetts Amherst School of Education, DOI: 10.1080/10665684.2014.866871
- Warschauer, M. & Kern, R. (2000). *Theory and practice of network-based language teaching*. In M. Warschauer & R. Kern (Eds.), *Network-based language teaching: Concepts and practice*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Wassilew, A. Z. (2014). A socio-cognitive approach to semantic analysis and categorization processes. *Online Journal of Applied Knowledge Management*. Volume 2, Issue 2. Retrieved from http://www.iiakm.org/ojakm/articles/2014/volume2_2/OJAKM_Volume2_2pp172-181.pdf
- Watson, J. B. (1930). *Behaviorism* (rev. ed.). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Webb, J. L. (2007). Pragmatism (Plural) part I: Classical pragmatism and some implications for empirical inquiry. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 41(4), 1063-1087.

- WGHB (1998). A science odyssey: People & discoveries. Retrieved May 20, 2008, from, <http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/aso/databank/entries/bhskin.html>
- Weegar, M. A. & Pacis, D. (2016). A Comparison of Two Theories of Learning -- Behaviorism and Constructivism as applied to Face-to-Face and Online Learning. *Chinese American Scholars Association (CASA)*. Retrieved from <https://www.g-casa.com/conferences/manila/papers/Weegar.pdf>
- Weininger, M. and Shield, L. (2001). *Orality in MOO: Rehearsing Speech in Text: A Preliminary Study*. In K. Cameron. (Ed.). CALL—The Challenge of Change (pp. 89-96). Exeter: Elm Bank Publication.
- Wellington, J. (2015). *Educational Research: Contemporary Issues and Practical Approaches* (Second ed.). London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Wesley, B. E., Krockover, G. H., & Hicks, C. R. 1985. Locus of control and acquisition of computer literacy. *Journal of Computer-Based Instruction*, 12(1), :12-16.
- Wisker, G. (2001). *The postgraduate research handbook*. U.K.: Palgrave.
- Wood, E. (2006). The Ethical Challenges of Field Research in Conflict Zones. *Qualitative Sociology*, 29(3), 373-386. doi:10.1007/s11133-006-9027-8
- Yarbrough, J. R. (2019). Adapting adult learning theory to support innovative, advanced, online learning - WVMD Model. *Research in Higher Education Journal*, Volume 35. Retrieved from: <http://www.aabri.com/manuscripts/182800.pdf>
- Yasmeen, S. (2005). Theoretical approaches to teacher education and supervision. *Harvest*, 20, 111-120.

Appendix

Appendix 1: Interview guides focus group interview

- ◆ How and what purpose do you use your computer or smartphone?
- ◆ How does technology help you in English Language learning process?
- ◆ What do you think using technology for language learning?
- ◆ How do you use internet at home or school?
- ◆ How does mobile based internet help you in English language learning?
- ◆ How does online chatting develop your English language learning?
- ◆ Which program helps you more in your English language learning process?
- ◆ How do you feel internet materials to be easier and more realistic than physical materials in your English language learning?
- ◆ What do you think using social network for language learning?
- ◆ How do you use language website for English language learning?
- ◆ How does language teacher influence you to use technology in language learning?
- ◆ How do you follow your teachers' instructions on using computer for language learning?
- ◆ How do you distract or divert from a particular search of English language learning using internet?
- ◆ How do you suggest improving computer-assisted language teaching and learning?
- ◆ What are the possibilities for future language learning? Please explain.

Appendix 2: Interview guides for individual interview (Teachers)

- ⇒ What kind of technologies do you use in the classroom for language teaching and for what purpose?
- ⇒ Which Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) programme do you use in your language teaching?
- ⇒ How do you design computer assisted activity for students' language learning class? Please explain?
- ⇒ How can technologies help English as a Foreign language (EFL) learners in teaching?
- ⇒ What kind of training or workshop will be helpful for the teachers to introduce them with Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL)?
- ⇒ How do you manage your self-access center or language lab' necessity in the school?
- ⇒ What type of homework do you give students for which might need to take help of technologies?
- ⇒ What kind of conflict like Religious restriction or Social constraints among students using web-based program and how do you overcome?
- ⇒ How do you experiencing using computer or other logistics in language classes?
- ⇒ What is your suggestion to improve computer-assisted language teaching and learning?
- ⇒ If I ask you for future language teaching and learning situation of Bangladesh, how do you evaluate it? Please explain.

Appendix 3: Interview guides for individual interview (Heads)

- How do you evaluate Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes in Bangladesh?
 - What do you think about infrastructure for CALL programme?
 - If the teachers demand for more logistic support for computer assisted language course, will the school fulfill that demand? Why or why not?
- What skills do you focus when you appoint a teacher for English language department?
- What kind of training can improve your teachers' computer skill to teach better in EFL class?
- If you find that the teachers perform better after training, will you be interested to arrange any kind of training for the teachers? Please explain.
- What kind of opportunity do you have to use computer or any other devices in English Language class (Teachers and students)?
- How do you experiencing using technology in English language classes?
- What is your suggestion to improve computer-assisted language learning?
- What are the possibilities for future language learning? Please explain.

Appendix 4: Participants list

Code Name	School Name	Age	
SA1	School A	17	Focus group interview 1 with girls from School A were all first year higher secondary business studies group.
SA2	School A	16	
SA3	School A	17	
SA4	School A	18	
SA5	School A	18	Focus group interview 2 with boys from School A were all first year higher secondary humanities group.
SA6	School A	17	
SA7	School A	19	
SA8	School A	16	
SB1	School B	16	Focus group interview 3 with girls from School B were all first year higher secondary level.
SB2	School B	18	
SB3	School B	17	
SB4	School B	17	
SB5	School B	18	Focus group interview 2 with boys from School B were all first year higher secondary humanities group
SB6	School B	16	
SB7	School B	17	
SB8	School B	17	
TA1	School A	40	3 Individual interviews from school A and all are language teachers. They are all masters in English.
TA2	School A	29	
TA3	School A	25	
TB1	School B	28	3 Individual interviews from school B and all are language teachers. They are all masters in English.
TB2	School B	45	
TB3	School B	50	
HA1	School A	52	2 Individual interviews for the Heads of School A & B. They are experienced and Masters.
HB1	School B	49	

Appendix 5: Research sites on the MAP

8

⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Portal:Bangladesh/Map#/media/File:Un-bangladesh.png>